

IJCSIS Vol. 19 No. 12, December 2021
ISSN 1947-5500

**International Journal of
Computer Science
& Information Security**

© IJCSIS PUBLICATION 2021
Pennsylvania, USA

Indexed and technically co-sponsored by :

AUTHOR SERIES

Indexing Service

IJCSIS has been indexed by several world class databases, for more information, please access the following links:

Global Impact Factor

<http://globalimpactfactor.com/>

Google Scholar

<http://scholar.google.com/>

CrossRef

<http://www.crossref.org/>

Microsoft Academic Search

<http://academic.research.microsoft.com/>

IndexCopernicus

<http://journals.indexcopernicus.com/>

IET Inspec

<http://www.theiet.org/resources/inspec/>

EBSCO

<http://www.ebscohost.com/>

JournalSeek

<http://journalseek.net>

Ulrich

<http://ulrichsweb.serialssolutions.com/>

WordCat

<http://www.worldcat.org>

Academic Journals Database

<http://www.journaldatabase.org/>

Stanford University Libraries

<http://searchworks.stanford.edu/>

Harvard Library

<http://discovery.lib.harvard.edu/?itemid=|library/m/aleph|012618581>

UniSA Library

<http://www.library.unisa.edu.au/>

ProQuest

<http://www.proquest.co.uk>

Zeitschriftendatenbank (ZDB)

<http://dispatch.opac.d-nb.de/>

IJCSIS

ISSN (online): 1947-5500

Please consider to contribute to and/or forward to the appropriate groups the following opportunity to submit and publish original scientific results.

CALL FOR PAPERS

International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS) January-December 2022 Issues

The topics suggested by this issue can be discussed in term of concepts, surveys, state of the art, research, standards, implementations, running experiments, applications, and industrial case studies. Authors are invited to submit complete unpublished papers, which are not under review in any other conference or journal in the following, but not limited to, topic areas.

See authors guide for manuscript preparation and submission guidelines.

Indexed by Google Scholar, DBLP, CiteSeerX, Directory for Open Access Journal (DOAJ), Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE), SCIRUS, Scopus Database, Cornell University Library, ScientificCommons, ProQuest, EBSCO and more.

Deadline: see web site

Notification: see web site

Revision: see web site

Publication: see web site

Context-aware systems
Networking technologies
Security in network, systems, and applications
Evolutionary computation
Industrial systems
Evolutionary computation
Autonomic and autonomous systems
Bio-technologies
Knowledge data systems
Mobile and distance education
Intelligent techniques, logics and systems
Knowledge processing
Information technologies
Internet and web technologies, IoT
Digital information processing
Cognitive science and knowledge

Agent-based systems
Mobility and multimedia systems
Systems performance
Networking and telecommunications
Software development and deployment
Knowledge virtualization
Systems and networks on the chip
Knowledge for global defense
Information Systems [IS]
IPv6 Today - Technology and deployment
Modeling
Software Engineering
Optimization
Complexity
Natural Language Processing
Speech Synthesis
Data Mining

For more topics, please see web site <https://sites.google.com/site/ijcsis/>

For more information, please visit the journal website (<https://sites.google.com/site/ijcsis/>)

Editorial Message from Editorial Board

It is our great pleasure to present the **December 2021 issue** (Volume 19 Number 12) of the **International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS)**. High quality research, survey & review articles are proposed from experts in the field, promoting insight and understanding of the state of the art, and trends in computer science and technology. It especially provides a platform for high-caliber academics, practitioners and PhD/Doctoral graduates to publish completed work and latest research outcomes. According to Google Scholar, up to now papers published in IJCSIS have been cited over **19950 times** and this journal is experiencing steady and healthy growth. Google statistics shows that IJCSIS has established the first step to be an international and prestigious journal in the field of Computer Science and Information Security. There have been many improvements to the processing of papers; we have also witnessed a significant growth in interest through a higher number of submissions as well as through the breadth and quality of those submissions. IJCSIS is indexed in major academic/scientific databases and important repositories, such as: Google Scholar, Thomson Reuters, ArXiv, CiteSeerX, Cornell's University Library, Ei Compendex, ISI Scopus, DBLP, DOAJ, ProQuest, ResearchGate, LinkedIn, Academia.edu and EBSCO among others.

A great journal cannot be made great without a dedicated editorial team of editors and reviewers. On behalf of IJCSIS community and the sponsors, we congratulate the authors and thank the reviewers for their outstanding efforts to review and recommend high quality papers for publication. In particular, we would like to thank the international academia and researchers for continued support by citing papers published in IJCSIS. Without their sustained and unselfish commitments, IJCSIS would not have achieved its current premier status, making sure we deliver high-quality content to our readers in a timely fashion.

"We support researchers to succeed by providing high visibility & impact value, prestige and excellence in research publication." We would like to thank you, the authors and readers, the content providers and consumers, who have made this journal the best possible.

For further questions or other suggestions please do not hesitate to contact us at ijcsiseditor@gmail.com.

A complete list of journals can be found at:
<http://sites.google.com/site/ijcsis/>

IJCSIS Vol. 19, No. 12, December 2021 Edition

ISSN 1947-5500 © IJCSIS, USA.

Journal Indexed by (among others):

Open Access This Journal is distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source.

Bibliographic Information

ISSN: 1947-5500

Monthly publication (Regular Special Issues)
Commenced Publication since May 2009

Editorial / Paper Submissions:

IJCSIS Managing Editor

(ijcsiseditor@gmail.com)

Pennsylvania, USA

Tel: +1 412 390 5159

IJCSIS EDITORIAL BOARD

IJCSIS Editorial Board	IJCSIS Guest Editors / Associate Editors
Dr. Shimon K. Modi [Profile] Director of Research BSPA Labs, Purdue University, USA	Dr Riktesh Srivastava [Profile] Associate Professor, Information Systems, Skyline University College, Sharjah, PO 1797, UAE
Professor Ying Yang, PhD. [Profile] Computer Science Department, Yale University, USA	Dr. Jianguo Ding [Profile] Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Norway
Professor Hamid Reza Naji, PhD. [Profile] Department of Computer Enigneering, Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran, Iran	Dr. Naseer Alquraishi [Profile] University of Wasit, Iraq
Professor Yong Li, PhD. [Profile] School of Electronic and Information Engineering, Beijing Jiaotong University, P. R. China	Dr. Kai Cong [Profile] Intel Corporation, & Computer Science Department, Portland State University, USA
Professor Mokhtar Beldjehem, PhD. [Profile] Sainte-Anne University, Halifax, NS, Canada	Dr. Omar A. Alzubi [Profile] Al-Balqa Applied University (BAU), Jordan
Professor Yousef Farhaoui, PhD. Department of Computer Science, Moulay Ismail University, Morocco	Dr. Jorge A. Ruiz-Vanoye [Profile] Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Morelos, Mexico
Dr. Alex Pappachen James [Profile] Queensland Micro-nanotechnology center, Griffith University, Australia	Prof. Ning Xu, Wuhan University of Technology, China
Professor Sanjay Jasola [Profile] Gautam Buddha University	Dr . Bilal Alatas [Profile] Department of Software Engineering, Firat University, Turkey
Dr. Siddhivinayak Kulkarni [Profile] University of Ballarat, Ballarat, Victoria, Australia	Dr. Ioannis V. Koskosas, University of Western Macedonia, Greece
Dr. Reza Ebrahimi Atani [Profile] University of Guilan, Iran	Dr Venu Kuthadi [Profile] University of Johannesburg, Johannesburg, RSA
Dr. Dong Zhang [Profile] University of Central Florida, USA	Dr. Zhihan Iv [Profile] Chinese Academy of Science, China
Dr. Vahid Esmaeelzadeh [Profile] Iran University of Science and Technology	Prof. Ghulam Qasim [Profile] University of Engineering and Technology, Peshawar, Pakistan
Dr. Jiliang Zhang [Profile] Northeastern University, China	Prof. Dr. Maqbool Uddin Shaikh [Profile] Preston University, Islamabad, Pakistan
Dr. Jacek M. Czerniak [Profile] Casimir the Great University in Bydgoszcz, Poland	Dr. Musa Peker [Profile] Faculty of Technology, Mugla Sitki Kocman University, Turkey
Dr. Binh P. Nguyen [Profile] National University of Singapore	Dr. Wencan Luo [Profile] University of Pittsburgh, US
Professor Seifeidne Kadry [Profile] American University of the Middle East, Kuwait	Dr. Ijaz Ali Shoukat [Profile] King Saud University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Riccardo Colella [Profile] University of Salento, Italy	Dr. Yilun Shang [Profile] Tongji University, Shanghai, China
Dr. Sedat Akleyek [Profile] Ondokuz Mayıs University, Turkey	Dr. Sachin Kumar [Profile] Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Roorkee

Dr. Basit Shahzad [Profile] King Saud University, Riyadh - Saudi Arabia	Dr. Mohd. Muntjir [Profile] Taif University Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Dr. Sherzod Turaev [Profile] International Islamic University Malaysia	Dr. Bohui Wang [Profile] School of Aerospace Science and Technology, Xidian University, P. R. China
Dr. Kelvin LO M. F. [Profile] The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong	Dr. Man Fung LO [Profile] The Hong Kong Polytechnic University
Dr. Nitish Pathak [Profile] Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, New Delhi, India	Dr. T. V. Surya Narayan [Profile] Chandigarh University, Chandigarh, India
Dr. S. Sophia [Profile] Sri Krishna College of Engineering and Technology, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India	

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. PaperID 01122101: A Depression Detection Model using Deep Learning and Textual Entailment (pp. 1-8)

*Manar Elshazly, Mohamed Hassan Haggag, Soha Ahmed Ehssan
Faculty of Computers and Artificial Intelligence, Helwan University, Cairo, Egypt*

Full Text: PDF [[Academia.edu](#) | [Scopus](#) | [Scribd](#) | [Archive](#) | [DOI](#) | [Google Scholar](#)]

2. PaperID 01122102: Performance Evaluation of Random Forest Algorithm in Cluster Environment (pp. 9-12)

*Cinantya Paramita, Catur Supriyanto, Yani Parti Astuti, Lukman Afi Syariffudin, Fauzi Adi Rafrastara
Department of Information Engineering, Faculty of Computer Science, Universitas Dian Nuswantoro, Semarang, Indonesia*

Full Text: PDF [[Academia.edu](#) | [Scopus](#) | [Scribd](#) | [Archive](#) | [DOI](#) | [Google Scholar](#)]

3. PaperID 01122103: An Improved Meta-Heuristic Oriented Early Size Estimation Utilizing ABC (pp. 13-18)

*Manisha, Research Scholar, U.I.E.T (M.D.U), Rohtak, India
Dr. Rahul Rishi, Professor, U.I.E.T (M.D.U), Rohtak, India*

Full Text: PDF [[Academia.edu](#) | [Scopus](#) | [Scribd](#) | [Archive](#) | [DOI](#) | [Google Scholar](#)]

4. PaperID 01122104: A Critical Analysis of Learning Technologies and Informal Learning in Online Social Networks Using Learning Analytics (pp. 19-31)

*Audu Kafwa Dodo, Department of Computer Science, Taraba State University Jalingo, Nigeria
Ezekiel Uzor Okike, Department of Computer Science, University of Botswana, Gaborone, Botswana*

Full Text: PDF [[Academia.edu](#) | [Scopus](#) | [Scribd](#) | [Archive](#) | [DOI](#) | [Google Scholar](#)]

5. PaperID 01122105: Design and Development of an Autonomous Car using Object Detection with YOLOv4 (pp. 32-35)

*Rishabh Chopda, Department of Computer Engineering, Thakur College of Engineering & Technology, Mumbai, India
Saket Pradhan, Department of Information Technology, Thakur College Of Engineering & Technology, Mumbai, India
Anuj Goenka, Department of Computer Engineering, Thakur College of Engineering & Technology, Mumbai, India*

Full Text: PDF [[Academia.edu](#) | [Scopus](#) | [Scribd](#) | [Archive](#) | [DOI](#) | [Google Scholar](#)]

6. PaperID 01122106: (IoT-based Peat Soil Heat Conduction Parameter Delivery System As Land Fire Mitigation Effort pp. 36-41)

*Ade Agung Harnawan, Physics Study Program, University of Lambung Mangkurat (ULM), Banjarmasin, Indonesia.
Muhammad Itqan Mazdadi, Computer Science Study Program, University of Lambung Mangkurat (ULM),
Banjarmasin, Indonesia.
Nugroho Adi Pramono, Physics Department, State University of Malang, Malang, Indonesia,*

Full Text: PDF [Academia.edu | Scopus | Scribd | Archive | DOI | Google Scholar]

7. PaperID 01122107: Analyze Cyber Attacks in Cloud Cryptography and Short Comings in Blockchain Cryptocurrency (pp. 42-49)

*Ravikumar Ch, Dr. Isha Batra & Dr. Arun Malik
Computer Science and Engineering, Lovely Professional University, Punjab, India.*

Full Text: PDF [Academia.edu | Scopus | Scribd | Archive | DOI | Google Scholar]

A Depression Detection Model using Deep Learning and Textual Entailment

Manar Elshazly #¹, Mohamed Hassan Haggag #², Soha Ahmed Ehssan #³

Faculty of Computers and Artificial Intelligence

Helwan University, Cairo, Egypt

¹manar.elshazly@gmail.com

²mohamed.haggag@fci.helwan.edu.eg

³dr.soha@fci.helwan.edu.eg

Abstract—Depression detection nowadays is essential to help in supporting depressed people. Detecting emotional disturbance is currently remarkable in people who suffer from depression, and yet for doctors and psychologists to help them in detection. Nowadays, social networks can be utilized to determine depressive content and thus depressed people. To accomplish this, twitter is used to collect the most recent tweets that is related to depression. This is done by PHQ-9 technique that classifies depression into 9 degrees. Each degree is represented by set of words. Using this classification, the model can alert users that need a have a visit to a psychiatrist or ask a psychologist as soon as possible based on their social content. The collected dataset is then trained using deep learning and then experimented with different tweets from the collected dataset to validate the model. In addition, with textual entailment, the model can determine whether the tweet is entailed or not from tweets used in the training phase, and thus will follow the same class. By combining deep learning with textual entailment, our model resulted in an improved and quicker depression detection.

Index Terms—deep learning ; depression detection ; Textual entailment ; PHQ-9 ; Social Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Depression detection is a major public health concern. Depression is the head problem of disability and contributes significantly to a load of disease worldwide. People with depression may have a lack of interest and happiness in daily activities, weight loss or heavy gain, insomnia or excessive sleep, lack of energy, inability to concentrate, feelings of worthlessness or guilt and recurring thoughts of death (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). As a matter of fact, depression can lead to suicide. Over 800.000 suicide deaths occur every year and it is the second leading cause of death in the 15-29 years-old range; that is, every 40 s a person dies due to suicide somewhere in the world (World Health Organization, 2014). In wealthier nations, men are three times more likely to commit suicide than women. Globally, suicides account for 50% all violent deaths in men and 71% in women (World Health Organization, 2014). Suicide accounted for close to 1.5% of all deaths worldwide, bringing it into the top 20 leading causes of death in 2015 (World Health Organization, 2017). In the United States, as well as in other high-income countries, suicide is among the 10 leading causes of death (along with cancer, heart disease, stroke, and diabetes),

additionally, from 2016 to 2017 the suicide rate increased by 3.7% (National Center for Health Statistics, 2019). As divided depression level into three classes as represents in [1]. This model also separate depression classes to the same levels but at [1] they decided those levels depending only 100 words they detected them from users tweets they supposed these words based on Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC) but in Our model more than 1000 words based on recent PHQ-9 as will be decribed later.

This paper contributes new dataset of depressed user using PHQ-9 that were collected during the last year with all nowadays problems and depressed reasons. It also proposes a high performance classification model using deep learning techniques which facilitate massive data training . Also, the paper contributes a novel textual entailment depression detection process that helps to extract the depression level for new tweets without re-classifying data.

The rest of paper was split as the following: Section II presenting literature review about depression detection models that used deep learning technique. section III explains the different parts of the proposed model . Section IV discusses experimental results and the evaluation of the proposed model. Finally, the conclusion and future direction and enhancements are discussed in section V.

II. PREVIOUS WORK

In textual entailment deep learning techniques are becoming gradually usable, exceeding the complexity of standard models with complex precision and imagination. In a neural network, deep learning turn into a widespread technique of machine learning due to the state-of-the-art accommodation of computer vision, speech recognition, and other areas[2]. Training huge datasets are the latest fulfillment, from images classification for object recognition to suitable machine translation texts. In spite of this information being now is widely available in the public domain, private information collected on an individual basis not only expands the motivation of current models but also provides new deep learning enhancements. Considering deep learning as the leading technology with the latest applications. Deep learning of successful activities that immediately identify text, image, or sound can be learned with

computer models. Deep learning models achieved higher accuracies that sometimes exceeded human-level performance[3]. Bi-directional GRU (Bi-GRU) is an extension to GRU and is proven suitable for lexical analysis task, in which the input is an entire sentence. Thus, it is important to have the future encoded as well as the history. In particular, a reversed direction GRU is combined with a forward GRU to form a Bi-GRU layer. These two GRUs take the same input but train in different directions, and concatenate their results as output. Deep, hierarchical neural networks can be efficient at representing some functions and modeling varying-length dependencies. Therefore, stacking multiple Bi-GRUs to form a deep network becomes an inevitable choice for improving the representation capability[4].

The repeating bidirectional Gated Recurrent unit is first used as a word-level encoder to capture the context information of the annotations. GRU is a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) that can capture sequence information and sentence dependencies over a long period. Only two reset gate functions are used and upgrade the gates. The renewal gate monitored the rate of data of the previous session that is transferred to the current session. The higher the value of the update gate, the higher the status of the prior build-up. The reset gate monitored the extent to which previous data of the ignored status. When the value of the reset gate is low, the context will be overlooked. Both previous and next texts influence the current word in consecutive texts. Where [5] was used GRU and its results exceeded the LSTM model by 0.03% and it explained that GRU is more specified than LSTM with true negative rate. And as mentioned in [6] only based RNN models is suitable for processing data sequence in their dataset such as GRU and LSTM. So the BiGRU model was used to exclude contextual features. GRU was used to get text and classify it in [7]. GRU was get high performance with text with random sample of classification depression tweets by good accuracy that was 76%. As in [8] they used BI-GRU to encode pattern of texts and it raised accuracy to +80%. Also [9] used the Bi-GRU to get users' tweets, and then use it for classifying user tweets. Where it got reasonable accuracy with 76.4%. The same technique is already used in [10] as an investigation the validity of a claim given based on matters relating to prior verification. That also significantly increased the preceding accuracy.

PHQ-9 is a questionnaire that is a multidisciplinary tool for diagnosing, monitoring, screening, and evaluating the severity of stress. PHQ-9 incorporates the DSM-IV (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders) diagnosis of depression and other vital depressive symptoms into a short reporting tool. The tool measures the frequency of the symbols that are included in the point size index. Question 9 on PHQ-9 screens of presence and duration of suicidal idea¹. The follow-up question, which does not score points on PHQ-9 screens and provides weight to the extent to which stressful issues

have affected the patient's performance level. Model [11] was used GRU to predict the score of PHQ-9 to detect depression of pre-collected dataset by DAIC-corpora 2019, where using more than one of deep learning classification model such as CNN and LSTM with development set score 0.696 and testing set score 0.497 and they aim to use so much complicated techniques to enhance their results in the future. Models [12], [1], and [13] are used lexical similarity techniques to collect words for classification. After researching most papers didn't entailment concept where our model used it to facilitate classification and detect direct the level of depression. We proposed semantic similarity models to determine from which tweet with which level that the input tweet was.

III. PROPOSED MODEL

We depicted a literature review analysis in [14] and researched many related works done in the depression detection using machine learning and deep learning. We concluded that using textual entailment with deep learning can enhance the detection. So, this research a novel model that use deep learning and textual entailment is proposed. Fig.1. shows the framework of our proposed model which begins with collecting dataset using PHQ-9, then altering users with high depressive content. Then, the deep learning is used in the classification of depression levels, and finally textual entailment is applied. All of these steps will be described briefly in the following subsections.

Fig. 1. Depression detection model with entailment

¹<https://pdf4pro.com/view/the-patient-health-questionnaire-phq-9-overview-4c0057.html>

A. Data Collection

The dataset was collected from twitter using tweepy depending on depression lexicon represents in Fig 2. This lexicon was mapped using PHQ-9(the Patient Health Questionnaire-9) technology that is a questionnaire about depression and its levels. This questionnaire is formulated with words and terms defined by psychiatry experts. PHQ-9 technique determined the extent of a person’s depression that is divided into 9 signals. We used more than 1000 words or terms and the model has collected a massive dataset suitable for deep learning. Some lexicon that used in collecting our data are represented in Table I.

Fig. 2. Data Collection Using PHQ-9

Recent tweets were gathered within the period from 23/07/2021 to 04/08/2021, 150 tweets per word or term. The

TABLE I
SOME PHQ-9 WORDS THAT WAS USED IN DATA COLLECTION

Depression Level	PHQ Signal	Symptoms of PHQ-9	Some Words of each Signal
Low	PHQ 0	Lost of interest	lack of joy,lost desire, no joy,no purpose, fed up,no motivation, hiding sadness,zero passion
	PHQ 1	Hopeless and feeling down	being lonely,bad day, breaking down,cry, day ruined,destroyed, disappointed,feeling blue, I am sad
	PHQ 2	Sleep Disturbance	active at night,awake, sleep loss,groggy, night owl,let me sleep, over slept,hibernate
Medium	PHQ 3	Lost of energy	did nothing, exhausted, feeling tired, laziness, sedentary, tired, weakness,motionless
	PHQ 4	Eating Disturbance	big tummy, binge eating, chunky, cut down on fat, dieting, feeling chubby, poor appetite, weighty
	PHQ 5	Let yourself down	I am useless,despicable, ignored,I am nobody, feel ashamed,loser, repulsion,worthless
High	PHQ 6	Concentrating Trouble	absent-minded, daydreamer, disturbed, lase focus, mindless, overthinking, unfocused, zone out
	PHQ 7	Laziness or Hyperactivity	anxiety,angry,annoyed, hysteric,stressed out, panic ,poky,restless, straggler ,unsteady
	PHQ 8	Death Wish or Suicide	better be dead,cut my life, deathly,deserve to die, harm myself, lifeless, kill myself , suicide

Model uses regular expression to remove retweets, special characters, websites’ links and keep only words and numbers. Then it returned all of tweets with username and date for each tweet in a cleaned dataset.

As in [15] PHQ-9 has 9 categories, in our model we re-categorized them into three categories. Low level category that includes (PHQ0 to PhQ2) , Medium level category that includes (PHQ3 to PHQ5) , and High level category that includes (PHQ6 to PHQ8). This new categorization is used for the first part of the model. After editing and filtering the dataset, and removing duplicate tweets the dataset’s size reached 67000 distinct records.

B. High depression user alert

In this step, the model groups tweets by user so that all tweets of each user is categorized using the three categories mentioned in the previous subsection.So, the model takes the name of this user and collects all the tweets that have high level depressive content and if the number of tweets contains more than five high depressed tweets, the system collects the names of all these Users in a new Dictionary. The system then

send an alert message to those users to visit a psychiatrist as soon as possible.

Fig. 3. Extract depressed user by making dictionary of names

Fig. 4. Classification Using Deep learning

C. Deep Learning Classification

To overcome the complexity of various traditional models with complex settings and views, deep learning techniques are becoming very popular in the textual entailment process. Deep learning in neural networks has become a popular method of machine learning due to the recent success of computer vision, speech recognition, and other areas. The latest success is in training large datasets, from object recognition for classified images and machine translation texts. While such information is widely available from public sources, personal data collected from humans not only enhances existing applications but also extends new motivation for deep learning. High accuracy can be accomplished in deep learning applications, sometimes beating human-level achievements.

BI-LSTM: LSTM represents short-term memory networks, used in the Deep Learning field. A variety of recurrent neural networks (RNNs) can learn long-term dependence, especially in consecutive prediction problems. When LSTM works in both directions it is called BI-LSTM [16]. BI-GRU:Bi-GRU [8] edgecontains advanced forward GRU and background GRU which are used, respectively, to process forward and

backward data . Deep learning has become popular in the textual entailment scope, conquering the elaboration of several ordinary models with complex ideas.In this work we used two deep learning techniques, GRU and LSTM and their bidirectional models.

First, the categories are mapped into numbers from 0 to 3 to where 0 is neutral, 1 is low , 2 is medium and 3 is high. The data is splitted into three parts: training, testing, and validation. Model put tweet into X and category into Y. Then, X is tokenized into words followed by padding into vertex to prepare it to be input the deep learning models.

This model applied GRU, and Bidirectional GRU [9],LSTM, and LSTM [17] .These mechanisms were noticed to obtain depression tweets, which the model then used for depression classification.

D. Textual Entailment

Recognition of textual entailment sometimes is called inference of natural language. That is the task of determining the distribution of two pieces of text that the translation of one

text can be translated into another text[18]. The relationship-connected action, sometimes three connections can occur between two sentences, is textual entailment. Entailed is the meaning of one sentence can be collective with another sentence, Not Entailed is the meaning of one text that disagrees with the meaning of another sentence, and the Neutral is the meaning of another text that does not add or contradict the meaning of another sentence. Or maybe divided into two categories (Entailed / Neutral)[19].

1) *Entailment using Lexical Similarity*: Lexical similarity has many famous techniques . We used the following methods to take entailment decision by calculating distance similarity between T,H in each one , then calculated the sim(T,H) after that depending on their results to take lexical decision [20]..

- 1) Shapira and sorter’s greedy edit distance method has two significant characteristics than other edit distance algorithms. It considers characters blocks if it appears in both text and hypothesis strings, so the editing distance between ‘abcab’ and ‘abc’ is only 1, as the substring, ‘ab’ comes from both and can be inserted as ‘abc’ blocks. Allows three editing functions: add, delete, and move (but not replace). So the distance between ‘abcde’ and ‘deabc’ is only 1 because the ‘abc’ block can be moved to 1 movement function, rather than removed and placed in 2 different functions. If the key is set to True at startup, this uses a greedy algorithm, which limits block switching to two strings with the same LCS matching .
- 2) BI-SIM similarity:it is based on n-gram, based on measuring the distance similarity.Where n-gram calculated by the following equations. when sequences of words are as in the equation 1 Probabilities of these words presented in equation 2 and bi-gram of these probabilities from equation 3 ,So n-gram probabilities likes equation 4

$$w_1^n = w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n \tag{1}$$

$$p(w_1^n) = p(w_1), p(w_2|w_1), p(w_3|w_1^2) \dots p(w_n|w_1^{n-1}) \tag{2}$$

$$p(w_1^n) = \prod_{k=1}^n p(w_k|w_{k-1}) \tag{3}$$

$$p(w_1^n) = \prod_{k=1}^n p(w_k|w_{k-n+1}^{k-1}) \tag{4}$$

- 3) Cosine similarity : Cosine similarity between two text computed from equation 5

$$sim_{cosine}(T,H) = \frac{|T \cap H|}{\sqrt{|T| \cdot |H|}} \tag{5}$$

- 4) normalized eudex hamming :it restores the normal range of Hamming between Eudex hashes for two words or texts.
- 5) SSK : String subsequence kernel (SSK) similarity. All that can follow is the vectors of the feature and the kernel includes their dot product as in the equation 6

$$k_{normalization}(T, H) = \frac{k(T, H)}{\sqrt{k(T, T) * k(H, H)}} \tag{6}$$

2) *Entailment using Semantic Similarity*: we just use two semantic similarity.

- 1) Sentence-Transformers-Bert:It puts a map of the sentences and paragraphs in the 768 density vector and can be used for tasks such as merging or semantic search [21].BERT uses a cross-encoder.it passed two sentences to network and then predict value of similarity.
- 2) Spacy:it depends on estimating semantic similarity. Estimated cosine similarity using the word vector measurement[22].

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

After collecting the dataset it is saved as csv containing 67161 distinct records , each record has User names, Date of tweet, Tweet’s content , and level of depression depending on PHQ-9 lexicon , Table II represents sample of collected dataset.

TABLE II
COLLECTED DATASET SAMPLE

user name	date	tweet	level
User1	08/02/21 10:32 AM	You can t tell me that the lack of joy comes from a country so divided that half of the idiotic population	low
User2	08/02/21 10:59 AM	I thought Joy came in the morning Well it s the morning and there s no joy in my life What s all that about huh	low
User3	08/04/21 11:51 AM	Man I can t never decide what I want to eat Tired of eating everything really	medium
User4	07/28/21 06:28 PM	anuraax feeling like a loser actually	medium
User5	08/04/21 11:58 AM	another dr apt today another day filled with anxiety and ptsd triggers	high
User6	08/01/21 06:01 PM	But I knew what I had to do I have to kill myself	high

The model is evaluated using Accuracy from Eq.7 which is mean to number of correct prediction to number of total dataset as described before in [12]. From equation 8 and equation 9 Precision and Recall which is computed to get F1 Score as described in equation 10.Where TP are true positives, TN are true negatives, FP is false positives and FN are false negatives as mentioned in [23].

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \tag{7}$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \tag{8}$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \tag{9}$$

$$F1 - Score = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} \tag{10}$$

when applying GRU , LSTM and Bi-directional models to our dataset, BI-GRU got the best results. We trained, tested, and validated our dataset with a batch size equals to 500 , no. of epochs =20 ,drop out size of any network = 0.4 ,vocabulary size that we applied our models on it was 5000 , with 32

hidden layer for every DL model , and finally embedding size was equaled to 60. Evaluation splitting parameter was testing on 90%,80%,70% for training with dividing equally the remaining for testing and validation.

The results showed that the 90% splitting was stable and better than two other splitting parameters fig 5 depending on the best Accuracy for each model within 20 epochs.GRU, BI-GRU, LSTM,and ending with BI-LSTM got 0.8195, 0.8240 , 0.8160, and 0.8248 respectively.These results are represented in figures Fig 6.,Fig 7. , Fig8. , Fig 9.

Fig. 5. Evaluation Splitting Parameters(Accuracy)

Fig. 6. Accuracy Using GRU training by 90%

Finally our evaluation of the deep learning step in the proposed model is mentioned in Table III .Accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score is presented for each model separately but only for the best evaluation splitting as mentioned before 90% for training ,5% testing, and also 5% validation.

TABLE III
MODELS EVALUATIONS COMPARISON

Models	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
GRU	0.8094	0.8492	0.7774	0.8117
BI-GRU	0.8182	0.8294	0.8091	0.8192
LSTM	0.8055	0.8101	0.8025	0.8063
BI-LSTM	0.8132	0.8194	0.8085	0.8139

After classification, the entailment process is followed. We tried two types of textual entailment, lexical similarity and

Fig. 7. Accuracy Using Bi-GRU training by 90%

Fig. 8. Accuracy Using LSTM training by 90%

Fig. 9. Accuracy Using BI-LSTM training by 90%

semantic similarity. which proved that the semantic similarity gives reasonable decision near to expert detection.Table IV contains some of classified collected tweets by deep learning as (Text) and the new tweets to be classified as (Hypothesis). Table V represents entailment decisions of the sample pairs in tableIV using lexical techniques. We tried different types of lexical methods, and the results were quite similar, so we took average of five lexical similarity techniques that was

mentioned in the proposed model to get the best realistic results. For semantic similarity, we used two famous similarity measure semantic similarity Spacy and sentence-transformer-BERT separately.

TABLE IV
TEXT (CLASSIFIED TWEETS BY DEEP LEARNING) AND
HYPOTHESIS(TWEETS TO BE CLASSIFIED BY TEXTUAL ENTAILMENT)
EXAMPLES

No.	Text	Hypothesis
1	being alone for a while is dangerous it s addicting once you see how peaceful it is you don t want to deal with people any	major play people who dislike this song are against joy and happiness idc this such mood lifter helped much when depression started
2	Let s not equate a rise in COVID cases with people dying Feeling crappy for 2 days isn t worth compromising your freedom	the lancet normal anxiety and depression works negatively your immune system thats why they scare for virus equal flue
3	2am Hearing cries of the children amp firing like fire crackers in the background as I talk to a friend	gavinnewsom can you speed for teachers and get our kids back school please the depression surging especially for teens
4	coldfallout Let me say it plain I loved someone and I failed at it Let me say it another way I like to call myself wound but I will	toxic relationship the lockdown because covid pandemic also had devastating effect relationships the sudden inactivities and depression brought out the beast some people and many found themselves toxic relationship
5	ageingacf older adults are at increased risk for loneliness and social isolation because they are more likely to be living alone espec	depression keeps from playing guitar and every time come back around like playing again for the first time

$$Entdecision(T, H) = \begin{cases} Entailed & \text{if } Sim(T, H) \geq \sigma \\ NotEntailed & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

TABLE V
ENTAILED DECISION

Text	Hypothesis	Lexical	sentence-transformers/ bert-base	Spacy
Text ₁	Hypothesis ₁	Entailed	Entailed	Entailed
Text ₂	Hypothesis ₂	Not Entailed	Entailed	Entailed
Text ₃	Hypothesis ₃	Not Entailed	Entailed	Entailed
Text ₄	Hypothesis ₄	Not Entailed	Not Entailed	Entailed
Text ₅	Hypothesis ₅	Entailed	Entailed	Entailed

V. CONCLUSION

With the current pressures of life, the rate of depression and anxiety in society was noticeably increasing. Thus, the percentage of posts and tweets on social networking sites with depressive contents increases as well. Therefore, there is a need for an efficient depression detection from textual social content. After researching similar studies, we found that textual entailment is promising when using with deep learning

as proposed in this research.

This work presents a new dataset collected using the latest underwriting words developed using PHQ-9. Four deep learning models were tested, GRU, Bi-GRU, LSTM, and BI-LSTM. BI-GRU had the best results and the accuracy rate was above 80%. Finally, the model used the textual entailment process to find out which of the classified tweets are similar to the new ones to find out their depression level without the need of reclassification using deep learning. Also, it helps in online detection for new tweets without the need of retraining. This is a quite novel combined model that enhance the performance of depression detection in terms of time. Also, considering textual entailment, the paper concludes that the semantic entailment is much better than lexical entailment when dealing with social text content.

In future work, we aim to increase our dataset and combine different deep learning methods for better detection. Also, we aim to take emojis into consideration in the preprocessing process. This work can be also extended by working on different social domains. Finally, working on Arabic content is one of our future directions.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. U. Mustafa, N. Ashraf, F. S. Ahmed, J. Ferzund, B. Shahzad, and A. Gelbukh, "A multiclass depression detection in social media based on sentiment analysis," in *Proceedings of the 17th IEEE International Conference on Information Technology—New Generations*. Springer, 2020, pp. 659–662.
- [2] T. Khot, A. Sabharwal, and P. Clark, "Scitail: A textual entailment dataset from science question answering," in *Thirty-Second AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 2018.
- [3] S. Gupta, S. Lakra, and M. Kaur, "Sentiment analysis using partial textual entailment," in *2019 International Conference on Machine Learning, Big Data, Cloud and Parallel Computing (COMITCon)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 51–55.
- [4] Z. Jiao, S. Sun, and K. Sun, "Chinese lexical analysis with deep bi-gru-crf network," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1807.01882*, 2018.
- [5] N. Gruber and A. Jockisch, "Are gru cells more specific and lstm cells more sensitive in motive classification of text?" *Frontiers in artificial intelligence*, vol. 3, p. 40, 2020.
- [6] S. G. Burdisso, M. Errecalde, and M. Montes-y Gómez, "A text classification framework for simple and effective early depression detection over social media streams," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 133, pp. 182–197, 2019.
- [7] T. Gui, L. Zhu, Q. Zhang, M. Peng, X. Zhou, K. Ding, and Z. Chen, "Cooperative multimodal approach to depression detection in twitter," in *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 33, no. 01, 2019, pp. 110–117.
- [8] D. Chen, Y. Li, M. Yang, H.-T. Zheng, and Y. Shen, "Knowledge-aware textual entailment with graph attention network," in *Proceedings of the 28th ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management*, 2019, pp. 2145–2148.
- [9] H. Zogan, I. Razzak, X. Wang, S. Jameel, and G. Xu, "Explainable depression detection with multi-modalities using a hybrid deep learning model on social media," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.02847*, 2020.
- [10] A. Bidgoly, H. Amirkhani, and F. Sadeghi, "Fake news detection on social media using a natural language inference approach," *Research Square*, 2020.
- [11] M. Rodrigues Makiuchi, T. Warnita, K. Uto, and K. Shinoda, "Multi-modal fusion of bert-cnn and gated cnn representations for depression detection," in *Proceedings of the 9th International on Audio/Visual Emotion Challenge and Workshop*, 2019, pp. 55–63.
- [12] M. M. Tadesse, H. Lin, B. Xu, and L. Yang, "Detection of depression-related posts in reddit social media forum," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 44 883–44 893, 2019.

- [13] F. M. Shah, F. Ahmed, S. K. S. Joy, S. Ahmed, S. Sadek, R. Shil, and M. H. Kabir, "Early depression detection from social network using deep learning techniques," in *2020 IEEE Region 10 Symposium (TENSYMP)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 823–826.
- [14] M. Elshazly, M. Haggag, and S. A. Ehssan, "Natural language processing applications: A new taxonomy using textual entailment," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 12, no. 5, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2021.0120580>
- [15] D. Li, H. Chaudhary, and Z. Zhang, "Modeling spatiotemporal pattern of depressive symptoms caused by covid-19 using social media data mining," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 17, no. 14, p. 4988, 2020.
- [16] S. Evensen, Y. Suhara, A. Halevy, V. Li, W.-C. Tan, and S. Mumick, "Happiness entailment: Automating suggestions for well-being," in *2019 8th International Conference on Affective Computing and Intelligent Interaction (ACII)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 62–68.
- [17] A. Sherstinsky, "Fundamentals of recurrent neural network (rnn) and long short-term memory (lstm) network," *Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena*, vol. 404, p. 132306, 2020.
- [18] S. H. Jayasinghe and K. Sirts, "Deep learning textual entailment system for sinhala language," 2019.
- [19] P. Kapanipathi, V. Thost, S. S. Patel, S. Whitehead, I. Abdelaziz *et al.*, "Infusing knowledge into the textual entailment task using graph convolutional networks," in *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 34, no. 05, 2020, pp. 8074–8081.
- [20] C. C. Little, "Abydos documentation," 2018.
- [21] N. Reimers and I. Gurevych, "Sentence-bert: Sentence embeddings using siamese bert-networks," in *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Association for Computational Linguistics, 11 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1908.10084>
- [22] "Spacy v3.2 spacy for semantic similarity," <https://spacy.io/api/docsimilarity>, accessed: 2021-10-30.
- [23] S. A. E. Aly, A. Hassanin, and S. Bekhet, "Esldl: An integrated deep learning model for egyptian sign language recognition," in *2021 3rd Novel Intelligent and Leading Emerging Sciences Conference (NILES)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 331–335.

Performance Evaluation of Random Forest Algorithm in Cluster Environment

Cinantya Paramita¹, Catur Supriyanto, Yani Parti Astuti, Lukman Afi Syariffudin, Fauzi Adi Rafrastara²

Department of Information Engineering
Faculty of Computer Science
Universitas Dian Nuswantoro, Semarang, Indonesia
cinantya.paramita@dsn.dinus.ac.id¹, fauziadi@dsn.dinus.ac.id²

Abstract—Cluster computing was introduced to replace the superiority of super computers. Cluster computing is able to overcome the problems that cannot be effectively dealt with supercomputers. In this paper, we are going to evaluate the performance of cluster computing by executing one of data mining techniques in the cluster environment. The experiment will attempt to predict the flight delay by using random forest algorithm with apache spark as a framework for cluster computing. The result shows that, by involving 5 PC's in cluster environment with equal specifications can increase the performance of computation up to 39.76% compared to the standalone one. Attaching more nodes to the cluster can make the process become faster significantly.

Keywords—Cluster computing, random forest, flight delay prediction, pyspark, apache spark.

I. INTRODUCTION

High Performance Computing (HPC) becomes one of hot topics in the recent years. Either one of the most popular HPC products in the world is called supercomputer. However, traditional supercomputer is no longer dominant in the area of computing and its availability has changed dramatically because of its high cost and low accessibility factors [1][2]. Thus, it is required the HPC system with low cost and high accessibility. Rajak [3] explains that there are 3 types of modern HPC which has better implementation than the traditional supercomputer in term of accessibility and cost. Those are: grid, cloud, and cluster computing. Grid computing is good for resource balancing, access to additional storage, and reliability. Cloud computing has the benefits in super computing power, high resource availability, virtualization, crash recovery, and flexibility. Whereas cluster computing has some advantages, especially in term of manageability, single system image (SSI), and high availability. Not all computation is suitable for all of those 3 solutions, i.e. grid and cloud computing are overkill to solve the simple data mining problems. So it is required the smaller scale of HPC to solve the simpler problem, and it can be overcome effectively by using cluster computing[1][3][4].

Data mining commonly is processed in a standalone computer. However, for the large dataset, mining the data in a standalone PC can take several seconds, minutes, hours, even days, depend on the hardware specifications. A solution is needed to make mining process become more effective, especially in term of processing time [4][5].

In this paper, we will implement data mining algorithm in a cluster environment to accelerate the mining process. We are going to analyze the computational performance of cluster computing by comparing with various numbers of nodes and the standalone one as well. We will evaluate the performance one by one so that we can see the significance of cluster computing for data mining processing. Case study of this research is predicting the flight delay by using random forest algorithm. All the simulations will be conducted in the virtual environment.

This paper consists of six sections. Rest of this paper is organized as follows. The ideas, terminologies, and related researches that conducted by other researchers is discussed in section II. The methodology that used in the experiment is explained in section III. Section IV consists of experiment process and result. In this section, random forest algorithm is executed in the both standalone and cluster environment. Conclusion of this research is presented in the section V, followed by the future work in section VI.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Cluster computing is a part of Superior Computing or High Performance Computing (HPC) [3]. Cluster computing is also known as a part of distributed or parallel processing system [4]. It consists of some interconnected individual computers, through Local Area Network (LAN) [6]. Those interconnected computers are running together as a single integrated source. It has some benefits, such as in term of performance improvement, high availability, cost reduction, and manageability [4][7][8].

According to [4], there are three types of cluster computing, those are High Performance Computing Cluster (HPC Cluster), High Availability Cluster, and Load Balancing Cluster. In this paper, cluster computing's type that are going to be implemented is High Performance Computing Cluster (HPC Cluster). The goal is to accelerate the prediction on flight delay problem.

Flight delay is defined when a carrier lands or takes off latter than its scheduled time for arrival or departure. This phenomenon is becoming common and happened frequently in all over the world. Around 20% carriers have more than 15 minutes delay [9].

PySpark is built to provide users the python API in Spark environment. Python is the most popular programming language or tool, especially for the analytics, data science, and machine learning [10][11]. On the other hand, Apache Spark [12] is a unified analytics engine for large scale data processing. Spark is also big data framework that widely used by both academia and industry. Spark has at least four advantages for performing data analytics [12][13], those are:

- Speed: spark is 100x faster than Hadoop in memory, or 10x on disk. Apache Spark has an Advanced Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) execution engine to support in-memory computing and acyclic data flow.
- Ease of Use: spark supports many popular programming languages, such as: java, scala, python, and R.
- Generality: spark has huge libraries that can be used to perform many activities, including SQL and DataFrames, Spark Streaming, GraphX, and MLlib for machine learning.
- Runs Everywhere: spark can run on top of Mesos, Hadoop, and also in the cloud and standalone. Spark also has the ability to access various data sources, such as: Cassandra, HBase, S3, and HDFS.

On-time flight is important for many parties. Passengers want to arrive several hours earlier or on-time to the destination for their business or appointment. Flight delay can bring the uncertainty for the passenger, lost the time, and sometime it increases the trip cost. On the other hand, the airline companies are also charged for the penalties, fines and additional operational costs for the crew and aircraft retention in airports. As a conclusion, flight delay have some negative impacts, especially on economic aspect, for the passengers, airline companies, and also airports [14].

In this research, the flight delay prediction is conducted by using random forest method, and it is executed in cluster environment. The result will be compared with the performance when executed in standalone mode. A lot of research papers discussed regarding flight delay prediction using some data mining techniques, such as decision tree [15][16][17], random forest [16][18][17], AdaBoost [16], KNN [16], Naïve Bayes [19], C4.5 [19], Linear Regression [19][17], Gradient Boosting Classifier [20], Deep Learning [21], etc.

Random forest is chosen because its popularity to predict something and also become one of the most common tools for analytical needs. It is a well-known algorithm that theoretically logic, appropriate in most applications, and easy to implement [22][23][5]. In this paper, random forest is used to predict the flight delay. As a future work, we will use other methods for the same case study, and compare it with the performance of random forest in cluster environment.

III. METHODOLOGY

The experiment that conducted in this research has the following details:

- Algorithm: Random forest
- Dataset: Flight (2702218 records, with 70% for training and 30% for testing)
- Number of nodes: 1-5 (using virtual machine)

- A computer with specification: Intel Xeon E5620 Processor (Cores: 4, Threads: 8), 16 GB RAM, DDR5 1024 MB VGA, 3TB HDD, Windows 10 OS.

This simulation was performed on top of virtual machine (VirtualBox). All the nodes created here have equal specifications, such as: single CPU Core, 2 GB RAM, Windows 8.1, and PySpark as a cluster computing platform. The dataset was already preprocessed, so we could use it directly.

Figure 1: 5 Virtual PCs created in Virtual Machine with equal specifications

Apache Spark was used in this research, since it is more powerful than the competitors for the cluster and distributed computing. Spark is 10x faster than Hadoop. Spark is platform to do either batch or stream computing with in memory computing capability. PySpark is a combination of Python and Spark, so that we can use all python's library in Spark environment. Such combination makes both python and spark become more powerful and very useful, especially in data science technology.

IV. EXPERIMENT & RESULT

We performed the experiment in 5 environments. Those are:

- Standalone: it involves a single PC (in virtual machine) with 2GB RAM. No other PCs connected to this standalone PC.
- Cluster_1: it involves two PCs (in virtual machine) in which 1 PC works as a master node and another PC works as a worker node. In addition, each PC has 2GB RAM.
- Cluster_2: it involves three PCs (in virtual machine), each acquires 2GB RAM. 1 PC works as master node and 2 other PCs work as worker nodes.
- Cluster_3: it involves four PCs (in virtual machine), each has 2GB RAM. There are 3 workers and 1 master node on this cluster.
- Cluster_4: it involves five PCs (in virtual machine) in which 4 PCs have the role of workers and 1 PC for master node.

For the first experiment, we created the first node (Node_1) and run the algorithm through Jupyter Notebook. This first attempt was conducted in standalone mode. The result was, it took 137.4 seconds to complete the task (Table 1).

Regarding the accuracy of the algorithm, we measured the error prediction by using Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). RMSE is used to calculate the differences between values that predicted by the algorithm and the values observed [24]. It shows that random forest algorithm has error prediction around 13,149 minutes for the flight delay dataset. However, this research is not focusing on this case. The accuracy of this algorithm remain the same, even when we conduct the experiment in the cluster environment with more and more

nodes attached. In this paper, we are going to highlight the performance of each experiment in term of time consumption, since cluster computing can help us to accelerate the performance speed of data mining computation.

On the next experiment, we started to create a cluster environment with 1 master node and 1 worker node. It resulted a processing time that slightly better than the standalone one. Faster performance can be acquired when more than 1 worker nodes are attached.

No.	Environment	Computational Time (in seconds)					
		Experiment					Average
		1	2	3	4	5	
1	Standalone (2GB RAM)	172,3	168,2	169,8	173,1	171,2	170,922
2	Cluster_1 (1 worker) - @2GB	160,4	166,3	162,4	164,8	165,2	163,82
3	Cluster_2 (2 worker) - @2GB	144,5	151,3	143,5	142,2	141,3	144,56
4	Cluster_3 (3 worker) - @2GB	124,5	123,7	126,4	122,6	122,2	123,88
5	Cluster_4 (4 worker) - @2GB	112,6	111,5	115,4	117,4	114,3	114,24

Table 1: Computation Performance between Standalone and Cluster environment.

On the third experiment, we used 1 master node and 2 worker nodes. The processing time became faster than the first and second experiment, with 144.5 seconds to complete the task.

The next step was running the algorithm on a master node which supported with 3 worker nodes. We obtained better computational performance compared to 3 experiments in advance. Here, we got 124.5 seconds.

Finally, we used 1 master and 4 worker nodes to increase the speed of computation. It was proofed by getting 112.6seconds to perform delay prediction on the flight dataset.

We then repeated each experiment 5 times to gain the average time for all computation environments. The average computational time for the standalone, cluster_1, cluster_2, cluster_3, and cluster_4 environments are 170.92, 163.82, 144.56, 123.88, and 114.24 respectively (Table 1).

According to the experiment’s result captured in Table 1, by using cluster computing, the computational time can be decreased up to 33.16%. The more computers attached to the cluster, the faster computing time.

Figure 2: Computing time has continued to go down when more computers are connected

These experiments show us that cluster computing is a good alternative to increase the computation performance, especially in data mining field. It is also a cheap way to accelerate the processing speed, thanks to its scalability. We only need the commodity hardware that probably no longer being used by others. Once we found unused PCs, we can attach them directly to our cluster environment so that the computing performance become faster and faster. Better specification of the attached PCs can also affect the computation performance of cluster as well.

V. CONCLUSION

This research was conducted to evaluate the performance of random forest algorithm to process the data in cluster environment. Random forest here was used to predict the flight delay, in which the dataset is publicly available on the internet. We performed the simulation in a virtual environment. The 1st experiment was running the algorithm in a virtual standalone PC. On the 2nd experiment, we started to develop cluster environment, but consist of 1 master and 1 worker node. The 3rd experiment was simulated on 1 master and 2 worker nodes. The 4th experiment, the simulation involved 1 master and 3 worker nodes. Lastly, on the 5th experiment, we use 5 virtual PCs with 4 PCs as worker and 1 PC as master node.

The performance of this algorithm became faster and faster when more PC attached. The computational time can be decreased up to 33.16% by involving 5 PCs with equal specifications on the cluster. But indeed by attaching more PCs with better specifications can affect the computing performance as well.

VI. FUTURE WORK

As a future work, we will perform the flight delay prediction using other machine learning methods in which implemented on the cluster environment. Those algorithms finally will be compared with the performance of random forest that already conducted in this paper to find the most suitable algorithm for the case of flight delay prediction.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. A. Al Etawi, “A Comparison between Cluster, Grid, and Cloud Computing,” *Int. J. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 179, no. 32, pp. 37–42, 2018.
- [2] Z. Yin, H. Lan, G. Tan, M. Lu, A. V. Vasilakos, and W. Liu, “Computing Platforms for Big Biological Data Analytics: Perspectives and Challenges,” *Comput. Struct. Biotechnol. J.*, vol. 15, pp. 403–411, 2017.
- [3] R. Rajak, “A comparative study: Taxonomy of high performance computing (HPC),” *Int. J. Electr. Comput. Eng.*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3386–3391, 2018.
- [4] M. M. Naeem, H. Mahar, F. Memon, M. Siddique, and A. Chohan, “Cluster Computing Vs Cloud Computing a Comparison and an Overview,” *Sci. Int.*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 5267–5271, 2016.
- [5] F. A. Rafrastara and Q. Deyu, “A Survey and Taxonomy of Distributed Data Mining Research Studies: A Systematic Literature Review,” *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Inf. Secur.*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 12–30, 2016.
- [6] M. Sharma and S. Husain, “Analyzing the Difference of Cluster, Grid, Utility & Cloud Computing,” *IOSR J. Comput. Eng.*, vol. 19, no. 01, pp. 55–60, 2017.
- [7] K. Kaur and A. K. Rai, “A Comparative Analysis: Grid, Cluster and Cloud Computing,” *Int. J. Adv. Res. Comput. Commun. Eng.*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 2278–1021, 2014.
- [8] I. Gandotra, P. Abrol, P. Gupta, R. Uppal, and S. Singh, “Cloud Computing Over Cluster, Grid Computing : a Comparative Analysis,” *J. Grid Distrib. Comput.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–4, 2011.
- [9] N. Chakrabarty, “A Data Mining Approach to Flight Arrival Delay Prediction for American Airlines,” *arXiv:1903.06740 [cs.LG]*, 2019.
- [10] G. Piatetsky, “KDnuggets,” 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kdnuggets.com/2019/05/poll-top-data-science-machine-learning-platforms.html>. [Accessed: 26-Sep-2019].
- [11] B. Santosa and A. Umam, *Data Mining dan Big Data Analytics*. Penebar Media Pustaka, 2018.
- [12] “Apache Spark.” [Online]. Available: <https://spark.apache.org/>. [Accessed: 26-Sep-2019].
- [13] W. Feng, “Learning Apache Spark with Python,” 2019.
- [14] A. Sternberg, J. Soares, D. Carvalho, and E. Ogasawara, “A Review on Flight Delay Prediction,” *arXiv:1703.06118 [cs.CY]*, pp. 1–21, 2017.
- [15] S. Manna, S. Biswas, R. Kundu, S. Rakshit, P. Gupta, and S. Barman, “A statistical approach to predict flight delay using gradient boosted decision tree,” in *ICCIDS 2017 - International Conference on Computational Intelligence in Data Science, Proceedings*, 2018.

- [16] S. Choi, Y. J. Kim, S. Briceno, and D. Mavris, "Prediction of weather-induced airline delays based on machine learning algorithms," in *AIAA/IEEE Digital Avionics Systems Conference - Proceedings*, 2016.
- [17] A. M. Kalliguddi and A. K. Leboulluec, "Predictive Modeling of Aircraft Flight Delay," *Univers. J. Manag.*, 2017.
- [18] J. J. Rebollo and H. Balakrishnan, "Characterization and prediction of air traffic delays," *Transp. Res. Part C Emerg. Technol.*, 2014.
- [19] Y. Ding, "Predicting flight delay based on multiple linear regression," in *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 2017.
- [20] N. Chakrabarty, T. Kundu, S. Dandapat, A. Sarkar, and D. K. Kole, "Flight Arrival Delay Prediction Using Gradient Boosting Classifier," in *Emerging Technologies in Data Mining and Information Security*, no. January, Springer Singapore, 2019, pp. 651–659.
- [21] Y. J. Kim, S. Choi, S. Briceno, and D. Mavris, "A deep learning approach to flight delay prediction," in *AIAA/IEEE Digital Avionics Systems Conference - Proceedings*, 2016.
- [22] B. Emir, D. C. Gruben, H. T. Bhattacharyya, A. L. Reisman, and J. Cabrera, "Predictive Modeling in HEOR," in *Statistical Topics in Health Economics and Outcomes Research*, CRC Press, 2018.
- [23] M. Su, Z. Zhang, Y. Zhu, and D. Zha, "Data-driven natural gas spot price forecasting with least squares regression boosting algorithm," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 6, 2019.
- [24] R. Varatharajan, G. Manogaran, and M. K. Priyan, "A big data classification approach using LDA with an enhanced SVM method for ECG signals in cloud computing," *Multimed. Tools Appl.*, 2018.

AN IMPROVED META-HEURISTIC ORIENTED EARLY SIZE ESTIMATION UTILIZING ABC

Manisha¹

Research Scholar, U.I.E.T (M.D.U), Rohtak, India
mvmanishavatsa@gmail.com

Dr. Rahul Rishi²

Professor, U.I.E.T (M.D.U), Rohtak, India
rahulrishi@mdurohtak.in

Abstract: *In order to channelize a team's effort in a fruitful direction any software oriented environment, pre-analysis of software components and the budget has always been useful practice. Estimation of the size becomes a tedious task when the machine is not trained well enough to provide good classification accuracy. In order to attain significant result when it comes to early prediction, the selection of the attribute set plays a vital role. Feature set selection has gained popularity in the last couple of years to make the classification process more precise. This paper utilizes and enhances the current behaviour architecture of Artificial Bee Colony (ABC), a meta-heuristic inspired algorithm is being used for feature vector selection. The data is further trained and classified by multiple multi-class classifiers. The evaluation of the results has been made on the base of quantitative parameter analysis and the co-relation of effort and size has also been presented. The paper utilizes dataset supported by NASA research frames.*

Keywords: *Software Size Estimation, Meta-Heuristics, Artificial Bee Colony (ABC).*

I. INTRODUCTION

The significance of software design can be summarised as a significant mixture of size and quality. A design creates software representations that can be evaluated for consistency [1]. The only way to correctly convert a customer's specifications into a finished software product is by design. Software design is the mechanism by which an agent establishes a specification for a software artefact that is intended to achieve goals and uses a collection of primitive components while adhering to constraints. A software design involves the estimation of total number of manpower needed to complete the work, total amount of other supplies and if the software project is extended or does not get complete on time, what would be the extra cost that would be applied to the design company. In order to save effort and to reduce computation complexity, pre-analysis of the software projects is required. NASA, the well-known organization of the world has submitted an analysed data based on the software projects which has been undertaken by NASA. In order to reduce the human effort, the system must be trained to deal with real time existing issues and architecture.

The software program is costly to develop and has a high cost due to its large size in the commercial informational systems. The degree of investment in software programs is estimated to be more than \$200 billion yearly. Boehm suggested carefully considering costs and the benefits before giving the needed resources for the software project. Generally, the precision of the software investment decisions has a direct impact on the quality of the software. Many times the costs for the project are underestimated, due to which many projects running are abandoned midway. This dropping of the project can be due to large costs consumption which was not estimated at an early stage or due to the wrong estimation of time and the resources needed. On the other hand, when the costs are overestimated, exaggerated project estimations may increase the project cost by putting less pressure on programmers to be creative. Moreover, in these cases sometimes the potential projects are rejected because of high cost or time. Resulting in the lost opportunity of creating a value-added project in the firm [2].

So, equally overestimation and under-estimation may cause costly errors. Hence, the accurate estimation of the project is purely needed for the reduction of excessive cost and lead to an increase in efficiency of the company [3]. The cost of the software projects are increasing day by day due to which the result of estimation errors can lead to bad consequences, so these estimations are equally significant or play an important role in project understanding and selection.

Estimating the development of the software has always remained a complicated problem. Improvement in these software estimation techniques leads to the more effective management of cost, time in the management of software. Software development contains numerous interrelated factors that affect the effort and productivity of the development process.

The important factors of size estimation which are generally considered in all the project estimation models are as follows:

- a) Time to be consumed in creating the project.
- b) Total human resources required for completing the project.
- c) Output quantity.

Software size estimation is a very critical issue to both designers and users. They can be used for producing requests for offers, contract talks, planning, and managing. Underestimating the sizes may consequence in management easily approving the project and then if the budget exceeds the failure of the project may occur as it may have underdeveloped functions and poor quality [4]. Overestimating may outcome in various resources dedicated to the project which can lead to loss of jobs.

Precise estimation of size is vital because:

1. It helps for classifying and ranking/arranging the development projects in terms of the overall business plan.
2. It is used for determining the resources needed for the project and at which interval which particular resource will be committed to which task.
3. The impact of changes can be easily viewed and assessed and re-planning can be easily done.
4. When resources are easily matched to the tasks then the project can be easily managed

Software size estimation includes the calculation of the following estimates:

1. Effort (usually in person-months)
2. Project duration (in calendar time)
3. Cost (in dollars)

For size estimation of any software, there are a large number of techniques are available. Machine learning (ML) is one of the most important techniques used to measure software cost estimation. There are a large number of shortcomings in previous methods that are applied for software effort estimation. So, ML is used to improve the shortcomings of the existing techniques. The choice of the learning category is depend upon the task.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

As the size of the software is dependent upon a lot of factors, this research articles sticks to the correlation of effort to software size and hence the literature survey is oriented towards machine learning and software effort to size estimation only.

Nanda et al. 2016 represented a model that is integrated neuro-fuzzy optimized with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to improve effort estimation on software projects of NASA dataset.

The Neuro-fuzzy algorithm is used for result optimization as well as training. The performance of the proposed model is computed with the comparison of another intelligent system model. The parameters that are computed such as Magnitude of Relative Error (MMER), Mean Standard Error (MSE), and Level Prediction. The proposed model represents better results as compared to others [5].

Novitasari et al. 2016 examine the use of PSO in conjunction with simulated annealing to improve SVM parameter selection. Proposed a local best PSO with SVR for software effort estimation with two objective functions including fitness and cost functions to measure the most favorable generated solution. The major criteria used for determining an acceptable solution is to have an optimization that enhances the fitness value or minimizes the cost value. The optimization is obtained by a cost-typed function, to minimize the error. Desharnais dataset is taken into consideration where local best PSO-SVR gives optimal cost [6].

Langsari et al. 2017 introduced the use of Gaussian Membership Function (GMF) FL and Multi-Objective PSO algorithms in calibrating and optimizing the COCOMO II model parameters. The proposed method is applied to the Nasa93 dataset. MOPSO is a calibration and optimization algorithm approach to improving the accurate degree of the COCOMO II model by optimizing its parameters. The proposed method gives significance in reduced MMRE and evaluation results have shown that the calibration and optimization with the proposed method gives an improved estimation compared to the basic COCOMO II model [7]. Following this, **Yigit-Sert and Kullu 2018** had also implemented ABC for software estimation work on similar dataset statistics [8].

Ali et al. 2019 presented a systematic review based upon recent studies related to software effort estimation models by applying machine learning approaches. The literature of the proposed work is based upon the previous studies that were published from January 1991 to December 2017. From the past studies, 75 were selected, then perform filtering of inclusion/exclusion and quality assessment. Most of the studies applied ANN as a machine learning model to compute the better mean magnitude of relative error (MMRE). Support Vector Machine (SVM) and ANN are mostly used as machine learning models rather than others [9].

Sehra et al. 2019 proposed a hybrid model which combines machine learning algorithms to predict the effort more accurately. The fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (FAHP) has been used effectively for feature ranking. Ranks generated from FAHP have been integrated into weighted kernel least square SVM for effort estimation. The combination

of weights generated by FAHP and SVM has resulted in more accurate effort estimates [10].

Chhabra et al. 2020 designed a FIS to optimize fuzzy logic-based COCOMO using PSO Algorithm to calculate the effect of cost parameters used in Intermediate COCOMO. PSO is used to solve the problem of parametric optimization of fuzzy systems. The magnitude of the relative error and its mean, calculated using COCOMO NASA2 and COCOMO NASA datasets are used as evaluation metrics to validate the proposed model. The model outperforms when compared to other optimization techniques. This fuzzy model handled the vagueness and ambiguity in information resulting in improved prediction accuracy of COCOMO. The resultant MMRE showed even more improved results in comparison to fuzzy-model-based COCOMO [11].

Suresh & Behera 2020 presented a comparative analysis based upon different models like; SVM, NN, RF, KNN, and back propagation algorithm. The orange data mining tool is used in the proposed work. Two datasets are used in the proposed work that is COCOMO'81 having 63 projects and the Desharnais dataset consists of 81 projects. The simulation results show that the back propagation model provides efficient results as compared to other approaches [12].

Rankovic et al. 2021 proposed two different architectures based upon Artificial Neural Network (ANN) that is used for software effort estimation. The author applied ANN as a machine learning approach due to its high speed of learning that helps to obtain better results. The main aim of the proposed work is to minimization of the Magnitude Relative Error (MRE) in effort estimation with the help of Taguchi's Orthogonal Arrays. It helps to find out the simple architecture of ANN for optimized learning. The proposed work is used to cover up different values of actual efficiency that belong to a huge range of projects. It helps to reduce the risk of error estimation to increase the rate of completed software projects [13].

Rhmann et al. 2021 introduced software effort estimation depends on the weighted hybrid search-based algorithm. The weighted ensembles were created by using various metaheuristic algorithms such as; black hole optimization, firefly algorithm, and genetic algorithm. The author used three datasets that are collected from the PROMISE repository. The simulation results were performed in R programming language using RKEEL and Metaheuristics Opt r packages. The results describe that the proposed metaheuristics based on weighted ensembles of hybrid search-based algorithms provide better results of software effort estimation [14].

As a result, it is recommended that a Neuro-based methodology be used to develop a suitable

generic form of model that can be used to estimate software effort for all types of projects. The authors proposed that NN-based techniques be used to create a generic form of model that can be used to estimate software effort for all types of projects.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology is divided into three steps architecture. The first step loads the dataset and applies machine learning based improved k-means algorithm to divide the data into three sizes depending upon the co-relation attained in the groups. The second part applied Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) to select attribute sets from each divided group and the third step used training and classification algorithms to classify the test data. The proposed methodology ends up with summarizing the co-relation between the size and the effort. The overall methodology can be represented by the following algorithmic pseudo code.

A. Algorithm: CC = Estimation (PR)

Where, PR \rightarrow Project Records (Input)

CC \rightarrow Classified Class (Output)

1. Collect all the data records from the repository and create a Dataset
2. Aggregated_Dataset = Aggregate (Dataset) // Aggregate the collected dataset
3. Apply Iterative K-means
4. **For each data in range(Dataset)**
5. New_Data = Iterative K-means (Aggregated_Dataset) // According to the improved k-means [15] which consist of different similarity measures
6. **End - For**
7. Apply K-means on New_Data
8. Set an estimated cluster (C)
9. Calculate size of New_Data in terms of [Row, Col.]
10. Define initial C-Data = [] // To store clustered data
11. Consider Centroid C = C1, C2, & C3
12. **For X in to range(Row)**
13. **For Y in range(Col)**
14. **If Data (X, Y) \in C1**
15. C-Data 1 = New_Data (X, Y)
16. **Else if Data (X, Y) \in C2**
17. C-Data 2 = New_Data (X, Y)
18. **Else Data (i,j) \in C3**
19. C-Data 3 = New_Data (X, Y)
20. **End - If**
21. **Using the average**, adjust the value of Centroid C
22.
$$C = \frac{\text{sum}(C\text{-Data } 1, C\text{-Data } 2, \text{ and } C\text{-Data } 3 \text{ n})}{3}$$
23. **End - For**

TABLE II. CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY

Total Number of Projects	Accuracy enhanced ABC	Accuracy normal ABC [Venkata et al. (2020)] [16]	Accuracy normal cuckoo[Kaushik et al. (2017)] [15]
25	0.642	0.543	0.521
30	0.660	0.545	0.523
35	0.689	0.554	0.523
40	0.706	0.561	0.525
45	0.709	0.569	0.530
50	0.714	0.593	0.532
55	0.725	0.613	0.534
60	0.735	0.627	0.537
65	0.791	0.634	0.538
70	0.825	0.662	0.540
75	0.902	0.694	0.547
80	0.921	0.725	0.552
85	0.932	0.741	0.559
90	0.956	0.771	0.568
92	0.967	0.8008	0.571

As the utilized dataset was limited to 92 projects only the proposed algorithm simulated some more records for reference. A total of 5000 simulations were performed on the later stage and it is identified as the overall accuracy attained after 5000 simulation is 15% more efficient as compared to existing average accuracy. The average classification accuracy of 0.79 was exhibited by the proposed work, 0.64 by Venkata et al. and 0.54 by Kaushik et al. The CCR is further computed using by evaluating the proposed classification accuracy over the classification accuracy of the existing work. The CCR of the proposed work in comparison to the two existing works is depicted in Fig. 1.

The average CCR of the proposed work over the Venkata et al. who had implemented ABC based architecture is observed to be 1.236. However, CCR of proposed work for the Kaushik et al. work who had taken advantage of CS is observed to be 1.466. The figure depicts that on an average, if the proposed algorithm architecture is not used, the major loss could be upto 87% if the number of projects are small in count. It is obvious that, if the learning algorithm will get more data, it will produce much precise classification value. The outcome of the paper can be extended by hybridizing the model value with other meta-heuristics algorithms.

Fig. 1 CCR of the proposed work over existing work

V. CONCLUSION

The paper had introduced a meta-heuristic inspired algorithm for early size estimation. To achieve this feature selection was performed using ABC fitness function. The multiclass classifier was used for the training and classification of the data obtained from the NASA that has been used as the base for the analysis by numerous existing studies. The evaluation of the proposed enhanced ABC is performed in terms of classification accuracy achieved against variation in the number of projects. The work further outperformed in terms of CCR computed against the existing works demonstrating CCR of 1.236 and 1.466. This shows that the reliable and cost effective size estimations using proposed work.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Zazworka, M. A. Shaw, F. Shull, en C. Seaman, "Investigating the impact of design debt on software quality", in *Proceeding of the 2nd working on Managing technical debt - MTD '11*, Waikiki, Honolulu, HI, USA, 2011.
- [2] M. Jorgensen en K. Molokken-Ostfold, "Reasons for software effort estimation error: impact of respondent role, information collection approach, and data analysis method", *IEEE trans. softw. eng.*, vol 30, no 12, bll 993–1007, Des 2004.
- [3] F. Walkerden en R. Jeffery, "An empirical study of analogy-based software effort estimation", *Empirical software engineering*, vol 4, bll 135–158, 1999.
- [4] E. Topp-Jørgensen, M. K. Poulsen, J. F. Lund, en J. F. Massao, "Community-based monitoring of natural resource use and forest quality in Montane forests and miombo woodlands of Tanzania", *Biodivers. Conserv.*, vol 14, no 11, bll 2653–2677, Okt 2005.
- [5] Suharjo, S. Nanda, en B. Soewito, "Modeling software effort estimation using hybrid PSO-ANFIS", in *2016 International Seminar on Intelligent Technology and Its Applications (ISITIA)*, Lombok, Indonesia, 2016..
- [6] D. Novitasari, I. Cholissodin, en W. F. Mahmudy, "Optimizing SVR using Local Best PSO for software effort estimation", *J. Inf. Technol. Comput. Sci.*, vol 1, no 1, bl 28, Apr 2016.
- [7] K. Langsari en R. Sarno, "Optimizing effort and time parameters of COCOMO II estimation using fuzzy multi-objective PSO", *Proceeding of the Electrical Engineering Computer Science and Informatics*, vol 4, no 1, Okt 2017..
- [8] S. Yigit-Sert en P. Kullu, "Software cost estimation using enhanced artificial bee colony algorithm", *Int. J. Adv. Comput. Sci. Appl.*, vol 9, no 4, 2018.
- [9] A. Ali en C. Gravino, "A systematic literature review of software effort prediction using machine learning methods", *J. Softw. (Malden)*, vol 31, no 10, Okt 2019.
- [10] S. K. Sehra, Y. S. Brar, N. Kaur, en S. S. Sehra, "Software effort estimation using FAHP and weighted kernel LSSVM machine", *Soft Comput.*, vol 23, no 21, bll 10881–10900, Nov 2019.
- [11] S. Chhabra en H. Singh, "Optimizing design of fuzzy model for software cost estimation using Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm", *Int. J. Comput. Intell. Appl.*, vol 19, no 01, bl 2050005, Mrt 2020.
- [12] P. S. Kumar en H. S. &behera, "Estimating software effort using neural network: An experimental investigation", *Computational Intelligence in Pattern Recognition*, vol 26, bll 165–180, 2020.
- [13] N. Rankovic, D. Rankovic, M. Ivanovic, en L. Lazic, "COSMIC FP method in software development estimation using artificial neural networks based on orthogonal arrays", *Conn. Sci.*, bll 1–20, Sep 2021.
- [14] W. Rhmann, B. Pandey, en G. A. Ansari, "Software effort estimation using ensemble of hybrid search-based algorithms based on metaheuristic algorithms", *Innov. Syst. Softw. Eng.*, Feb 2021.
- [15] A. Kaushik, S. Verma, H. J. Singh, en G. Chhabra, "Software cost optimization integrating fuzzy system and COA-Cuckoo optimization algorithm", *Int. j. syst. assur. eng. manag.*, vol 8, no S2, bll 1461–1471, Nov 2017..
- [16] K. M. G. Venkata, N. M. Babu, J. S. Havisha, B. Haritha, en V. Y. Lakshmi, "Cost Estimation Based On Artificial Bee Colony", *International Journal of Scientific and Technology*, vol 9, no 2, bll 6096–6098, 2020.

A Critical Analysis of Learning Technologies and Informal Learning in Online Social Networks Using Learning Analytics

Audu Kafwa Dodo¹, Ezekiel Uzor Okike²

¹Department of Computer Science, Taraba State University Jalingo, Nigeria

¹Department of Computer Science, University of Botswana, Gaborone, Botswana

¹ kafwa@tsuniversity.edu.ng

² euokike@gmail.com

Abstract— This paper presents a critical analysis of the current application of big data in higher education and how Learning Analytics (LA), and Educational Data Mining (EDM) are helping to shape learning in higher education institutions that have applied the concepts successfully. An extensive literature review of Learning Analytics, Educational Data Mining, Learning Management Systems, Informal Learning and Online Social Networks are presented to understand their usage and trends in higher education pedagogy taking advantage of 21st century educational technologies and platforms. The roles of and benefits of these technologies in teaching and learning are critically examined. Imperatively, this study provides vital information for education stakeholders on the significance of establishing a teaching and learning agenda that takes advantage of today's educational relevant technologies to promote teaching and learning while also acknowledging the difficulties of 21st-century learning. Aside from the roles and benefits of these technologies, the review highlights major challenges and research needs apparent in the use and application of these technologies. It appears that there is lack of research understanding in the challenges and utilization of data effectively for learning analytics, despite the massive educational data generated by high institutions. Also due to the growing importance of LA, there appears to be a serious lack of academic research that explore the application and impact of LA in high institution, especially in the context of informal online social network learning. In addition, high institution managers seem not to understand the emerging trends of LA which could be useful in the running of higher education. Though LA is viewed as a complex and expensive technology that will culturally change the future of high institution, the question that comes to mind is whether the use of LA in relation to informal learning in online social network is really what is expected? A study to analyze and evaluate the elements that influence high usage of OSN is also needed in the African context. It is high time African Universities paid attention to the application and use of these technologies to create a simplified learning approach occasioned by the use of these technologies.

Keywords: Learning Analytics, Educational Data Mining, Informal Learning, Online Social Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

Learning is essential for obtaining new information and skills in today's ever-changing world, and it does not always take place in traditional educational settings. Most of the student learning, take place informally [34] and technology plays an

important role in facilitating these encounters. Although informal learning is not a new concept, social media technologies have opened new possibilities that were previously unavailable and have even "blurred the line between formal and informal learning" [22]. Many researchers [75], [43], [47] stress the social character of informal learning in the digital age since social media technologies have a significant impact on student experiences. For example, as a type of informal learning, today's students utilize instant messaging, browse websites, use Facebook for chatting, Twitter, Instagram, listen to music, play games, and download materials [100], and all these practices are important for social interaction. As a result, there has been an increase in the amount of data created from various sources of online social networking sites.

In retrospect between 2014 and 2020, the rate of data growth was anticipated to double every month, according to [102]. Higher education has not been spared from the "data flood" age, as it has witnessed a massive increase in data input as well as the introduction and acceptance of new technologies for teaching and learning. However, as compared to other sectors like marketing, finance, health, security, and sport, the primary challenge in the sector has been the inefficient use of this data to create value in a way that satisfies the educational market demand. Furthermore, the popularity of Online Social Networks (OSN) for personal communication and entertainment is driving up demand for OSN-integrated apps. People tend to exchange personal information with linked colleagues in the OSN, whether through games or programs that track one's sports activity. Over the last few years, educational hypermedia has progressed from static systems to dynamic content display and delivery platforms [26]. A shift in personal learning is driving the demand for collaborative learning in OSNs. Additional services have recently been incorporated into OSNs, allowing users to search up and debate subjects of interest with other users. Typically, there is no moderator or facilitator to steer the debate. Active and passive triggers can be used to start conversations. The more active option is to start a text-voice or video chat and ask other users to join. Posting messages on one's page and waiting for a response from someone who happens to be looking at it by

chance is a passive form of communication. Any user who has been granted access to a post may respond on the person's profile.

The quantity of social media data allows us to better comprehend students' experiences, but it also creates methodological challenges in interpreting social media data for educational purposes. Consider the enormous volume of data, the diversity of Internet slang, the unpredictability of student posting locations and timing, as well as the complexity of students' experiences. Pure manual analysis is unable to cope with the ever-increasing volume of data, while pure automatic algorithms are unable to grasp the data's in-depth significance [36]. Traditionally, educational researchers have collected data about students' learning experiences using methods such as surveys, interviews, focus groups, and classroom activities [111], [78]. Because these procedures are often time-consuming, they cannot be replicated or repeated frequently. The scope of such research is generally constrained as well. Furthermore, when asked about their experiences, students must reflect on what they were thinking and doing in the past, which may have faded with time.

Learning analytics and educational data mining (EDM) are new areas that focus on analyzing structured data from course management systems (CMS), classroom technology usage, or regulated online learning environments to help educators make better decisions [44], [12], [54]. Learning analytics is defined as "the use, assessment, elicitation, and analysis of static and dynamic information about learners and learning environments, for the near real-time modeling, prediction, and optimization of learning processes and learning environments, as well as for educational decision-making" in this study [6]. Since early 2010, the study of learning analytics has grown tremendously in the fields of education and psychology, as well as computers and data science [80]. As a result, while learning analytics is a broad concept, it has many conceptual variations, such as school analytics [64], teacher or teaching analytics [23], academic analytics [44], assessment analytics [113], social learning analytics [32], or multimodal [53]. Predictive models are used in learning analytics to offer actionable data. Data processing, technology-enhanced learning, educational data mining, and visualization are all part of this interdisciplinary approach [41]. The goal of LA is to customize educational opportunities to the needs and abilities of each individual learner by intervening with at-risk pupils and giving feedback and instructional content. While LA focuses on the use of established methods and models to address challenges impacting student learning and the organizational learning system, educational data mining focuses on the creation of new computational data analysis approaches [77].

There has been considerable criticism that the process of big data mining is driven by higher education management and the economic framework of education [109], nonetheless, empirical studies have shown that LA may be beneficial for

enhancing education. LA heightens learners' and instructors' awareness of their current conditions, allowing them to make better informed decisions and execute their duties more efficiently [41]. One of the most common uses of learning analytics is to track and forecast student performance, as well as to detect possible problems and at-risk individuals [20]. Some institutions have already used LA in a variety of courses to help students study more effectively. Purdue University, for example, utilized predictive modeling based on data from its course management system to identify students at danger and intervene. The University of Alabama enhanced student retention by developing a prediction model for at-risk students based on a huge dataset of demographic information. Northern Arizona University, for example, linked resource utilization, risk level, and student success by developing a prediction model to determine which students would benefit from which resource [112]. These are among the first institutions of higher learning to use LA. Equally, in the UK, the Open University of UK linked the strategic priorities to continue students' enhancement and experience to retention and progression. Nottingham Trent University UK also linked the area of student's retention-less quarter with low average engagement progress of second year students. In the same vein. The Open university of Austria mention that learning analytics is used to drive personalization and adoption of content recommended to individual students as well as provide input and evidence for curriculum redesign. In Edith Cowen University in Austria, they created a probability of retention scores for each undergraduate students to identify most likely students to need support [60]. While some Higher Education Institutes have had great success in exploiting the benefits of Learning Analytics, many others especially in the African context have yet to do so. This calls for research in LA among African Universities.

There is a knowledge gap in terms of how Learning Analytics is utilized and what the consequences are in higher education. This paper calls for research to fill this gap. The authors of this paper are currently engaged in research to examine and identify the key factors influencing the use and impact of Learning Analytics and provide a systematic overview of the use and impact of informal online social network learning in higher education institutions. More specifically, this research aims to determine how informal online social networks can effectively use data in the era of Big Data and Learning Analytics as learning tools to influence learning outcomes. This paper therefore serves as input from the various literature reviewed. Although research on the use of LA in higher education institutions has been published in recent years, LA is still a new topic of study. Higher education stakeholders, leaders, administrators, teachers, and course designers must get familiar with LA methodologies and applications [41]. The difficulty is that few studies have integrated prior research or offered a comprehensive review of concerns related to the use of LA in higher education.

A. Statement of Research Problem

Informal online social network learning, according to educators, is inherently disruptive to the learning process. As a result of this belief, many educators have declared it illegal to use electronic devices such as computers or mobile phones in class [117]. However, online social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter, Linked In, and others can help students become more academically and socially integrated while also enhancing learning outcomes [7]. Most of informal learning processes are implicit, ad hoc, spontaneous, and unnoticed by others [16]. As a result, this topic poses a fascinating challenge for the field of information systems: capturing and analyzing traces of (social) informal learning in everyday life and the learning environment.

B. Significance of the Study

This study has the potential to make a significant contribution to the field of learning analytics using an informal online social network, as well as its application and technique being beneficial in the fields of big data, and data mining. This ongoing study stands in stark contrast to the currently prevalent, management-driven training model, which prioritizes formal learning guided by corporate curricular agendas and relies on outside experts and knowledge sources [38].

C. Current Research Effort

Our current research effort is aimed at developing a framework that will be used to utilize learning analytics in higher institution. The study will examine the current status of informal leaning using the online social networks.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Big Data

Data is pervasive and has always been important in making decisions. As a result of todays advanced technologies, massive data can be collected quickly, mined, processed and interpreted as explained in [120]. Digital networks, social networking, cellphones, and the World Wide Web are just a handful of the methods used to generate this massive amount of data. These massive datasets are referred to as "Big Data" because they are beyond the capacity of conventional database tools to collect, search, store, transfer, manage, visualize, share, query, analyze, and update them. Nevertheless, depending on the technologies employed and the average amount of datasets connected with the industry, the definition of Big Data may vary from sector to sector, and the present pace of data collection is staggering. Effective data handling and analysis is a significant issue. Formally, Big Data may be defined as collections of datasets whose volume, velocity, or variety is so large that it is difficult to store, manage, process and analyze the data using traditional databases and data processing tools [106]. Figure 1 shows the main characteristics of Big Data in terms of volume, velocity and variety.

Fig. 1. Big Data Characteristics: Source [102].

In recent years, exponential growth in both structured and unstructured data generated by information technology, academia, industry, healthcare, the Internet of Things, and other systems. An estimate by IBM indicate that 2.5 quintillion bytes of data are created every day [107]. According to DOMO report [88], the estimates of the amount of data generated every minute on popular online platforms can be seen as presented in figure 2.

Fig. 2. Data generated every minute by OSNs Source [88]

As of July 2021, the internet reaches 65% of the world's population and now represents 5.17 billion people – a 10% increase from January 2021. Of this total, 92.6% access the internet via mobile devices. According to Statista, the total amount of data consumed globally in 2021 is 79 zettabytes, an annual number projected to grow to over 180 Zettabytes by 2025.

Essentially, Big data is generated from heterogeneous data sources such as email, social media, medical instruments, commercial and scientific sensors, financial transactions, satellite, and traditional databases, etc. in the form of text,

image, audio, video, or any combinations of any form of these. Expectedly, organizations will be able to make educated decisions as a result of the massive volume of data being generated [105]. However, because of the diverse nature and scale of big data, managing it is a difficult undertaking.

B. Big Data Analytics and Educational Data

Recently, Data Mining (DM), Educational Data Mining (EDM), and Learning Analytics (LA) have been employed to handle big homogenous datasets. Traditional data mining approaches, on the other hand, must be updated to process diverse types of data in parallel to handle the heterogeneity of big data. For this reason, some researchers refer to "data mining" as "old big data" and "big data" as "new data mining" [103], [114]. Big data analytics is a technique for analyzing big datasets comprising a range of datasets to find hidden patterns, unknown connections, market trends, consumer preferences, and other relevant business data. Although big data analytics is frequently employed in business to anticipate future trends and consumer behaviors, it is shockingly underused in education. Learners, educators, educational researchers, course developers, learning institutions, and education administrators are the six stakeholders in education. Through learning systems based on big data analytics, learners may receive immediate and thorough feedback on their interactions with the information they are learning. Big data may be utilized to teach pupils about what they have correctly learned and what they have not. Similarly, high-performing students' practices can be shared with other students so that they can adapt their learning by the system. Educators may use big data to assess the overall performance of the class at a macro level, allowing them to plan broad tactics for the class. They can also examine an individual student's performance at a microscopic level to determine his or her strengths and shortcomings. As a result, educators can concentrate on the learner's weak spots to enhance their total performance. Educational researchers may utilize a vast quantity of learner datasets to suggest new learning theories and practices, as well as assess the efficacy of the theories and models offered. Course creators can leverage the rapid availability of numerous online participants, as well as their comments, to create new course materials or alter existing course materials.

Analysis of large educational datasets can be done by using the combination of two techniques, namely, educational data mining (EDM) and learning analytics (LA). These techniques develop a capacity for quantitative research in response to the growing need for evidence-based analysis related to education policy and practice [94]. As Big data is being used to evaluate the rationality and effectiveness of training programs at universities [7], evidence from [17] which studied three different online learning environments: Open Learning Initiative (OLI) at Stanford University and Carnegie Mellon University, Code Webs Project, and massive open online courses (MOOC), suggest that learners and instructors both can benefit from big data. Big data assists instructors in the assessment process by enabling the continuous diagnosis of

learners' knowledge and related states and by promoting learning through targeted feedback. Data-enhanced assessment can provide feedback to instructors in designing teaching and assessment strategies in online and offline learning environments. The influence of technology can be seen in many aspects of education from student engagement in learning and content creation to helping teachers provide personalized content and improving student outcomes [19]. One may argue that educational data is not Big Data when studying big data in education. Is educational data characterized by the three Big Data characteristics of volume, velocity and variety? Data collected within a MOOC is high in velocity and volume but low in variety unless deliberate efforts are made to increase variety. Demographic information such as (gender, ethnicity, etc.) and previous knowledge assessments can be included in educational data (prior college enrolments, high school grades, standardized test scores, etc.). However, these variables are not collected automatically in MOOCs [85]. Also, when comparing the volume of educational data to other industry data such as web data, retail, and health care data, learning analytics may fall short on volume. Volume, speed, and variety are the major distinctions between Big Data and Analytics [100]. Despite these variations, many research projects are looking into the use of learning analytics and educational data, as significant quantities of data are generated every day via eLearning tools that might provide valuable insight into students' performance, attentiveness, and habits [70].

C. Big Data and Learning Analytics

Big Data is at the heart of both learning analytics and business analytics and provides data sources for generating insights through analytics. Big Data has a lot of value and may have a lot of influence, but it's all predicated on Learning Analytics and Business Analytics. Big Data may be extremely valuable and impactful, but companies must utilize analytics to make sense of it [96]. Some individuals use the terms "Big Data Analytics" and "Business Analytics" interchangeably. Analytics in business is referred to as Business Analytics, while Analytics in high education is referred to as Learning Analytics. According to [44], Big Data encompasses the emerging field of Learning Analytics, which is now an emerging field in education. Reports in [89] have highlighted the use of Big Data in Higher Education, claiming that technical advancements have facilitated the shift to greater use of analytics in high education.

In addition, Big Data in higher education implies an understanding of a wide range of administrative and operational data collected procedures aimed at examining institutional performance and improvement to predict future performance and identify potential challenges related to research, academic programming, teaching, and learning [18], [99]. In a similar vein, [104] claims that most of the current work on analytics in higher education comes from interdisciplinary research, which includes educational technology, statistics, math, computer and information

science, and data mining is a key component of the current work on analytics in education.

Big Data is now well-positioned to begin tackling some of the major problems now confronting high education using today's technologies. With these technologies, organizations (including educational institutions) get superior perspectives from data at previously unattainable levels of complexity, speed, and accuracy. Students, systems, and computer applications [37, 45]. Learning Analytics (LA) therefore, is a fundamental instrument for learning change in education that provides evidence on which to build a better perspective and make learned rather than inherent choices [72]. Formally defined, Learning Analytics is the process of gathering, analyzing, and reporting educational Big Data because of business intelligence and data mining [13]. As a growing field of study, it provides students, instructors, and other stakeholders with a better knowledge of how they learn [32], [42]. Other key benefits of Big data and LA include student course performance prediction, identifying risk of abrasion, interactive visualization and reporting of data, smart feedback, course commendations, approximation of skill development, identification of group-based collaborative feedback, and schedule management [39]. The idea is extended to smart learning environments and interactive educational systems in order to sustain active learning and therefore a general development for learning and engagement [11,59]. With the current shift in educational settings to blended and online learning, as well as the introduction of Learning Management Systems (LMSs) like Moodle and Blackboard, it is unsurprising that Big Data has made its way into education and is expected to be widely used in high institutions as these platforms generate massive educational data sets over a period of time.

D. Learning Analytics and Educational Data Mining

Data produced by and accessible in higher education (HE) provide the basis for conducting research and analysis in understanding and improving teaching and learning. The sources of these data are not only from teaching and learning but also include all data units of a university such as finance, human resources, the registrar's office, maintenance and faculties, internet usage, admission, program development, libraries, and research. As a result, HE has been paying careful attention to utilizing technologies made accessible by advancements in big data analysis, with employability and graduate skills at the forefront of many institutional initiatives to harness the usefulness of educational data. For teaching, learning and services provided to students, it seems that both Educational Data Mining (EDM) and Learning Analytics (LA) can become optimal tools to guide universities in adapting to changes and addressing specific needs for the future. EDM has grown into its own discipline, using data mining methods in educational settings. EDM includes a wide range of techniques and applications that may be divided into two groups. On the one hand, EDM may be utilized to achieve practical research goals like improving learning quality. On the other hand, it may be utilized as a tool for pure research

purposes, such as improving our knowledge of how people learn [81]. EDM provides a variety of options for analyzing and directing learning in a multidimensional environment where data comes from many sources and in various formats [118]. These methods are eclectic in character, combining qualitative and quantitative approaches. They also let researchers examine large amounts of data that are influenced by a variety of unknown factors. Hence, analysis of observational datasets to find unsuspected relationships and to summarize the data in novel ways that are both understandable and useful to the data owners is a critical [92]. Data mining as a multidisciplinary field also involves methods at the intersection of artificial intelligence, machine learning, statistics, and database systems as shown in fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Areas related to EDM and LA: Source:[82]

Data analytics in the context of learning and education (Learning Analytics) entails gathering information on student actions and behaviors, as well as educational settings and situations, and then utilizing statistics and data mining methods to uncover important patterns that show how learning occurs. LA may be used to report learning activity measurements and patterns or optimize learning methods and settings.

Because of the enormous quantities of data becoming accessible from the increasing number of courses offered in e-learning and hybrid settings, the educational applications of EDM and LA in higher education are new and developing trends. They are a great tool for methodically analyzing the massive amounts of data generated by higher institutions.

E. Benefits of LA and EDM

Papamitsiou and Economides performed a comprehensive systematic literature evaluation of empirical evidence on the advantages of LA as well as the related area of educational data mining (EDM). They categorized the approaches into case studies that focused on student behavior modeling, performance prediction, increased self-reflection and self-

awareness, dropout prediction, and retention. Their results indicate that vast amounts of educational data as well as the use of pre-existing algorithmic techniques were accessible. Furthermore, LA allows for the creation of accurate learner models that may be used to guide adaptive and customized treatments. Other advantages of LA include the detection of key learning moments, learning methods, navigation behaviors, and learning patterns [61]. A separate systematic review on LA. Was done in [76]. The authors suggest that, in order to effectively assist learning processes, logs of students' data activity should be supplemented with extra information (e.g. actual time spent learning, semantic-rich information). As a result, extensive data on students' attempts and performance, as well as precise information about psychological, behavioral, and emotional states, are required for LA to promote study success. There is a lot of overlap between these two areas of study. Despite this, there are several divergences view in the literature. Notwithstanding, the aim of EDM and LA is the same: to improve education quality by analyzing massive quantities of data and extracting valuable information for stakeholders. Companies in other industries, such as finance, and healthcare, have already used statistical, machine-learning, and data-mining methods to improve performance via data-driven choices. Figure 4 shows the evolution of EDM and LA

conceptual models of learning analytics adoption in higher education, as recently pointed out by [33], fail to operationalize how key dimensions interact to inform the realities of the implementation process, necessitating a need to rethink learning analytics adoption through complexity leadership theory and to develop systems understanding at leadership levels to enable the movement of boutique analytics projects into the enterprise. Learning analytics adoption is frequently hampered by a lack of resources, obstacles requiring many stakeholders' buy-in, and worries and anxiety about big data ethics as well as privacy concerns in higher education [87], [24]. To meet these difficulties, leaders must be flexible, sensitive to environmental forces, adept at handling disputes, and able to harness complex social networks for change [15].

One of the most promising techniques for investigating the complexity of social impact, multilayer hierarchies, and relationship development is network analysis. In [66] network techniques were used to describe the spread and diversity of behaviors, forecast the pattern of dissemination of innovations, analyze educational phenomena, and identify opinion leaders and followers in order to better comprehend information flows [39]. Epistemic network analysis is noteworthy in the context of learning analytics.

Fig. 4. Evolution of EDM and LA Source [82]

Although EDM research began a few years earlier, the popularity of EDM and LA areas of study has been on the increase since the early 2010s (Figure 4). Due to the potential advantages (for students, instructors, administrators, researchers, and society in general) and the relevance of current Big Data research, these areas are anticipated to continue to grow [21].

F. Incorporating Social Systems into Learning Analytics

The complex social networks that facilitate the flow of adoption processes are part of the broad social system settings that are engaged in higher education [10]. The existing

G. Conceptualizing Informal Learning and Online Social Network

The study of asynchronous discussion forums dominated previous work on online informal learning analysis, with an emphasis on finding successful learning and knowledge-building processes through content analysis [91] [116]. In social contexts, learning is defined as a collection of processes through which a learner builds meaning, and new ideas based on prior experiences. This implies that evidence of learners' online interactions, like chats, may be used to identify cognitive and social processes that learners participate in to give meaning to their new concepts.

a) Informal Learning

Informal learning is more difficult to describe due to many conceptual and methodological problems [97] [35]. In terms of learning context location, informal learning refers only to learning that occurs outside of the classroom [68], [57]. Other research, such as [98], examines informal learning in terms of structure and technique, as well as teacher-student interaction. It is viewed as a self-directed, purposeful activity from this perspective. Another perspective emphasizes the goal of learning, describing informal learning as learning that occurs inadvertently, spontaneously, and without attention, and is typically associated with leisure activities [69]. Learning is a continuous process in which the learner's capacity to arrange, classify, and evaluate knowledge determines the degree of formality or informality. As described in [1], it is about "the degree of control teachers and learners have over the selection, organization, and timing of knowledge transmitted and absorbed." When a student has more control over learning possibilities, as well as the flexibility to select what

to study and how learning is assessed, learning becomes more informal. As stated in [14] informal learning gives the learner the focal point of control. Laurillard [110] argues that there is no instructor, no specified curriculum topic or concept, and no external evaluation. The informal learner chooses their own 'teacher,' who may or may not be a person; they determine their curriculum, or what they wish to learn about, and they choose whether to submit to external evaluation. If informal learning experiences are beneficial, how can these experiences be transferred from one context to another to create "seamless learning" informal learning settings?

Furthermore, there is a growing understanding that formal and informal learning have a pragmatic connection. While students learn differently in school and out of school contexts, learning may occur across boundaries, and what is acquired outside of school can help shape what is taught in school [65]. What children learn in school, on the other hand, might encourage them to learn outside of school [67]. Students' informal learning has been demonstrated to be prompted by their schoolwork in [58]. While learners will utilize the kinds of learning that they have already mastered in formal settings, in informal learning circumstances, they will also use techniques that are not often used in schools identified as "informal learning methods" [1]

It appears there is a gap in how learners utilize technology in formal and informal learning. In school, technology is utilized to accomplish curricular work in public areas in an organized, supervised, guided, and most individual way. Learners, on the other hand, use technology in chaotic, unsupervised ways at home and in other informal settings, socially and cooperatively, to pursue interests in private places. Learners have established habits and expectations of how electronic devices should be used in informal contexts, and because schools do not encourage these practices, it has resulted in what some observers have dubbed "digital dissonance" [108]. As a result, teachers and institutions are frightened of the disruptive social potentials of the disputed technologies, and do not identify or comprehend the expanded repertory of practices available to learners in their interaction with them. At the same time, most students are ignorant of these materials' broader educational potential. Leveraging in online social networks could turn learning into a seamless aspect of daily life to the point that it is no longer recognized as learning challenge [56]

b) *Online Social Network*

Through interactions people establish networks of connections that allow them to access resources like jobs, information, and materials, goods, and services. The concepts and cross-disciplinary potential of network principles derived from graph theory are currently gaining significant attention across fields, for example, in bringing together ideas small-world structures from physics to bear on the social results embodied in the idea of "six degrees of separation" [27]. Thus, a more cross-disciplinary approach that is becoming known as "network science" has been born. Our focus here is on maintaining the social network viewpoint, which, as pointed

out in [52] has a long history and a strong empirical and theoretical foundation. Figure 5 illustrates the basics of social network.

Fig 5. Social network basic; Source: [28]

The nodes or actors in the network, as well as the connections between them are the building elements of social networks. Students, instructors, informal learners in an online forum, coworkers in a company, colleagues on a research team, industries or regions, and academic disciplines are all examples. Individuals, organizations, communities, and other types of collectives can all be actors. However, there is little research using social network analysis to incorporate objects at this point and interpreting the social elements of networks that contain mixed and/or inanimate items. Our current study focuses on person-to-person contact and the application of contemporary network theory to learning networks.

Relations in the network refer to the relationships that exist between actors. Actors may have one or more ties, which can range from impersonal to intimate, rare or regular, and elective or mandatory. Actors are linked when they retain at least one type of relationship. Such relationships might be weak when contacts are few, insignificant, or incidental, or strong when interactions are based on numerous types of exchanges, reciprocity in the relationship, and self-disclosure. The actors and the relationships that bind them together constitute networks, which are patterns of connections between members of a certain group of people, such as students in a class, project team members, or instructors in a school. Networks can be drawn based on any relationship between individuals, such as by asking each member of a group of people a broad question such as "who do you talk to?" Networks can also be created using more specific inquiries, such as "with whom do you discuss significant issues?" "Who have you worked with this week?" [115].

To investigate changing network dynamics, [51] proposed an integrated multi-method and temporal methodology. By integrating questions like "who talks to whom?" with "what

are they talking about?" and "why are they talking the way they do?" this technique seeks to provide a more comprehensive view of the processes and behaviors involved in networked learning. Learners now have more choices over what, how, and with whom they learn in a wide range of settings: classrooms, after-school programs, home-school, formal online learning, and so on. These changes impact constructs for learning, teaching, and future research [58]. Increasing learners' educational attainment, science and math learning, technological fluencies, communication skills, civic engagement, and preparation for the twenty-first-century workplace are some of the most pressing issues facing education today [9], [50].

Learners prefer to use the online social network while they are not in school, during their free time, and among peers of all ages, ethnicities, and socioeconomic levels [74]. Essentially, we provide some basic definitions. Formally, social network sites are collections of Web-based services that allow individuals to establish a public or semi-public profile inside the system's limits, to give a list of other users with whom they are connecting, and to monitor and roll over the list of connections [30]. Hence, social network websites are online communication platforms for individuals who have common interests and activities [49]. Users may interact with one another via several means on websites, including chat, messaging, and e-mail. Online social network software are Internet-based programs that enable users to build and manage virtual social networks.

In [2], a study of trends among non-profits, foundations, and socially responsible businesses was conducted. The result suggests that facilitation of human relationships and connections via social media has the potential to gather significant organizational advantages, such as weaving community; encouraging greater openness and transparency; accelerating information-sharing; accessing more diverse perspectives; and mobilizing a workforce. There are also disadvantages of using social media to facilitate relational practices. These include the fact that "half-baked" ideas are made public, and those trying to manage workflows and processes must deal with concerns about brand and message control, privacy concerns, dealing with information overload, and learning the language. range of technology options and leveraging the right social media for one's purposes [2]. Some important questions are:

- How should we think about these broader trends with thinking about learning, teaching, and the incorporation of social media into education? To advance this conversation, it is good to synthesize what the educational research currently says about learning and social network, the dominant form of social media used by learners. The goal is to inform educational leaders, apprehensive or cautiously optimistic about learners' media-using practices.
- What are learners' purposes and practices with social network sites, and are they doing anything of educational value?

- How might these understandings help us to design for wider civic participation, increasingly sophisticated interactions, and accomplishments, and deal with potential dangers?
- Are existing social networking technologies and attendant practices appropriated and/or re-envisioned and re-worked to produce improvements in areas of educational priority such as educational attainment, the development of science, math, and technology literacies, communication and twenty-first-century skills, and preparation for future work lives?

Two insights related to these questions are generated from a review of the educational literature [58], from explorations of learners (ages 16-24) use of the social network sites MySpace and Facebook [67], [73], [58] and an ongoing investigation of learners use of an open-source social networking application, implemented within Facebook, and designed for informal science learning and civic action. At the end of the investigation, it was found that learners would adapt the spaces they frequent for their educational-related purposes, as well as school-related activities. What is surprising is the presence of these behaviors and beliefs even among most of our students, a group understudied in the educational technology literature and presumably experiencing more barriers to (but potentially more to gain from) participating in social network sites where such social media are typically blocked-in schools and public libraries [58].

Furthermore, where such informal sharing, peer validation and feedback, alumni support, and spontaneous help with school-related tasks has typically occurred offline, pre-dating the internet, these social processes, moved online into social network sites, can now be archived and tracked with social graphing software. In theory, we should be able to begin to identify what learning resources exactly are moving through the network, to and from whom, and with what impacts over time [119]. Moreover, educational designers might think about how some of the socio-technical features most utilized in naturally occurring, learners social network sites, like MySpace (e.g., multimedia identity-posting capabilities, frequent updating, and sharing of microcontent, social search, linking users with content contributions, annotation, ranking, recommendation systems) could be incorporated into the personalized learning systems touted in the Educational Technology Plan of the institution.

H. Empirical Study of Online Social Networks

In everyday life, we make informal observations of the people and things around us, and use these observations as basis for making decisions [40]. In educational institutions for example, a teacher might observe that his or her students seem bored and decide to switch to a livelier instructional activity. A study in [5] on informal learning networks in the workplace and their impact on professional growth was done. In this study, it was noted that most of the participants (school leaders) in the study had limited knowledge of what

instructors daily study entail. This implies the need for raising awareness about the value of informal learning. Another study in [3] also underscores the need for n facilitating informal professional development networks and the need for creating a framework on it. The study noted that informal organizations support and activities are critical to effective organizational transformation and innovation. An innovative approach in [3] created the change mirror research technique to identify informal networks and reflect their voices and views of the company. Using social networks analysis (SNA) the approach first raises awareness of the presence of the informal networks. Second, utilizing group discussion software, the technique elicits information about what the networks are all about, and by combining the two stages it significantly simplifies the understanding of change process in companies.

In the context of networked learning, the change mirror method in an organization was used to examine how well it fits with the goal of detecting informal professional development networks. Using a multi-method framework (fig 6) the goal was to get a better understanding of networked learning processes in a realistic environment [51, 84]. The multi-method framework triangulates SNA to find out “who is talking to whom,” content analysis (CA) to find out “what they are talking about,” and contextual analysis (CxA), focusing on the context of the organization the participants are working in to find out “why they are talking as they do.” The change mirror method with a three-step research design is described as follows:

Fig 6: Multi-method research framework for studying networked learning; source: [46]

Step 1—SNA (Social Network Analysis): This is used to determine who is talking to whom about an issue. This phase visualizes existing informal networks where experts cooperate on a specific issue and illustrates how linked (or not) they are throughout the whole organization. This is accomplished via the use of an online survey.

Step 2—CA (Content Analysis): The next stage is to figure out what these networks are talking about, as well as their opinions and views regarding the issue. Synthetron, a group discussion tool, is used for this. Everyone takes part in an asynchronous online conversation where they may share and discuss their thoughts and experiences with this work-related issue. The application allows you to analyze the whole conversation as well as the logged data.

Step 3—CxA (Contextual Analysis): This phase is to figure out how and why these networks act the way they do in their informal settings. CxA is based on focus groups, interviews, which may assist in understanding the impact that certain networks may have on the organization and give weight to the "voices" that exist inside these networks. We can create a clear picture of the possibility for networks to start working together or sharing information and resources by integrating the findings of the survey and the Synthetron conversation

with the input from the research teams. Such findings suggest that after identifying informal networks (Step 1), there may be a desire to link the networks (Steps 2 and 3). The important characters in these networks may be seen as latent connections [25], bridging the gap between the organization's presently disconnected networks. The ability to link these spontaneous informal learning networks will improve knowledge sharing and productive learning across the business. Despite believing in the potential of informal professional development networks, the study team observed that the visualization process and attempts to bring these networks closer together were time-consuming. They also discovered that local management at the participating schools misinterpreted their job as a member of the study team, as well as their motivations for doing so. They discovered that school leaders struggled to grasp what informal networks are and how they support professional growth in discussions with local management.

III. CONCLUSION

This paper provided a comprehensive review of Learning Analytics (LA), Educational Data Mining (EDM) and Online Social Networks (OSN) and some interesting current best practices. Imperatively, this kind of study goes a long way in informing education stakeholders on the significance of establishing a teaching and learning agenda that takes advantage of today's educational relevant technologies to promote learning while also acknowledging the difficulties of 21st-century learning. From the extensive reviews, it appears that there is lack of research understanding in the challenges and utilization of data effectively for learning analytics, despite the massive educational data generated by high institutions. Also due to the growing importance of LA, there appears to be a serious lack of academic research that explore the application and impact of LA in high institution, especially in the context of informal online social network learning. In addition, high institution managers seem not to understand the emerging trends of LA which could be useful in the running of higher education. Though LA is viewed as a complex and expensive technology that will culturally change the future of high institution, the question that comes to mind is whether the use of LA in relation to informal learning in online social network is really what is expected? A study to analyze and evaluate the elements that influence high usage of OSN is also needed in the African context. It is high time African Universities paid attention to the application and use of these technologies to create a simplified learning approach occasioned by the use of these technologies.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge all sources used in this paper.

REFERENCES

- 1 J. Furlong and C. Davies, 'Young people, new technologies and learning at home: Taking context seriously', *Oxford Review of Education*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 45–62, 2012.

- 2 D. Searce, G. Kasper, and H. M. Grant, 'Working wikily', *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 30–37, 2010.
- 3 T. H. Homan, *Wolkenridders: over de binnenkant van organisatieverandering*. Open Universiteit Nederland, 2006.
- 4 L. Hamilton, *What Facebook users share: Lower grandes*. Time. 2009.
- 5 M. De Laat and B. Schreurs, 'Visualizing informal professional development networks: Building a case for learning analytics in the workplace', *American Behavioral Scientist*, vol. 57, no. 10, pp. 1421–1438, 2013.
- 6 D. Ifenthaler and J. Y.-K. Yau, 'Utilising learning analytics to support study success in higher education: a systematic review', *Educational Technology Research and Development*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 1961–1990, 2020.
- 7 Y. Yang, Q. Wang, H. L. Woo, and C. L. Quek, 'Using Facebook for teaching and learning: a review of the literature', *International Journal of Continuing Engineering Education and Life Long Learning*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 72–86, 2011.
- 8 P. Mahajan, 'Use of social networking in a linguistically and culturally rich India', *The International Information & Library Review*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 129–136, 2009.
- 9 O. L. S. BUREAU, 'US department of Labor', *College Enrollment and Work Activity of 2013 High School Graduates*, 2007.
- 10 E. B. Kozleski, D. Gibson, and A. Hynds, 'Transforming complex educational systems: Grounding systems issues in equity and social justice', *Defining social justice leadership in a global context*, pp. 263–286, 2012.
- 11 R. Hammad and D. Ludlow, 'Towards a smart learning environment for smart city governance', in *Proceedings of the 9th international conference on utility and cloud computing*, 2016, pp. 185–190.
- 12 R. S. Baker and K. Yacef, 'The state of educational data mining in 2009: A review and future visions', *Journal of educational data mining*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 3–17, 2009.
- 13 J. A. Reyes, 'The skinny on big data in education: Learning analytics simplified', *TechTrends*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 75–80, 2015.
- 14 D. Laurillard, 'The pedagogical challenges to collaborative technologies', *International Journal of Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 5–20, 2009.
- 15 K. Gibson, 'The moral basis of stakeholder theory', *Journal of business ethics*, pp. 245–257, 2000.
- 16 R. L. Cross, R. L. Cross, and A. Parker, *The hidden power of social networks: Understanding how work really gets done in organizations*. Harvard Business Press, 2004.
- 17 C. Thille, E. Schneider, R. F. Kizilcec, C. Piech, S. A. Halawa, and D. K. Greene, *The future of data-enriched assessment. Research & Practice in Assessment*, 9 (2), 5–16. 2014.
- 18 A. G. Picciano, 'The evolution of big data and learning analytics in American higher education.', *Journal of asynchronous learning networks*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 9–20, 2012.
- 19 J. Wellings and M. H. Levine, 'The digital promise: Transforming learning with innovative uses of technology', 2009.
- 21 L. Johnson, S. Adams, and M. Cummins, *Technology outlook for Australian tertiary education 2012-2017: An NMC Horizon Report regional analysis*. The New Media Consortium, 2012.
- 22 J. Dron and T. Anderson, *Teaching crowds: Learning and*

- social media. Athabasca University Press, 2014.
- 23 S. Sergis and D. G. Sampson, 'Teaching and learning analytics to support teacher inquiry: A systematic literature review', *Learning analytics: Fundamentals, applications, and trends*, pp. 25–63, 2017.
- 24 D. Ifenthaler and C. Schumacher, 'Student perceptions of privacy principles for learning analytics', *Educational Technology Research and Development*, vol. 64, no. 5, pp. 923–938, 2016.
- 25 C. Haythornthwaite, 'Strong, weak, and latent ties and the impact of new media', *The information society*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 385–401, 2002.
- 26 H. Roreger and T. C. Schmidt, 'Socialize online learning: Why we should integrate learning content management with Online Social Networks', in *2012 IEEE International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications Workshops*, 2012, pp. 685–690.
- 27 J. Bruggeman, *Social networks: An introduction*. Routledge, 2013.
- 28 C. Haythornthwaite and M. De Laat, 'Social networks and learning networks: Using social network perspectives to understand social learning', in *Proceedings of the 7th international conference on networked learning*, 2010, pp. 183–190.
- 29 J. Williams, 'Social networking applications in health care: threats to the privacy and security of health information', in *Proceedings of the 2010 ICSE workshop on software engineering in health care*, 2010, pp. 39–49.
- 30 D. M. Boyd and N. B. Ellison, 'Social network sites: Definition, history, and scholarship', *Journal of computer mediated Communication*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 210–230, 2007.
- 31 H. Tankovska, *Social media-Statistics & Facts*. Statista. Com. <https://www.statista.com/topics/1164/social-networks>, 2021. Last Accessed 2021/09/15
- 32 S. B. Shum and R. Ferguson, 'Social learning analytics', *Journal of educational technology & society*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 3–26, 2012.
- 33 S. Dawson, O. Poquet, C. Colvin, T. Rogers, A. Pardo, and D. Gasevic, 'Rethinking learning analytics adoption through complexity leadership theory', in *Proceedings of the 8th international conference on learning analytics and knowledge*, 2018, pp. 236–244.
- 34 D. W. Livingstone, 'Researching expanded notions of learning and work and underemployment: Findings of the first Canadian survey of informal learning practices', *International Review of Education*, vol. 46, no. 6, pp. 491–514, 2000.
- 35 J. Osborne and J. Dillon, *Research on learning in informal contexts: Advancing the field?* Taylor & Francis, 2007.
- 36 M. Rost, L. Barkhuus, H. Cramer, and B. Brown, 'Representation and communication: Challenges in interpreting large social media datasets', in *Proceedings of the 2013 conference on Computer supported cooperative work*, 2013, pp. 357–362.
- 37 F. A. Hrabowski III and J. Suess, 'Reclaiming the lead: higher education's future and implications for technology', *UMBC Office of the Vice President of Information Technology*, 2010.
- 38 D. Boud and P. Hager, 'Re-thinking continuing professional development through changing metaphors and location in professional practices', *Studies in continuing education*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 17–30, 2012.
- 39 E. Lazega, 'Rationalité, discipline sociale et structure', *Revue française de sociologie*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 305–329, 2003.
- 40 M. Patten, *Questionnaire research: A practical guide*. Routledge, 2016.
- 41 M. Scheffel, H. Drachler, S. Stoyanov, and M. Specht, 'Quality indicators for learning analytics', *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 117–132, 2014.
- 42 J. Clarke and K. Nelson, 'Perspectives on learning analytics: issues and challenges. Observations from Shane Dawson and Phil Long', *The International Journal of the First Year in Higher Education*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2013.
- 43 N. Dabbagh and A. Kitsantas, 'Personal Learning Environments, social media, and self-regulated learning: A natural formula for connecting formal and informal learning', *The Internet and higher education*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 3–8, 2012.
- 44 G. Siemens and P. Long, 'Penetrating the fog: Analytics in learning and education.', *EDUCAUSE review*, vol. 46, no. 5, p. 30, 2011.
- 45 L. P. Macfadyen, 'Overcoming barriers to educational analytics: How systems thinking and pragmatism can help', *Educational Technology*, pp. 31–39, 2017.
- 46 M. De Laat, V. Lally, L. Lipponen, and R.-J. Simons, 'Online teaching in networked learning communities: A multi-method approach to studying the role of the teacher', *Instructional Science*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 257–286, 2007.
- 47 G. Veletsianos and C. Navarrete, 'Online social networks as formal learning environments: Learner experiences and activities', *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 144–166, 2012.
- 48 L. M. Miller and D. D. Prior, 'Online social networks and friending behaviour: A self-determination theory perspective', in *Proceedings of the Australia and New Zealand Marketing Academy Annual Conference, Christchurch, New Zealand*, 2010, pp. 1–9.
- 49 C. Steinfield, N. B. Ellison, C. Lampe, and J. Vitak, 'Online social network sites and the concept of social capital', in *Frontiers in new media research*, Routledge, 2013, pp. 122–138.
- 50 M. Warschauer and T. Matuchniak, 'New technology and digital worlds: Analyzing evidence of equity in access, use, and outcomes', *Review of research in education*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 179–225, 2010.
- 51 M. De Laat, 'Networked learning', 2006.
- 52 S. P. Borgatti, A. Mehra, D. J. Brass, and G. Labianca, 'Network analysis in the social sciences', *science*, vol. 323, no. 5916, pp. 892–895, 2009.
- 53 P. Blikstein and M. Worsley, 'Multimodal learning analytics and education data mining: Using computational technologies to measure complex learning tasks', *Journal of Learning Analytics*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 220–238, 2016.
- 54 S. Cetintas, L. Si, H. P. Aagard, K. Bowen, and M. Cordova-Sanchez, 'Microblogging in a classroom: Classifying students' relevant and irrelevant questions in a microblogging-supported classroom', *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 292–300, 2011.
- 55 A. Karpinski, 'Media sensationalization of social science research: Social networking insites', *Teachers College Record*, 2009.
- 56 L. Naismith, P. Lonsdale, G. Vavoula, and M. Sharples, 'Literature Review in Mobile. 5', *RESULTADOS Technologies and Learning*, 2004.
- 57 J. Sefton-Green, 'Literature review in informal learning with

- technology outside school', 2004.
- 58 C. Greenhow, B. Robelia, and J. E. Hughes, 'Learning, teaching, and scholarship in a digital age: Web 2.0 and classroom research: What path should we take now?', *Educational researcher*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 246–259, 2009.
- 59 A. Merceron, P. Blikstein, and G. Siemens, 'Learning analytics: From big data to meaningful data', *Journal of Learning Analytics*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 4–8, 2015.
- 60 N. Slater, A. Peasgood, and J. Mullan, *Learning analytics in higher education: A review of UK and international practice Full report, Educause 39 (2016)*.
- 61 Z. K. Papamitsiou and A. A. Economides, 'Learning analytics and educational data mining in practice: A systematic literature review of empirical evidence.', *J. Educ. Technol. Soc.*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 49–64, 2014.
- 62 G. Cormode and B. Krishnamurthy, 'Key differences between Web 1.0 and Web 2.0', *First Monday*, 2008.
- 63 N. Carr, 'Is Google making us stupid: What the Internet is doing to our brains', 2008.
- 64 S. Sergis, D. G. Sampson, and L. Pelliccione, 'Investigating the impact of Flipped Classroom on students' learning experiences: A Self-Determination Theory approach', *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 78, pp. 368–378, 2018.
- 65 B. Barron, 'Interest and self-sustained learning as catalysts of development: A learning ecology perspective', *Human development*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 193–224, 2006.
- 66 D. Ifenthaler, D. Gibson, and E. Dobozy, 'Informing learning design through analytics: Applying network graph analysis', *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, vol. 34, no. 2, 2018.
- 67 C. Greenhow and B. Robelia, 'Informal learning and identity formation in online social networks', *Learning, media and technology*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 119–140, 2009.
- 68 M. Callanan, C. Cervantes, and M. Loomis, 'Informal learning', *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Cognitive Science*, vol. 2, no. 6, pp. 646–655, 2011.
- 69 S. Kerka, 'Incidental Learning. Trends and Issues Alert No. 18.', 2000.
- 70 N. Kvartranyi, *Impact of big data on education: history, benefits and examples*. 2020.
- 71 K.-W. Lai, 'ICT supporting the learning process: The premise, reality, and promise', in *International handbook of information technology in primary and secondary education*, Springer, 2008, pp. 215–230.
- 72 G. Siemens, 'How data and analytics can improve education, July 2011', *Retrieved on August*, vol. 8, 2011.
- 73 C. Greenhow and L. Burton, 'Help from my "friends": Social capital in the social network sites of low-income students', *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, vol. 45, no. 2, pp. 223–245, 2011.
- 74 V. J. Rideout, U. G. Foehr, and D. F. Roberts, 'Generation m 2: Media in the lives of 8-to 18-year-olds.', *Henry J. Kaiser Family Foundation*, 2010.
- 75 B. Czerkawski and J. N. Hernández, 'Formal, non-formal, and informal e-learning experiences with emerging technologies: a case study of a Graduate Educational Technology Program', in *Cases on formal and informal e-learning environments: Opportunities and practices*, IGI Global, 2013, pp. 337–355.
- 76 S. Kilis, Y. Gülbahar, and C. Rapp, 'Exploration of teaching preferences of instructors' use of social media', *European Journal of Open, Distance and E-learning*, vol. 19, no. 1, 2016.
- 77 M. Bienkowski, M. Feng, and B. Means, 'Enhancing Teaching and Learning through Educational Data Mining and Learning Analytics: An Issue Brief.', *Office of Educational Technology, US Department of Education*, 2012.
- 78 C. J. Atman *et al.*, 'Enabling engineering student success: The final report for the Center for the Advancement of Engineering Education', *San Rafael, CA: Morgan & Claypool Publishers*, 2010.
- 79 L. C. Giles, G. F. Glonek, M. A. Luszcz, and G. R. Andrews, 'Effect of social networks on 10 year survival in very old Australians: the Australian longitudinal study of aging', *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*, vol. 59, no. 7, pp. 574–579, 2005.
- 80 P. J. Piety, D. T. Hickey, and M. J. Bishop, 'Educational data sciences: Framing emergent practices for analytics of learning, organizations, and systems', in *Proceedings of the fourth international conference on learning analytics and knowledge*, 2014, pp. 193–202.
- 81 B. Bakhshinategh, O. R. Zaiane, S. ElAtia, and D. Ipperciel, 'Educational data mining applications and tasks: A survey of the last 10 years', *Education and Information Technologies*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 537–553, 2018.
- 82 C. Romero and S. Ventura, 'Educational data mining and learning analytics: An updated survey', *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, vol. 10, no. 3, p. e1355, 2020.
- 83 R. Zhou, 'Education web information retrieval and classification with big data analysis', *Creative Education*, vol. 7, no. 18, p. 2868, 2016.
- 84 D. A. Erlandson, E. L. Harris, B. L. Skipper, and S. D. Allen, *Doing naturalistic inquiry: A guide to methods*. Sage, 1993.
- 85 R. F. Kizilcec and C. Brooks, 'Diverse big data and randomized field experiments in massive open online courses: Opportunities for advancing learning research', *G. siemens & c. lang (eds.), handbook on learning analytics & educational data mining*, 2017.
- 86 K.-W. Lai, 'Digital technology and the culture of teaching and learning in higher education', *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, vol. 27, no. 8, 2011.
- 87 D. Ifenthaler, *Designing effective digital learning environments: toward learning analytics design*. Springer, 2017.
- 88 R. centre Domo, 'Data Never Sleeps 9.0', *Domo*, 2021. <https://www.domo.com/learn/infographic/data-never-sleeps-9> (accessed Oct. 19, 2021).
- 89 K. J. Cios, W. Pedrycz, R. W. Swiniarski, and L. A. Kurgan, *Data mining: a knowledge discovery approach*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2007.
- 90 E. Wagner and P. Ice, 'Data changes everything: Delivering on the promise of learning analytics in higher education.', *Educause Review*, vol. 47, no. 4, p. 32, 2012.
- 91 S. Dawson, D. Gašević, G. Siemens, and S. Joksimovic, 'Current state and future trends: A citation network analysis of the learning analytics field', in *Proceedings of the fourth international conference on learning analytics and knowledge*, 2014, pp. 231–240.
- 92 D. R. Garrison, T. Anderson, and W. Archer, 'Critical thinking, cognitive presence, and computer conferencing in distance education', *American Journal of distance education*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 7–23, 2001.
- 93 J. Han, M. Kamber, and D. Mining, 'Concepts and techniques', *Morgan Kaufmann*, vol. 340, pp. 94104–3205, 2006.

- 93 C. Shirky, *Cognitive surplus: Creativity and generosity in a connected age*. Penguin UK, 2010.
- 94 R. Besbes and S. Besbes, 'Cognitive dashboard for teachers professional development', in *Qatar Foundation Annual Research Conference Proceedings Volume 2016 Issue 1*, 2016, vol. 2016, no. 1, p. ICTPP2984.
- 95 J. Voogt, O. Erstad, C. Dede, and P. Mishra, 'Challenges to learning and schooling in the digital networked world of the 21st century', *Journal of computer assisted learning*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 403–413, 2013.
- 96 H. Chen, R. H. Chiang, and V. C. Storey, 'Business intelligence and analytics: From big data to big impact', *MIS quarterly*, pp. 1165–1188, 2012.
- 97 A. Hofstein and S. Rosenfeld, 'Bridging the gap between formal and informal science learning', 1996.
- 98 H. Eshach, 'Bridging in-school and out-of-school learning: Formal, non-formal, and informal education', *Journal of science education and technology*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 171–190, 2007.
- 99 F. A. Hrabowski III, *Boosting minorities in science*. American Association for the Advancement of Science, 2011.
- 100 K.-W. Lai, F. Khaddage, and G. Knezek, 'Blending student technology experiences in formal and informal learning', *Journal of computer assisted learning*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 414–425, 2013.
- 101 A. McAfee, E. Brynjolfsson, T. H. Davenport, D. J. Patil, and D. Barton, 'Big data: the management revolution', *Harvard business review*, vol. 90, no. 10, pp. 60–68, 2012.
- 102 N. Khan *et al.*, 'Big data: survey, technologies, opportunities, and challenges', *The scientific world journal*, vol. 2014, 2014.
- 103 M. Giacalone and S. Scippacercola, 'BIG DATA: ISSUES AND AN OVERVIEW IN SOME STRATEGIC SECTORS.', *Journal of Applied Quantitative Methods*, vol. 11, no. 3, 2016.
- 104 B. K. Daniel, 'Big data in higher education: The big picture', in *Big data and learning analytics in higher education*, Springer, 2017, pp. 19–28.
- 105 S. Erevelles, N. Fukawa, and L. Swayne, 'Big Data consumer analytics and the transformation of marketing', *Journal of business research*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 897–904, 2016.
- 106 A. BAGHA and V. Madisetti, *Big Data Analytics: A Hands-On Approach*. USA: Arshdeep Bahga & Vijay Madisetti, 2019.
- 107 A. IBM, 'Big data analytics', *IBM*, 2021. <https://www.ibm.com/analytics/hadoop/big-data-analytics> (accessed Oct. 19, 2021).
- 108 W. Clark, K. Logan, R. Luckin, A. Mee, and M. Oliver, 'Beyond Web 2.0: Mapping the technology landscapes of young learners', *Journal of computer assisted learning*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 56–69, 2009.
- 109 D. Clow, 'An overview of learning analytics', *Teaching in Higher Education*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 683–695, 2013.
- 110 N. Rushby, 'An agenda for mobile learning.', *British Journal of Educational Technology*, vol. 43, no. 3, pp. 355–356, 2012.
- 111 M. Clark *et al.*, 'Academic pathways study: Processes and realities', in *2008 Annual Conference & Exposition*, 2008, p. 13.137. 1-13.137. 23.
- 112 J. P. Campbell, P. B. DeBlois, and D. G. Oblinger, 'Academic analytics: A new tool for a new era', *EDUCAUSE review*, vol. 42, no. 4, p. 40, 2007.
- 113 A. Nouira, L. Cheniti Belcadhi, and R. Braham, 'An ontology based framework of assessment analytics for massive learning', *Computer Applications in Engineering Education*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 1343–1360, 2019.
- 114 Z.-H. Zhou, 'Learnware: on the future of machine learning.', *Frontiers Comput. Sci.*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 589–590, 2016.
- 115 R. S. Burt, 'Network items and the general social survey', *Social networks*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 293–339, 1984.
- 116 F. Henri, 'Computer conferencing and content analysis', in *Collaborative learning through computer conferencing*, Springer, 1992, pp. 117–136.
- 117 A. I. Kiser and T. Porter, 'Social networking: Integrating students and university professor utilization', in *Global Conference on Business and Finance Proceedings*, 2011, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 191–196.
- 118 S. ElAtia and D. Ipperciel, 'Learning Analytics and Education Data Mining in Higher Education', in *Advancing the Power of Learning Analytics and Big Data in Education*, IGI Global, 2021, pp. 108–126.
- 119 D. Lazer *et al.*, 'Social science. Computational social science.', *Science (New York, NY)*, vol. 323, no. 5915, pp. 721–723, 2009.
- 120 Okike, E. U., & Mgorosi, M. (n.d.). *Educational Data Mining for Monitoring and Improving Academic Performance at University Levels. Environments*, 4, 5.

Design and Development of an Autonomous Car using Object Detection with YOLOv4

Rishabh Chopda
Department Of Computer Engineering
Thakur College of Engineering &
Technology
Mumbai, India
aaditchopda2@gmail.com

Saket Pradhan
Department of Information Technology
Thakur College Of Engineering &
Technology
Mumbai, India
saketspradhan@gmail.com

Anuj Goenka
Department Of Computer Engineering
Thakur College of Engineering &
Technology
Mumbai, India
anujgoenka06@gmail.com

Abstract—Future cars are anticipated to be driverless; point-to-point transportation services capable of avoiding fatalities. To achieve this goal, auto-manufacturers have been investing to realize the potential autonomous driving. In this regard, we present a self-driving model car capable of autonomous driving using object-detection as a primary means of steering, on a track made of colored cones. This paper goes through the process of fabricating a model vehicle, from its embedded hardware platform, to the end-to-end ML pipeline necessary for automated data acquisition and model-training, thereby allowing a Deep Learning model to derive input from the hardware platform to control the car’s movements. This guides the car autonomously and adapts well to real-time tracks without manual feature-extraction. This paper presents a Computer Vision model that learns from video data and involves Image Processing, Augmentation, Behavioral Cloning and a Convolutional Neural Network model. The Darknet architecture is used to detect objects through a video segment and convert it into a 3D navigable path. Finally, the paper touches upon the conclusion, results and scope of future improvement in the technique used.

Keywords—autonomous, self-driving, computer vision, YOLO, object detection, embedded hardware

I. INTRODUCTION

A ‘Self-Driving Car’ is one that is able to sense its immediate surroundings and operate independently without human intervention. The main motivation behind the topic at hand is the expeditious progress of applied Artificial Intelligence and the foreseeable significance of autonomous driving ventures in the future of humanity, from independent mobility for non-drivers to cheap transportation services to low-income individuals. The emergence of driverless cars and their amalgamation with electric cars promises to help minimize road fatalities, air and small-particle pollution, being able to better manage parking spaces, and free people from the mundane and monotonous task of having to sit behind the wheel. Autonomous navigation holds quite a lot of promise as it offers a range of applications going far beyond a car driven autonomously. The main effort here is to keep the humans out of the vehicle control loop and to relieve them from the task of driving. The prime requisite of self-driving vehicles are the visual sensors (for acquiring traffic insight of vehicle surroundings), microprocessors or computers (for processing the sensor information and transmitting vehicle control instructions) and actuators (to receive said instructions and be responsible for the longitudinal and lateral control of the car) [1-4]. Autonomous vehicles are also expected to be manoeuvred in many of the most complex human planned endeavours, such as asteroid mining [5]. The meteoric rise of AI along with deep learning

(DL) methods and frameworks, have made possible the development of such autonomous vehicles by many venture companies at the same time.

II. SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT

A. Data Collection & Labelling

Around 2,000 images were collected for two types of coloured cones, namely: Orange and Blue. The cones were made from craft paper and were 4.5 centimetres tall with a base diameter of 3cm. The pictures included the cones laid out as track, single colour cones, multiple same-coloured cones and a mix of the two cones. A total of 16,382 cones were observed in the collected images with Labellmg being later used to label these cones from the images. ‘Labellmg’ is a graphical image annotation tool [6]. It is written in Python and uses Qt for its graphical interface. The Labellmg tool was used to label the photographed images in the YOLO format by drawing bounding boxes around the cones and naming each cone with their respective class i.e., colour (orange or blue). After labelling via Labellmg, a common class file was created to all images which contained the two classes “Orange” and “Blue”. Another file was created unique to each image which contained the coordinates of each cone present in that image. For example, 1 0.490809 0.647894 0.235628 0.342580 is an entry from the class file created where the first parameter determines the class of the cones, the second and third parameters determine the midpoint of the bounding box while the fourth and fifth parameters determine the height and width of the bounding box. For the randomization and renaming of the images, a software tool called ‘Rename Expert’ was used. It randomized the images and then named them from 0-1681. Data augmentation was used to increase the amount of data by adding slightly modified copies of already existing data. It involves injecting some noise, rotation and flipping of the images to increase the number of images used for training. It usually helps in preventing overfitting the model and acts as a regularizer [7].

B. Model Training

YOLOv4 Tiny, a version of YOLOv4 developed for edge and lower-power devices, is a real-time object detection algorithm capable of detecting and providing bounding boxes for many different objects in a single image [8-11]. The model achieves this by dividing an image into regions and then predicting bounding boxes in addition to the probabilities for each region. Relative to inference speed, YOLOv4 outperforms other object detection models by a significant margin. We needed a model that prioritizes real-

time detection and conducts the training on a single GPU as well. 'Darknet' is a framework like the TensorFlow, PyTorch and Keras that proved to be apt for the task at hand. While Darknet is not as intuitive to use, it is immensely flexible, and it advances state-of-the-art object detection results. We train the model on darknet and then later convert it to TensorFlow for ease in usability. This model can be tested on a physical model or on virtual simulators [12-15]. In terms of training the model, the labelled dataset was segregated into training and validation datasets and was uploaded on cloud VM. After that, the darknet was cloned and built on which the model was trained. The parameters were configured periodically to achieve the best weights. It was important that we convert our darknet framework into TensorFlow because only then could we make use of the TensorFlow lite model which is optimized for embedded devices such as Jetson Nano to make the inference at the edge.

C. Deployment

Deployment includes reading the coordinate text data generated from the YOLO4 model into a NumPy framework and labelling the coordinate points according to the two classes, blue and orange. This is done by iterating through the text data line by line, and appending the required point objects into a python array, and finally converting the array into a NumPy format. Matplotlib is used to visualize the set of data points from the camera's perspective, on a 10 x 10 cm² adjusted screen. Using the Scikit-Learn Library, a Linear Regression model is trained using the NumPy data. Two different models are to be trained; one for the blue set of cones, and one for the orange cones. Again, a graph is plotted of Matplotlib for visual aid of the lines. Next, the equations of the previously formed lines are derived using simple geometric calculations. Straight line equations of the type: $ax + by + c = 0$ are obtained for both blue and orange lines. Next, the point of intersection of the two lines is calculated using the formula of point of intersection. The offset of this line is calculated from the centre of the screen and the x-coordinate of each point is subtracted by the corresponding point on the centre of the screen. This value is the mean deviation and will be used further to calculate the angle by which servo attached on the assembly is to be turned. Fig. 1 shows the outcome of the entire video capture and path mapping process.

Fig. 1 Video capture and path mapping process

III. HARDWARE DESIGN

Before The car was designed and built with the proper placement and positioning of electronic components, such as the camera, in mind. It consists of three main parts, the steering assembly, the spur gear gearbox and the wheels. The steering system has a rack and pinion type design, chosen for its simple assembly and for providing easier and more compact control over the car. A 3-sided gear box ensures the effortless placement and positioning of the axles and larger gears. Given the opposing forces caused by the axles and front chassis, it also stays strong and sturdy. Spur gears are used in the gear box as they have high power transmission efficiencies (95% to 99%) and are simple to design and install. The wheels are designed and entirely 3D printed to have built-in suspension providing additional steering stability. Because the wheels must be flexible, TPU (Thermoplastic Polyurethane) is used to produce them. All other 3D printed components were produced using PLA (Polylactic acid) as it's easy to use, has a remarkably low printing temperature compared to other thermoplastics and produces better surface details and sharper features. A list of all materials is given below:

List Of Materials: All components required for the prototype, including sensors, actuators, power supply, and hardware, are listed here. Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show all the 3D printed parts and their assembly in SolidWorks Simscape respectively.

- 3D Printed Parts
- 608zz Bearings (4x)
- Nvidia Jetson Nano
- 1200KV Brushless DC Motor
- 20A ESC (Electronic Speed Controller)
- 5000mAh Power Bank
- 11.1V - 2200MAH (Lithium Polymer) LiPo Rechargeable Battery

- PCA9685 16 Channel Servo Driver
- TowerPro SG90 180° Rotation Servo Motor
- Logitech C615 HD Webcam

Fig. 2 3D Printed parts

Fig. 3 Car assembly on Solidworks Simscape

IV. FUNCTIONALITY

A Nvidia Jetson Nano single-board computer (SBC) serves as both the brain and the communication node in the prototype control system. This SBC receives data from the camera, analyses them, and integrates them into the navigation system to determine the steering angle. A 11.1V - 2200mAh LiPo battery is used solely to power the vehicle's propulsion system, that is, the 1200KV Brushless DC Motor with a 20A ESC. A 180° rotation servo motor with a torque of 1.2KgCm, controlled by the PCA9685 16 Channel Servo Driver, is used to steer the car. Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 show a flowchart of the instruction feedback loop and a schematic diagram of the hardware connections respectively. Fig. 6 shows the entire assembled car.

Fig. 4 Flowchart of the instruction feedback loop

Fig. 5 Circuit Diagram

Fig. 6 Assembled Car

V. CONCLUSION

Through this paper, we present an approach for designing and building a model self-driving car based on the concept of Behavioural Cloning. This approach being an end-to-end one does not require any of the conventional tasks of feature extraction or connection of various modules, which are often monotonous, manual in nature and necessary for efficient working. Our model car is tried and tested in real life against various standard models such as DenseNet-201, Resnet-50, and VGG19 for the comparison and performance. The final proposed model is a convolution-based, ten 2D-Convolutional Layers, one Flat Layer and four Dense Layers model. When compared with other Deep Learning based models, our model seems to have outperformed all of the aforementioned standard models by a substantial margin. The work presented through this paper can be realized to build vehicles capable of autonomous

steering and driving. Additional training data of real-world obstacles with different track situations and conditions may be required to increase the agility and robustness of the system.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

Through this project, we aimed to provide proof of concept for self-driving cars that can solely rely on vision-based object detection techniques for navigation, rather than the conventional feature extraction-based lane detection techniques. Results obtained on our model car made it clear that our approach towards object detection as a means of steering has either outclassed or is at-par with humans in the parameters being tested for. Reinforcement learning methods can be introduced in addition to this method to better performance. This method can be used as a prototype for future citywide self-driving cars projects. It can also be used exclusively, or in addition to conventional lane detection, to further improve on accuracy of self-driving cars. Via these techniques, automobiles might truly serve as end-to-end personal transportation devices and may give rise to an entire ecosystem of car-pooling or car sharing services as well as numerous start-ups thereby making personal transport cheaper, faster and safer. However, when implementing in the real world, many more parameters might be introduced which may increase the complexity of such a system while affecting the performance of the car.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Endres, J. Hess, J. Sturm, D. Cremers, and W. Burgard, "3-d mapping with an rgb-d camera," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 177–187, 2014.
- [2] M. Tipping, M. Hatton, and R. Herbrich, "Racing line optimization," in *US Patent*, March 2013.
- [3] L. Cardamone, D. Loiacono, P. Lanzi, and A. Bardelli, "Searching for the optimal racing line using genetic algorithms," in *Computational Intelligence and Games (CIG)*, August 2010.
- [4] K. Kritayakirana and J. C. Gerdes, "Using the centre of percussion to design a steering controller for an autonomous race car," *Vehicle System Dynamics*, vol. 50, no. sup1, pp. 33–51, 2012.
- [5] H. Fujiyoshi, T. Hirakawa, and T. Yamashita, "Deep learning-based image recognition for autonomous driving," *IATSS Research*. Elsevier B.V., Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.iatssr.2019.11.008.
- [6] darrenl, (2015) LabelImg (Version Window_v1.8.0) [Source code]. <https://github.com/tzutalin/labelImg>
- [7] C. Nwankpa, W. Ijomah, A. Gachagan, and S. Marshall, "Activation Functions: Comparison of trends in Practice and Research for Deep Learning," Nov. 2018.
- [8] S. Ren, K. He, R. Girshick, and J. Sun, "Faster R-CNN: Towards Real-Time Object Detection with Region Proposal Networks," *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 1137–1149, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TPAMI.2016.2577031.
- [9] R. Kulkarni, S. Dhavalikar, and S. Bangar, "Traffic Light Detection and Recognition for Self Driving Cars Using Deep Learning," *Proc. - 2018 4th Int. Conf. Comput. Commun. Control Autom. ICCUBEA 2018*, pp. 1–4, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ICCUBEA.2018.8697819.
- [10] A. K. Jain, "Working model of Self-driving car using Convolutional Neural Network, Raspberry Pi and Arduino," in *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology, ICECA 2018*, Sep. 2018, pp. 1630–1635, doi: 10.1109/ICECA.2018.8474620.
- [11] J. Kim, G. Lim, Y. Kim, B. Kim, and C. Bae, "Deep Learning Algorithm using Virtual Environment Data for Self-driving Car," in *1st International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Information and Communication, ICAIIC 2019*, Mar. 2019, pp. 444–448, doi: 10.1109/ICAIIIC.2019.8669037.
- [12] Y. Kang, H. Yin, and C. Berger, "Test Your Self-Driving Algorithm: An Overview of Publicly Available Driving Datasets and Virtual Testing Environments," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Veh.*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 171–185, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1109/tiv.2018.2886678.
- [13] S. Shah, D. Dey, C. Lovett, and A. Kapoor, "AirSim: High-Fidelity Visual and Physical Simulation for Autonomous Vehicles," 2018, pp. 621–635.
- [14] A. Dosovitskiy, G. Ros, F. Codevilla, A. Lopez, and V. Koltun, "CARLA: An Open Urban Driving Simulator," Nov. 2017.
- [15] B. Wymann, C. Dimitrakakis, A. Sumner, E. Espic, and C. Guionneau, "TORCS: The open racing car simulator," 2015.

IoT-based Peat Soil Heat Conduction Parameter Delivery System As Land Fire Mitigation Effort

Ade Agung Harnawan
Physics Study Programme
University of Lambung Mangkurat (ULM)
Banjarmasin, Indonesia
adeagungharnawan@ulm.ac.id

Nugroho Adi Pramono
Physics Departement
State University of Malang
Malang, Indonesia
nugroho.adi.fmipa@um.ac.id

Muhammad Itqan Mazdadi
Computer Science Study Programme
mazdadi@ulm.ac.id

Abstract— Mitigating peatland fires needs to be done because the handling is more complex than ordinary land fires because of the fire spread in the layers below its surface. One of the efforts is to create an IoT-based data parameter of peat heat conduction sending system that integrates with information systems using web technology. Some conduction parameter data is generated by a multisensory system delivered on IoT devices that use the raspberry pi as client-side. The data is transmitted to cloud hosting to be displayed in real-time on the Web as server-side. The interface software on both sides used PHP and MySQL scripts. This system can send 14 data on the conduction parameters of peat soil samples, consisting of seven sample temperature points, one heater temperature, four sample water content points, air temperature, and surface air humidity of samples. Then all these parameters are saved and displayed on the Web in real-time.

Keywords—component; delivery; IoT; mitigation; peatland fires; Raspberry Pi;

I. INTRODUCTION

Peat soil has good potential in agriculture, but several obstacles cause low productivity. The characteristics of peat soils are very distinctive. Namely, they are easy to dry, do not turn over, and experience subsidence under aerobic conditions. Irreversible dry conditions make peat soil repel water on its surface, so water cannot enter the lower layer of peat[1].

The observation system that has been done only on vegetation above the surface using GIS (Geographic Information System) has not reached the peat layer below the surface. To determine the temperature of peat when approaching burning in the soil from the surface required the value of peat heat conductance so that the characterization of peat soil heat conductance is expected to provide data on the relationship between the heat temperature in the peat soil and the heat temperature at the peat soil surface. In the first stage in determining the heat conduction of peat soil, it is necessary to measure several parameters, including temperature and water

content of peat soil by a multisensory system, then proceed with further data processing.

Peatland fire mitigation efforts are carried out by monitoring the main indicators of peat fire triggers, namely peat temperature below the surface and surface of the land, groundwater content, air temperature, and surface air humidity, and can be observed in real-time. This article is discussed one of the systems to deliver data parameters of peat soil heat conduction based on IoT integrated with the information system on the website.

A. The Multisensor System

In situ measurement of thermal properties of a northern peatland had been done to make a temperature model with dual-probe heat pulse sensors and triple-probe heat pulse sensors [2]. This measurement gives the idea of making a multisensory system. It shown in Fig. 1 has been developed to measure in situ several parameters of peat soil samples placed in a chamber with a height of 0.5 m. The first parameter is peat soil moisture content, consisting of 4 soil moisture sensors arranged vertically in the chamber[3]. Then the next parameter is the temperature of the peat soil, which is measured by eight sensors in total. Seven of which are used to measure the temperature of 7 depth points of the peat soil sample arranged vertically in the chamber and a temperature sensor to measure the temperature of the heater placed at the bottom of the room. In addition, the system is also equipped with measuring environmental conditions around the sample, which consists of air temperature and humidity. The explanation of code sensors and chamber in Fig. 1 is written in Table 1.

B. Raspberry Pi

Raspberry Pi, shortened to RPi, is like a computer system with a complete I/O for computer support equipment, such as USB port, HDMI port, ethernet, wifi, and so on [4]. A very useful feature of the RPi that strongly supports this research is General Purpose Input Output (GPIO). The GPIO supports doing the interface with other equipment connected with RPi.

Identify applicable sponsor/s here. (sponsors)

(a) Hardware (b) Sensors and chamber

Fig. 1 System multisensory

Table 1 SENSOR CODE

No.	Code	Sensor Type
1	St1	Heater temperature1
2	St2	Soil temperature2
3	St3	Soil temperature3
4	St4	Soil temperature4
5	St5	Soil temperature5
6	St6	Soil temperature6
7	St7	Soil temperature7
8	St8	Soil temperature8
9	Su9	Air temperature
10	Ku10	Air humidity
11	Kt11	Soil moisture 1
12	Kt12	Soil moisture 2
13	Kt13	Soil moisture 3
14	Kt14	Soil moisture 4

Fig. 2 Raspberry Pi [5]

Specification of RPi shown in Fig. 2 is The Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+ is the final revision in the Raspberry Pi 3, integrated with Broadcom BCM2837B0. The processor is Cortex-A53 (ARMv8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.4GHz, 1GB LPDDR2 SDRAM, 2.4GHz and 5GHz IEEE 802.11.b/g/n/ac wireless LAN, the wireless communication using Bluetooth 4.2, BLE Gigabit Ethernet over USB 2.0 (maximum throughput 300 Mbps), extended 40-pin GPIO header, and Full-size HDMI[5]. This device can be applied for general purposes.

The application of RPi as the main unit of a particular system has begun to be thought of because it can be used as the main device faster than a microcontroller even though the I/O device is limited. One of which is used to make decisions for three detection levels for drunk drivers[6]. The other is exposed to various cybercriminals and protects data [7], then monitors temperature[8].

C. IoT

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a set of heterogeneous connected devices that collaborate with the internet of services via the global network infrastructure [9]. IoT Application domains focus on nine domains: smart manufacturing or industrial, smart transportation/mobility, smart grid/energy, smart retail, smart cities, smart healthcare, smart supply chain, smart agriculture, and smart building/home[10], and IoT security issues emphasis on availability, authenticity, confidentiality, integrity, non-repudiation, and privacy[9]. The IoT applied here prefers smart agriculture, especially in disaster management.

D. Information System based on Web

Web-based technology is one of information and communication technology applications. The development of web technology is very fast, with both related devices and software-hardware devices associated with it.[11]

Web data framework, or web-based data framework, employs Web innovations to provide data and administrations to clients or other data systems/applications. It may be a code whose fundamental reason is to distribute and keep up information by utilizing hypertext-based standards [12]. A web data system usually comprises one or more web applications, particular functionality-oriented components, besides data components and other non-web components. The web browser is regularly utilized as front-end while the database is back-end.

The development of WBIS (web-based information system) is required a server with services like Web Server, Database Services, Messaging Services, Mailing Services, and Collaboration Services [13].

II. HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION

The data of peat heat conduction sending systems are composed of IoT devices and web-based information systems. To apply this, then in simple term shown in Fig. 3. The multisensory system is connected to the IoT device via wireless media, and then the data is sent to the information system on the Web. In this article, the multisensory systems will not be discussed further.

Fig. 3 The general block system

Identify applicable sponsor/s here. (sponsors)

The IoT device is developed with RPi 3, module wireless nRF24101, and modem. It is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 The IoT device

The main device of IoT is RPi. RPi manages the interface of the nRF24101 module so that the received wirelessly transmitted peat conduction parameter data can be read and processed in the RPi. and then sent to a web-based information system via a modem using an internet connection.

III. SOFTWARE TOOLS

A. Delivery IoT System

The IoT system uses a special algorithm to work. RPi uses the Raspbian operating system, then installs Thonny, Python IDE for beginners with many features, including a focus on Python and has an interactive environment[14][15], to interface with the system multisensory through GPIO connected to the nRF24101 module. The special algorithm to receive data from the system multisensory is shown in Fig. 5. And then, the data is delivered to system information with PHP, a popular general-purpose scripting language that is especially suited to web development[16].

Fig. 5 Flowchart receiving data from system multisensory

B. System Information

Some of the software used to develop the system in this study uses CodeIgniter (CI) as Framework[17] with Domain

Identify applicable sponsor/s here. (sponsors)

Name is <http://sensorkebakaranlahan.id/>. It is hosted on Cloud Hosting by Rumahweb Indonesia. In general, an outline of how this software works is presented in Fig. 6:

Fig. 6 Software works

To gather data from the sensor, we create the HTTP request catcher, where the sensor through RPi sends data as HTTP URL access with several data parameters. The parameters are automatically inserted into the database on the cloud hosting. Then Web-Based Information is processing text data into charts and graphics that can be seen on <http://sensorkebakaranlahan.id/>.

C. Interface System IoT and System information

In most RPi projects, sending data to a website (or in the website's database) is very crucial. If we want to access the room's sensor and consumption data in our devices through a website in real-time, we must first transfer data from the IoT device to the website. The algorithm to transfer data is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Flowchart interface of system IoT and system information

On the client-side (RPi), we make an HTTP(s) request to the server sending the data as request parameters using URL every two minutes using this code.

```

pload = {'sens1':(sc1),'sens2':(sc2),'sens3':(sc3),'sens4':(sc4),
        'sens5':(sc5),'sens6':(sc6),'sens7':(sc7),'sens8':(sc8),
        'sens9':(sc9),'sens10':(sc10),'sens11':(sc11),
        'sens12':(sc12),'sens13':(sc13),'sens14':(sc14)}
if (int(round(time.time()*1000)) - last_time >= time_interval*60000):
    print(datetime.now().strftime("%H:%M:%S"))
    last_time = int(round(time.time()*1000))

try:
    print('hostname = ' is up!')
    r = requests.Session().post
    |'http://sensorkebakaranlahan.id/sensorbaru/sensor.php',data = pload,timeout = 5)
except:
    traceback.print_exc()
    print(datetime.now().strftime("%H:%M:%S"))
    
```

Fig. 8 Code of interface in client-side

The output URL on Fig. 8 will look like this :

<http://sensorkebakaranlahan.id/sensorbaru/sensor.php?sens1=val1&sens2=val2&sens3=val3&sens4=val4&sens5=val5&sens6=val6&sens7=val7&sens8=val8&sens9=val9&sens10=val10&sens11=val11&sens12=val12&sens13=val13&sens14=val14>

On the server-side, the HTTP server runs a small PHP script sensor.php for each such request which receives the data, makes some plausibility checks (and possibly authentication), and then stores the data into the database. Sensor.php will receive 14 values as sens1, sens2, sens3 until sens14 then convert it to MySQL values for insert into database. This small PHP script is shown in Fig. 9.

```

@sens1 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens1']);
@sens2 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens2']);
@sens3 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens3']);
@sens4 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens4']);
@sens5 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens5']);
@sens6 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens6']);
@sens7 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens7']);
@sens8 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens8']);
@sens9 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens9']);
@sens10 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens10']);
@sens11 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens11']);
@sens12 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens12']);
@sens13 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens13']);
@sens14 = mysql_real_escape_string ($link, $_REQUEST['sens14']);
    
```

Fig. 9 Code of interface in server-side

The web interface on <http://sensorkebakaranlahan.id/> contains some information that shows sensor data like air temperature, land temperature, air humidity, and land humidity in the chart shown in Fig. 10, Fig. 11, Fig. 12, and Fig. 13.

Fig. 10 Graph time series of seven-point soil and heater temperatures

Fig. 11 Graph time series of four-point soil moisture

Fig. 12 Graph time series of air temperature

Fig. 13 Graph time series of air humidity

And the history of data is also shown in Fig. 14 at the bottom of the page.

Fig. 14 Time series of historical data on master-side

IV. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

After IoT device and system information are integrated, the heat conduction parameter of peat soil measurement is ready to be implemented. The process implementing system started with sampling data peat soil. The sampling location is at Banua Hanyar Village, Batumandi District, Balangan Regency, in South Kalimantan - Indonesia. The sampling process and peat soil appearance are presented in Fig. 15. Samples were taken from the surface to a depth of 50 cm and put into a container with the same depth position as the point where the sample was taken.

Fig. 15 Sampling peat soil

Second, the implementation system is the main function process that delivers and receives the data measurement from the multisensory system. This process is shown in Fig. 16. The sample is put in a container in the multisensory system, and then some data is measured. It is sent wirelessly to the IoT device. Then the IoT device receives it and then sends it back to the server to be saved and displayed on a web-based information system.

Fig. 16 Process in situ measurement sample parameters of heat conduction

Third, the sample measurement is displayed on a Web-based information system, and they are presented in Fig. 10, Fig. 11, Fig. 12, Fig. 13., and Fig. 14. To see the data more clearly the condition when the data was measured. Each data point can be marked using the mouse by using a left click on the data point in question, and then a legend of the measurement time and its value will be displayed near the data point, then presented in Fig. 17. Integrating IoT devices and Web-based information systems in real-time and historical data from smart objects have been discussed[18].

The data measurement is further analyzed to determine the heat conduction. The data is plotted again to find a special condition with a small fluctuation temperature for a long time. From this condition temperature of two points, the heat conduction of soil peat was determined. One of the plot graphs is shown in Fig. 18. Based on the graph, it can be seen that the system can run for approximately 8,500 minutes without stopping.

Fig. 17 The data point measurement

Fig. 18 Analyze data in chart

Several events can be a concern in the measurement process when implementing the system. The first is that the internet quota used in the modem cannot be used up because there is no relationship between the IoT device and the server. And the data is never stored in the IoT device nor displayed. So in the future, the bandwidth of the internet to send data need to be managed[19].

The second is to restart the IoT device if the first condition reconnected to the server. So it is necessary to use a warning system to the administrator if both conditions occur. For the future, a data security system must be developed and implemented[20].

The three stages of system implementation have been carried out with good results, especially for the second and the third. So the delivery system parameter of heat conduction peat soil IoT-based as land fire mitigation can be used to measure the conduction parameters of peat soils with varying peat samples.

V. CONCLUSION

The delivery system parameter of heat conduction peat soil based on IoT can work well. The system consists of two main parts: IoT devices and web-based information systems. In its implementation, the system can run for approximately 8,500 minutes without stopping, and data can be displayed and stored on the server properly.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by Lambung Mangkurat University with a PNPB financing scheme on a PDWM number 009.80/UN8.2/PL/2021. We thank Yoga Pambudi for providing wireless communication with the nRF24101 module; we thank Satrio Yudha Prakoso for convenient access to the hosting Web. We thank Wahyu Ansari for the convenient access interface GPIO Raspberry Pi.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. C. Adinugroho, I. N. N. Suryadiputra, B. H. Saharjo, and L. Siboro, *Panduan Pengendalian Hutan dan Lahan Gambut*, I. Bogor: Wetlands International, 2004.
- [2] N. Kettridge and A. Baird, "In situ measurements of the thermal properties of a northern peatland: Implications for peatland temperature models," *J. Geophys. Res.*, vol. 112, no. F2, p. F02019, May 2007, doi: 10.1029/2006JF000655.
- [3] A. A. Harnawan, N. S. Mulyana, I. Ridwan, and M. I. Mazdadi, "Rancang bangun sistem multisensor pengukur kelembaban tanah gambut berdasar variasi kedalaman sebagai upaya mitigasi kebakaran lahan," in *Seminar Nasional Lingkungan Lahan Basah*, 2021, vol. 6, no. 2.
- [4] M. Schmidt, *Raspberry Pi, A quick-start guide*. The Pragmatic Programmers, LLC., 2012.
- [5] T. R. P. Foundation, "Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+." <https://www.raspberrypi.com/products/raspberry-pi-3-model-b-plus/> (accessed Dec. 11, 2021).
- [6] V. V, V. S. R. R, A. K. P, and P. kumar S, "Internet of Things(IoT) Based Multilevel Drunken Driving Detection and Prevention System Using Raspberry Pi 3," *CoRR*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 131–137, 2020, doi: 10.31227/osf.io/byc/jn.
- [7] M. E. E. Ezema, Francis .A. Okoye, Anthony .O. Okwori, and Christopher . C., "The Sharp Increase in Unmasking of Obtrusion into Internet of Things (IoT) IPV6 and IPV6 Low – power Wireless Personal Area Network (6LoWPAN), a Lead Way to Secure Internet of Things Services," *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Inf. Secur.*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 161–167, 2018.
- [8] F. Y. Q. Ontowirjo, V. C. Poekoel, P. D. K. Manembu, and R. F. Robot, "Implementasi Internet of Things Pada Sistem Monitoring Suhu dan Kelembaban Pada Ruang Pengerang Berbasis Web," *J. Tek. Elektro dan Komput.*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 331–338, 2018, doi: 10.35793/jtek.7.3.2018.23638.
- [9] P. Pukkasenung, "Internet of Things (IoT): A Basic Concept and Analysis Security Issues," vol. 18, no. 11, pp. 1–10, 2020.
- [10] M. ichsan Kamil, R. Ardianto, and ig prasetya dwi Wibawa, "Prototipe Sistem Monitoring Dan Kontrol Lampu Rumah Berbasis Iot (Internet of Things)," *e-Proceeding Eng.*, vol. 6, no. 2, p. 2974, 2019.
- [11] I. Soesanti, "Design and development of Web-Based Information System for The Batik Industry," *IPTEK J. Proc. Ser.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 2354–6026, Jul. 2015, doi: 10.12962/j23546026.y2014i1.388.
- [12] K.-C. Kao, W.-H. Chieng, and S.-L. Jeng, "Design and development of an IoT-based web application for an intelligent remote SCADA system," *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 323, p. 012025, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1088/1757-899X/323/1/012025.
- [13] A. Oluwatofunmi, I. S., and I. A., "Web-based Information System (WBIS) Framework: Facilitating Interoperability within Business Ventures," *Int. J. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 180, no. 26, pp. 7–12, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.5120/ijca2018916595.
- [14] Cybernetica, "Thonny," 2018. <https://thonny.org/> (accessed Dec. 18, 2021).
- [15] S. HYMEL, "Python Programming Tutorial: Getting Started with the Raspberry Pi," [Online]. Available: [https://learn.sparkfun.com/tutorials/python-programming-tutorial-getting-started-with-the-raspberry-pi/hello-world#:~:text=Start Thonny by clicking on,in the bottom interpreter pane.](https://learn.sparkfun.com/tutorials/python-programming-tutorial-getting-started-with-the-raspberry-pi/hello-world#:~:text=Start%20Thonny%20by%20clicking%20on,in%20the%20bottom%20interpreter%20pane.)
- [16] T. P. Group, "PHP." <https://www.php.net/> (accessed Dec. 18, 2021).
- [17] EllisLab, "CodeIgniter User Guide," 2019. <https://www.codeigniter.com/userguide3/index.html> (accessed Oct. 21, 2020).
- [18] A. Orestis, A. Dimitrios, and C. Ioannis, "Towards integrating IoT devices with the Web," in *Proceedings of 2012 IEEE 17th International Conference on Emerging Technologies & Factory Automation (ETFA 2012)*, Sep. 2012, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/ETFA.2012.6489729.
- [19] I. P. Sudharma Yoga, G. Sukadarmika, and . L., "Dynamic Bandwidth Allocation for Internet of Things System Using Elastic Wireless Local Area Network," *J. Rekayasa Elektr.*, vol. 17, no. 3, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.17529/jre.v17i3.21087.
- [20] C.-Y. Chen, M. Hasan, and S. Mohan, "Securing Real-Time Internet-of-Things," *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 12, p. 4356, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.3390/s18124356.

...

Analyze Cyber Attacks in Cloud Cryptography and Short Comings in Blockchain Cryptocurrency

Ravikumar Ch¹, Dr. Isha Batra² and Dr Arun Malik³

¹ Computer Science and Engineering, Lovely Professional University, Punjab, India.

² Computer Science and Engineering, Lovely Professional University, Punjab, India.

³ Computer Science and Engineering, Lovely Professional University, Punjab, India.

E-mail: chrk5814@gmail.com, isha.17451@lpu.co.in, arun.17442@lpu.co.in

Abstract: Technological improvements have happened in companies digitalizing various elements of their actions. The threat landscape of cyber-attacks is rapidly changing. The possible consequence of such attacks is unknown because there is a lack of useful metrics, tools and frameworks to explain and evaluate the harm industries suffer from cyber-attacks. Cyber-attacks are not new to IoT, but as IoT will be strongly mixed in our days and communities, it is becoming important to step up and take cyber security severely. Hence, there is a real need to secure IoT, resulting in a need to comprehensively recognize the warnings and attacks on IoT infrastructure. The paper's main objective is to investigate the impact of the cyber-attacks in the common cyber framework and analyze the blockchain crypto-currency architecture to evaluate the weaknesses and safety representation. The security of cryptocurrency heavily relies on the incentive-compatible Proof of Authority (PoA) based on distributed consensus protocol; a consensus algorithm type based on the reputation of trusted parties in a blockchain network. This paper introduces Proof of Authority (PoA) based distributed consensus protocol and a novel blockchain-based decentralized federation model that embodies quality verification for cloud providers who lease computing resources from each other.

Keywords: Blockchain security, Cryptocurrency, Internet of Things, Cloud service, Proof of Authority.

I. INTRODUCTION

The recent fast growth of the Internet of Things (IoT)[1] and its capacity to perform certain services have performed it the fastest developing technology, significantly affecting social lifestyles and business conditions. The Internet of Things has slowly infiltrated all components of human life today, including training, healthcare, and businesses, including collecting sensitive data about people and businesses, financial records transactions, product growth, and marketing. The extensive generation of associated devices within the Internet of Things has commenced high requirements for robust protection in response to the growing requirement for tens of millions or possibly billions of associated devices and offerings internationally [2]. The number of threats is increasing daily, and the attacks are increasing in scope and complexity. The number of potential attackers and the growing network size are not the most practical. Still, the equipment available to potential attackers has also become more advanced, efficient, and powerful [3]. Therefore, for the Internet of Things to achieve its full potential, it needs to be secure against threats and vulnerabilities. Security has been described as a way to protect an item from physical harm, unauthorized entry, theft, or loss, with the help of maintaining excessive confidentiality and integrity of facts about the item and establishing facts about that item. Any time. It is necessary.

Today, cryptocurrency has grown a buzzword in both business and academia. As one of the common strong cryptocurrencies, Bitcoin has enjoyed significant compliance with its capital market that produced \$10 billion in 2016 [4]. With a specially produced form of data storage, transactions on the Bitcoin network may wish to proceed without any service. The primary generation to make Bitcoin is the blockchain, first introduced in 2008 and executed in 2009 [5]. Blockchain can appear as a public record, and all authorized transactions are kept in the block list. This category is growing as new blocks are continually being attached to it. Asymmetric encryption and shared consensus algorithms have been implemented for user security and public ledger compatibility. The blockchain age frequently has the essential features of decentralization, resolution, anonymity, and audibility. With these trends, blockchain can significantly buy fees and improve efficiency.

Blockchain can be applied for various financial contributions, including virtual property, online transfers, and shipping. Furthermore, it can also be achieved in other areas, including smart contracts [6], public contributions [7], and the Internet of Things (IoT).

The transaction can be accomplished using automated miners for smart contracts as soon as the transaction is performed on the blockchain. Although blockchain technology can improve targeted Internet systems globally, it allows various challenging technical conditions. First of all, scalability is a huge challenge. The bitcoin block is now restricted to at least one megabyte, while the block is mined roughly every ten minutes. Thus, the Bitcoin network is limited to seven transaction fees based on the second and cannot handle frequent excessive trading. However, larger blocks indicate a larger storage area and slower spread within the network. This will begin to centralise, as fewer users will like to operate one of these huge blocks. Hence, trade-offs between block length

and security were a challenging task. Second, it has been described that miner may want to create sales above their fair share through a self-centred mining method. Miners cover their mined blocks to get more sales within the destination. In this way, the branches must be regularly closed, which makes blockchain development difficult. Therefore, should recommend some answers to solve this problem.

BLOCKCHAIN ARCHITECTURE

Fig.1 An example of Blockchain which consists of a continuous sequence of blocks.

Fig.2 Block structure

Blockchain is a chain of blocks that includes a full list of transaction facts like a common public ledger. Figure 1 shows an example of a blockchain. With the past block's hash in the block header, the block includes only one highlight block. It is worth remarking that hashes of uncle blocks (children of the block ancestors) would also be stored on the ethereum Blockchain. The first blockchain block is known as the configuration block that does not include a select block. Then we describe the inside of the blockchain in detail.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows

- We recommend a Proof of Authority (PoA) based distributed consensus protocol to present safety.
- We recommended a Blockchain-based distributed cloud storage design to produce more reliable and secure cloud storage assistance for companies or individual users.
- We customize a genetic algorithm to determine the file block replica situation problem among various users and data centres in the distributed cloud storage conditions.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Cloud storage is a network generation method for sharing assets with associated IT skills, critical for business or personal users. In particular, traditional cloud storage protection strategies include knowledge about log encryption, access management, and many more. Recently, Software-Defined Storage (SDS) integrated several cloud storage services that are dispensed to address the issue that a separate cloud cannot meet user needs.

Nguyen et al. [2020] Blockchain technology has become what is moving the world through a hurricane, and Blockchain emerged as a disruptive technology for the subsequent generation of various commercial software. In this paper, a new model for integrating Blockchain and Cloud of Things, known as BCoT, is widely emerging as a promising enabler for various public service situations. This article provided an up-to-date overview of BCoT integration to give regular readers an overview of BCoT in many aspects: experience, motivation, and embedded architecture. They also provided an in-depth survey of BCoT packages across different use case areas: smart healthcare, smart cities, smart transportation, and smart industry.

WissamZaki et al. [2020] Cloud computing has become a completely useful generation in our daily existence; this computing uses the internet to provide software and transmit and keep facts. It becomes necessary to provide an environment that protects applications and records inside this cloud; networks should be protocols. That used powerful algorithms to protect it. This article mentioned some of them, and compared to others, factual security and encryption became among the most important discoveries. Although improved in the days of wine completely separately, this fact confirmed a close connection between them.

Mohamed MounirMoussa et al.[2020] It was looked at the implementation and organization techniques associated with dew computing, where processing was added even towards the user compared to the different IoT computing paradigms. This document aims to assess IoT threats and the use of deep field technology to counter cyber anomalies and then validate them by analyzing their metrics. They evaluated the state of the variable stats between the cloud and the relevant vehicle-embedded dew stop devices. They used a modified version of Stacked Autoencoder that improved detection accuracy for specific attacks, using school information loss as a threshold.

Aditi Patel et al. [2020] An emerging era has been suggested offering computer services along with online business software and online data storage. Deployed cloud enables an unauthorized operating environment where business expenses are reduced, data is provided, real security, etc. As many companies embrace cloud computing, attackers exploit the cloud to achieve unauthorized manipulation of valuable records stored in it. The evolution from traditional computing to the cloud has brought many security challenges for every customer and vendor. Online cloud service providers have made various offers using various technologies, which generate distinct security threats.

Chengpeng Xia et al. [2018] An incentive is provided to encourage nearby servers to serve cellular clients for the mobile blockchain software. They formulated the problem as a useful and useful resource allocation problem, then proposed a public sale of three levels of beneficial implementation of resource allocation tailored to the cellular blockchain, and brought in a specific purchasing mechanism to encourage customers smartphones. It also showed that his auction scheme turned out to be honest, personal sanity and athletic performance. The proposed scheme was compared with the mechanisms of TACD and HAF, and the simulation results showed that appropriate social status with the help of its scheme was better than the mechanisms of TACD and HAF.

Aydogan et al. [2017] Mobile attack techniques can be categorized as primarily software-based attacks and frequency-based attacks. Utility-based assaults have been radically reviewed in the literature. However, frequency-based attacks on mobile phones have not been thoroughly tested. This panel experimentally attacks an Android cell phone using a radio circuit based primarily on a simple application. They have developed a "Mobile Hack Master Builder" to control your Android smartphone remotely. SMS information and photos may be received within the cell phone using this device. On the contrary, after going out for a walk with a cellular smartphone application, it can control the virtual camera of the mobile phones to take pictures and download them to the chassis of our laptop.

Jiaying et al. [2017] suggested Blockchain-based security architecture for distributed cloud storage. With the improvement of the ICT industry, the number of events produced has grown exponentially, which has increased the demand for storage capacity. Due to the limited garage capacity of customer terminals, more and more software prefers to upload statistics to cloud platforms. However, it is known that you cannot forget about security in current cloud garage architectures. Driven by the growing popularity of the emerging blockchain age, they have proposed Blockchain-based security architecture for out-of-pocket cloud storage.

Garay et al. [2017] presented the first formal analysis of the functionality of (re)calculating the Bitcoin target in a crypto site, that is, against all potential adversaries who seek to subvert the properties of the protocol. They extend the q-delimited synchronous model of the Bitcoin Pillar Protocol (Eurocrypt 2015), which rolls out the simple houses of Bitcoin's underlying Blockchain data structure and demonstrates how a robust public transaction ledger can be built at its peak to environments that can enter or suspend matches each round.

III. TYPES OF CYBER ATTACKS IN CLOUD CRYPTOGRAPHY

Cyber attacks in cloud computing tend to generate most of the vulnerabilities found in the cloud's core structural additions. These weaknesses and vulnerabilities have attracted hobbies from various attack profiles ranging from children of scripts to APT. Several cyberattacks are seen in many cloud environments that exploit vulnerabilities in cloud extensions or misconfigurations based on the design sample. All of these attacks violate at least one of the principles of the CIA's Trinity. Most attacks are directed at cloud components within a particular layer or across different layers. Therefore, the attacks considered from now on represent both multi-

stage attacks within a layer and between layers. Bye, they use some form of pivot nodes to boost the attack. The intent of a specific attack is different from the alternative.

There are various cyber-attacks involved in cloud cryptography listed below

1. Hyperjacking
2. Honest but Curious Server
3. Link Aggregation Attack (DoS type attack)
4. Side Channel Attack
5. VM Migration Attack:
6. VM Escape Attack
7. MITC Attack
8. XML - HTTP DOS

IV. VARIOUS SHORTCOMINGS IN CRYPTOCURRENCY

There are a few shortcomings related to crypto-currency are given below

a) Scalability

Probably the biggest issues with cryptocurrencies are the volume issues that can arise. While the wide variety and adoption of virtual currencies are unexpectedly increasing, it is dwarfed by the number of transactions that cost so much, VISA, that comes in every day. Moreover, transaction rate is another important metric that cryptocurrencies cannot compete with in the same arena as players like VISA and Mastercard until the infrastructure that provides this technology is greatly expanded.

b) Cyber security issues

As a virtual technology, cryptocurrencies can be a problem for cybersecurity breaches and can fall into the hands of hackers. We've already seen evidence of this, with some ICOs hacked and costing buyers tens of millions of dollars this summer alone (this kind of raid alone resulted in a \$473 million loss). Mitigating this may require keeping the security infrastructure uninterrupted. Still, we are already seeing many players tackle this without delay and use more robust cyber security features beyond those used in the traditional banking industries.

c) Price volatility and lack of inherent value

Price volatility, linked to an inherent lack of value, is a primary annoyance and one of the details that Buffett has primarily been referring to in the past few weeks while describing the cryptocurrency environment as a bubble. However, it is a fundamental situation that can be overcome by linking the price of a foreign cryptocurrency directly to tangible and intangible properties (as we have seen some new players do with diamonds or energy derivatives). High adoption should enhance customer confidence and reduce this volatility.

d) High volatility and potential for large losses

The annualized monthly percentage volatility of trading within the bitcoin price in US dollars has been set at 90% measured over the past five years. This compares to the annual volatility of monthly percentage changes in the S&P 500 and gold rate at 15.3% and 13.4%, respectively. To give some insight into what this volatility might suggest to an investor, consider the range of returns: the maximum monthly returns for bitcoin in the 60 months to the end of December 2020 have changed to 76.1% and the minimum -37.6%. The timing of investing in bitcoin or other cryptocurrencies can have a significant impact on completed returns.

e) Endless potential supply

While it is very true that sooner or later, the variety of bitcoins produced will be set at 21 million different cryptocurrencies and also have a limited supply built into their protocols, there is currently nothing stopping a wide range of new cryptocurrencies from developing. Therefore, cryptocurrency delivery is likely to be unlimited. It is also worth noting that several important banks are exploring the opportunity to launch their cryptocurrency, which could weaken private issuance.

f) Poor store of value and limited acceptance

While Bitcoin and a few different cryptocurrencies are currently enshrined via a growing variety of fee structures, the number of places you can exchange cryptocurrencies for actual items or services is still very limited. For similar reasons, the inherent volatility of cryptocurrencies makes them a terrible store of value.

When converted into a base currency for an individual, the cost of cryptocurrencies will vary significantly, even during the day.

g) Unregulated and unbacked

Cryptocurrency is a private sector build with no approved supervision or regulation. This approach is that cryptocurrencies are widely open to being exploited by criminals to deceive unsuspecting investors. A 2019 educational study found that 25% of bitcoin customers are concerned about illegal interests, and 46% of bitcoin transactions are related to illegal activities.

V. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Proof of Authority (PoA) consensus algorithm

Proof of Authority (PoA) is a type of consensus algorithm primarily based on the popularity of affiliate parties in a blockchain network. It is a completely new consensus algorithm organization that offers high performance and fault tolerance. In PoA, the advantages of creating new blocks are given to nodes that have proven their authority. A node must provide pre-authentication to gain this authority and sufficient authentication to create new blocks.

PoA is a set of rules for consensus within the blockchain that proposes a robust and effective answer to the privacy of facts in blockchain networks. The PoA algorithm uses the value of identities to enforce security by personally validating nodes set to be trusted. The Proof of Authority set of rules relies on various block validators, making it a remarkably scalable device. Blocks and transactions are viewed with the help of pre-approved peers who act as device admins. The proof of authority model allows organizations to maintain their privacy while taking advantage of blockchain technology. Microsoft Azure is an instance in which PoA is implemented. The Azure platform offers answers to non-public blockchain networks without the local currency “fuel” of ether, as there is no need for mining. Smart contracts are pieces of software or code on the blockchain managed by a P2P network of computer systems. Smart contracts are human rights monitoring teams that provide a framework for coordinating and enforcing agreements between individuals in a community without the need for traditional criminal contracts. They can be used to implement simple agreements between parties, company bylaws, or to create tokens. In the context of a blockchain, smart contracts are a public, private boundary built into the blockchain, which can receive or execute transactions as multiple parameters (transactions can be rejected or require unique arguments for a function), which can act as an immutable element. The purpose of smart contracts is to act like a “computerized transaction protocol that implements the agreement's provisions”.

The PoA protocol is that there is a decentralized network of cryptocurrencies whose security mainly depends on a combination of Proof of Work and Proof of Stake. In terms of fashion, fully Proof of Work-based protocols provide decision-making power to entities that perform computational responsibilities, even as fully Proof-of-stake-based protocols provide decision-making power to entities that maintain participation in the device.

PoA algorithms are based on a set of N trusted nodes called governance. Each authority is diagnosed with the help of unique identification, and most of them are considered to be honest, particularly at least $N = 2 + 1$. Authorities come to a consensus to order outgoing transactions through customers. The consensus on activity program algorithms is based on the mining rotation scheme, a widely used approach to equitably allocating responsibility for the emergence of blocks between authorities. The time is divided into steps, each of which has an expert chosen to be the mining leader.

It is an eco-friendly mechanism for personal blockchains and was developed with the help of Ethereum co-founder and former CTO Gavin Wood in 2017. The PoA consensus algorithm is primarily based on the cost of identities within the community and various devices; Auditors are not betting on assets but their identities and reputation. Therefore, PoA Blockchain networks are protected by validation nodes that can be arbitrarily selected as honest events.

The Proof of Authority model runs on a powerful and fast set of block validation tools, making it an easily scalable blockchain device because transactions are verified with the help of already accepted community contributors. The PoA consensus rule set can be used in packets that include delivery chains or exchange networks because the actual identities of the nodes are considered trusted.

PoA consensus algorithm

Step 1: Each miner uses her hash power to try to generate an empty block header.

Step 2: When a miner succeeds in generating an empty block header, meaning that the hash of her block header data is smaller than the current difficulty target.

Step 3: All the network nodes regard the hash of this block header as data that deterministically derives N pseudorandom stakeholders.

Step 4: Every stakeholder who is online checks whether the empty block header that the miner broadcasted is valid, meaning that it contains the hash of the previous block and meets the current difficulty.

Step 5: The Nth stakeholder broadcasts the wrapped block to the network, and when the other nodes see that this wrapped block is valid according to the above, they consider it a legitimate extension of the blockchain.

Step 6: The fees from the transactions that the Nth stakeholder collected are shared between the miner and the N lucky stakeholders.

PoA mechanism makes it possible to defend against this attack because network nodes are pre-authenticated, block generation rights can be granted only to nodes that can withstand DoS attacks.

Use of Cryptography in Blockchain

Blockchain uses types of encryption algorithms, asymmetric key algorithms, and hash functions. The hash functions are used to provide the ability to view one blockchain per player, and Blockchains generally use the SHA-256 hash rule set as the hash function.

Basic architecture for Cryptocurrency:

Fig.3 Basic architecture for cryptocurrency

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the experimental are conducted using python 3.7 programming language and the KDD dataset used with 5 rows and 42 columns to perform the analysis of the previous algorithm of RNN (recurrent neural network).

```

Python 3.7.3 (64-bit)
Python 3.7.3 (v3.7.3:ef4ec6d12, Mar 25 2019, 22:22:05) [MSC v.1916 64 bit (AMD64)] on win32
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license()" for more information.
>>> import numpy as np
>>> import pandas as pd
>>> import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
>>> import time
>>> import datetime
>>>
>>> df = pd.read_csv('C:/Users/sravan/Desktop/2021/satya/block chain/obj1/dataset.csv')
>>> df.head()
   0  tcp  private  REJ    0.1    0.2  0.3  0.4  ...  0.061  0.003  0.004  0.005  0.006  1.002  1.003  anomaly
1  0  tcp  private  REJ    0    0  0  0  ...  0.06  0.00  0.00  0.00  0.00  0.0  1.00  1.00  anomaly
2  2  tcp  ftp_data  SF  12983  0  0  0  ...  0.04  0.61  0.02  0.00  0.0  0.00  0.00  normal
3  0  icmp  eco_i    SF    20    0  0  0  ...  0.00  1.00  0.28  0.00  0.0  0.00  0.00  anomaly
4  1  tcp  telnet   RSTO    0    15  0  0  ...  0.17  0.03  0.02  0.00  0.0  0.83  0.71  anomaly
5  0  tcp  http     SF   267  14515  0  0  ...  0.00  0.01  0.03  0.01  0.0  0.00  0.00  normal

[5 rows x 42 columns]
>>>
    
```

Fig.4 Identifying the cyber attacks on block chain intrusion for previous RNN method

Fig.4 indicates the data set with the features for identifying the cyber-attacks on block chain intrusion.

```
Python 3.7 (64-bit)
dst_host_same_srv_rate dst_host_diff_srv_rate \
0 0.06 0.00
1 0.04 0.61
2 0.00 1.00
3 0.17 0.83
4 0.00 0.01

dst_host_same_src_port_rate dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate \
0 0.00 0.00
1 0.02 0.00
2 0.25 0.00
3 0.02 0.00
4 0.03 0.01

dst_host_serror_rate dst_host_srv_serror_rate dst_host_rerror_rate \
0 0.0 1.00 1.00
1 0.0 0.00 0.00
2 0.0 0.00 0.00
3 0.0 0.83 0.71
4 0.0 0.00 0.00

class
0 anomaly
1 normal
2 anomaly
3 anomaly
4 normal
>>>
```

Fig.5: working with the class labels from the data

```
Python 3.7 (64-bit)
dst_host_same_src_port_rate dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate \
0 0.00 0.00
1 0.02 0.00
2 0.25 0.00
3 0.02 0.00
4 0.03 0.01

dst_host_serror_rate dst_host_srv_serror_rate dst_host_rerror_rate \
0 0.0 1.00 1.00
1 0.0 0.00 0.00
2 0.0 0.00 0.00
3 0.0 0.83 0.71
4 0.0 0.00 0.00

class
0 anomaly
1 normal
2 anomaly
3 anomaly
4 normal
>>> df_new = df
>>> from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
>>> labelencoder = LabelEncoder()
>>> df_new['protocol_type'] = labelencoder.fit_transform(df_new['protocol_type'])
>>> df_new['service'] = labelencoder.fit_transform(df_new['service'])
>>> df_new['flag'] = labelencoder.fit_transform(df_new['flag'])
>>> df_new['class'] = labelencoder.fit_transform(df_new['class'])
>>>
```

Fig.6 label encoder which works on encoding the classified label for the process of intrusion

Fig.7 Support features for the intrusion of previous method

```
Python 3.7 (64-bit)
NameError: name 'y_pred' is not defined
>>> from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, confusion_matrix
>>> print(classification_report(y_test, predictions))
precision recall f1-score support
0 0.74 1.00 0.85 2532
1 0.99 0.55 0.71 1977
accuracy 0.87 0.77 0.80 4509
macro avg 0.85 0.80 0.79 4509
weighted avg 0.85 0.80 0.79 4509
>>>
>>>
>>>
>>>
>>>
>>>
>>>
>>>
>>>
```

Fig.8 Accuracy of the model with the prediction and rate

0	0.74	1.00	0.85	2532
1	0.99	0.55	0.71	1977
accuracy			0.80	4509
macro avg	0.87	0.77	0.78	4509
weighted avg	0.85	0.80	0.79	4509

Fig.9 Accuracy for previous method

VII.CONCLUSION

Cloud computing is seen as the future of computing and storage technology, and the work carried out with blockchain technology in the next era is studied in this paper. Considering these security issues, we analyzed the existing deep learning-based RNN model with experimental steps that increased the integrity of the statistics. The emergence of connected devices and computing is the need for cloud computing in its current form. We can say that the previous method achieved 80% accuracy with prediction and rate by analyzing the experiment. Further, enhance the approach to building a Blockchain-based secure and decentralized access control network on a Cloud platform.

VIII.REFERENCES

1. L. Atzori, A. Iera, and G. Morabito, "The internet of things: A survey," *Computer networks*, vol. 54, no. 15, pp. 2787–2805, 2010.
2. J. S. Kumar and D. R. Patel, "A survey on internet of things: Security and privacy issues," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 90, no. 11, pp. 20–26, March 2014, published by Foundation of Computer Science, New York, USA.
3. B. Schneier, *Secrets and lies: digital security in a networked world*. John Wiley & Sons, 2011.
4. "State of blockchain q1 2016: Blockchain funding overtakes bitcoin," 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://www.coindesk.com/state-of-blockchain-q1-2016/>
5. S. Nakamoto, "Bitcoin: A peer-to-peer electronic cash system," 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf>.
6. Kosba, A. Miller, E. Shi, Z. Wen, and C. Papamanthou, "Hawk: The blockchain model of cryptography and privacy-preserving smart contracts," in *Proceedings of IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, San Jose, CA, USA, 2016, pp. 839–858.
7. W. Akins, J. L. Chapman, and J. M. Gordon, "A whole new world: Income tax considerations of the bitcoin economy," 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2394738>
8. Nguyen, Pubudu N. Pathirana, Ming Ding, Aruna Seneviratne, "Integration of Blockchain and Cloud of Things: Architecture Applications and Challenges", *Communications Surveys & Tutorials IEEE*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 2521-2549, 2020.
9. Chengpeng Xia, Hui Chen, Xuelian Liu, Jigang Wu, Long Chen, "ETRA: Efficient Three-Stage Resource Allocation Auction for Mobile Blockchain in Edge Computing", *Parallel and Distributed Systems (ICPADS) 2018 IEEE 24th International Conference on*, pp. 701-705, 2018
10. Jiaying Li; Zhusong Liu; Long Chen; Pinghua Chen, 2017, "Blockchain-Based Security Architecture for Distributed Cloud Storage", pp.408-411.
11. J. Garay, A. Kiayias, and N. Leonardos, "The bitcoin backbone protocol with chains of variable difficulty," in *Advances in Cryptology – CRYPTO 2017: 37th Annual International Cryptology Conference*, Santa Barbara, CA, USA. Springer International Publishing, 2017, pp. 291–323.
12. Wissam Zaki Mizyad Al-Humadi, "CRYPTOGRAPHY IN CLOUD COMPUTING FOR DATA SECURITY AND NETWORK SECURITY", pp. 6965-6973.
13. N., Aydogan, A.F. and Varol, A., 2017, April. Cyber attacks targeting Android cellphones. In *2017 5th International Symposium on Digital Forensic and Security (ISDFS)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE
14. Mohamed Mounir Moussa, Lubna Alazzawi, 2020, "Cyber Attacks Detection based on Deep Learning for Cloud-Dew Computing in Automotive IoT Applications", IEEE, DOI: 10.1109/SmartCloud49737.2020.00019.
15. Aditi Patel, Nisarg Shah, Dipak Ramoliya, 2020, "A detailed review of Cloud Security: Issues, Threats & Attacks", IEEE, DOI: 10.1109/ICECA49313.2020.9297572.

IJCSIS REVIEWERS' LIST

Assist Prof (Dr.) M. Emre Celebi, Louisiana State University in Shreveport, USA
Dr. Lam Hong Lee, Universiti Tunku Abdul Rahman, Malaysia
Dr. Shimon K. Modi, Director of Research BSPA Labs, Purdue University, USA
Dr. Jianguo Ding, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Norway
Assoc. Prof. N. Jaisankar, VIT University, Vellore, Tamilnadu, India
Dr. Amogh Kavimandan, The Mathworks Inc., USA
Dr. Ramasamy Mariappan, Vinayaka Missions University, India
Dr. Yong Li, School of Electronic and Information Engineering, Beijing Jiaotong University, P.R. China
Assist. Prof. Sugam Sharma, NIET, India / Iowa State University, USA
Dr. Jorge A. Ruiz-Vanoye, Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Morelos, Mexico
Dr. Neeraj Kumar, SMVD University, Katra (J&K), India
Dr Genge Bela, "Petru Maior" University of Targu Mures, Romania
Dr. Junjie Peng, Shanghai University, P. R. China
Dr. Ilhem LENGILIZ, HANA Group - CRISTAL Laboratory, Tunisia
Prof. Dr. Durgesh Kumar Mishra, Acropolis Institute of Technology and Research, Indore, MP, India
Dr. Jorge L. Hernández-Ardieta, University Carlos III of Madrid, Spain
Prof. Dr.C.Suresh Gnana Dhas, Anna University, India
Dr Li Fang, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore
Prof. Pijush Biswas, RCC Institute of Information Technology, India
Dr. Siddhivinayak Kulkarni, University of Ballarat, Ballarat, Victoria, Australia
Dr. A. Arul Lawrence, Royal College of Engineering & Technology, India
Dr. Wongyos Keardsri, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand
Dr. Somesh Kumar Dewangan, CSVTU Bhilai (C.G.)/ Dimat Raipur, India
Dr. Hayder N. Jasem, University Putra Malaysia, Malaysia
Dr. A.V.Senthil Kumar, C. M. S. College of Science and Commerce, India
Dr. R. S. Karthik, C. M. S. College of Science and Commerce, India
Dr. P. Vasant, University Technology Petronas, Malaysia
Dr. Wong Kok Seng, Soongsil University, Seoul, South Korea
Dr. Praveen Ranjan Srivastava, BITS PILANI, India
Dr. Kong Sang Kelvin, Leong, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong
Dr. Mohd Nazri Ismail, Universiti Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
Dr. Rami J. Matarneh, Al-isra Private University, Amman, Jordan
Dr Ojesanmi Olusegun Ayodeji, Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo, Nigeria
Dr. Riktish Srivastava, Skyline University, UAE
Dr. Oras F. Baker, UCSI University - Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
Dr. Ahmed S. Ghiduk, Faculty of Science, Beni-Suef University, Egypt
and Department of Computer science, Taif University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Tirthankar Gayen, IIT Kharagpur, India
Dr. Huei-Ru Tseng, National Chiao Tung University, Taiwan
Prof. Ning Xu, Wuhan University of Technology, China
Dr Mohammed Salem Binwahlan, Hadhramout University of Science and Technology, Yemen
& Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Malaysia.
Dr. Aruna Ranganath, Bhoj Reddy Engineering College for Women, India
Dr. Hafeezullah Amin, Institute of Information Technology, KUST, Kohat, Pakistan

Prof. Syed S. Rizvi, University of Bridgeport, USA
Dr. Shahbaz Pervez Chattha, University of Engineering and Technology Taxila, Pakistan
Dr. Shishir Kumar, Jaypee University of Information Technology, Wakanaghat (HP), India
Dr. Shahid Mumtaz, Portugal Telecommunication, Instituto de Telecomunicações (IT) , Aveiro, Portugal
Dr. Rajesh K Shukla, Corporate Institute of Science & Technology Bhopal M P
Dr. Poonam Garg, Institute of Management Technology, India
Dr. S. Mehta, Inha University, Korea
Dr. Dilip Kumar S.M, Bangalore University, Bangalore
Prof. Malik Sikander Hayat Khiyal, Fatima Jinnah Women University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan
Dr. Virendra Gomase , Department of Bioinformatics, Padmashree Dr. D.Y. Patil University
Dr. Irraivan Elamvazuthi, University Technology PETRONAS, Malaysia
Dr. Saqib Saeed, University of Siegen, Germany
Dr. Pavan Kumar Gorakavi, IPMA-USA [YC]
Dr. Ahmed Nabih Zaki Rashed, Menoufia University, Egypt
Prof. Shishir K. Shandilya, Rukmani Devi Institute of Science & Technology, India
Dr. J. Komala Lakshmi, SNR Sons College, Computer Science, India
Dr. Muhammad Sohail, KUST, Pakistan
Dr. Manjaiah D.H, Mangalore University, India
Dr. S Santhosh Baboo, D.G.Vaishnav College, Chennai, India
Prof. Dr. Mokhtar Beldjehem, Sainte-Anne University, Halifax, NS, Canada
Dr. Deepak Laxmi Narasimha, University of Malaya, Malaysia
Prof. Dr. Arunkumar Thangavelu, Vellore Institute Of Technology, India
Dr. M. Azath, Anna University, India
Dr. Md. Rabiul Islam, Rajshahi University of Engineering & Technology (RUET), Bangladesh
Dr. Aos Alaa Zaidan Ansaef, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Dr Suresh Jain, Devi Ahilya University, Indore (MP) India,
Dr. Mohammed M. Kadhum, Universiti Utara Malaysia
Dr. Hanumanthappa. J. University of Mysore, India
Dr. Syed Ishtiaque Ahmed, Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (BUET)
Dr Akinola Solomon Olalekan, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria
Dr. Santosh K. Pandey, The Institute of Chartered Accountants of India
Dr. P. Vasant, Power Control Optimization, Malaysia
Dr. Petr Ivankov, Automatika - S, Russian Federation
Dr. Utkarsh Seetha, Data Infosys Limited, India
Mrs. Priti Maheshwary, Maulana Azad National Institute of Technology, Bhopal
Dr. (Mrs) Padmavathi Ganapathi, Avinashilingam University for Women, Coimbatore
Assist. Prof. A. Neela madheswari, Anna university, India
Prof. Ganesan Ramachandra Rao, PSG College of Arts and Science, India
Mr. Kamanashis Biswas, Daffodil International University, Bangladesh
Dr. Atul Gonsai, Saurashtra University, Gujarat, India
Mr. Angkoon Phinyomark, Prince of Songkla University, Thailand
Mrs. G. Nalini Priya, Anna University, Chennai
Dr. P. Subashini, Avinashilingam University for Women, India
Assoc. Prof. Vijay Kumar Chakka, Dhirubhai Ambani IICT, Gandhinagar ,Gujarat
Mr Jitendra Agrawal, : Rajiv Gandhi Proudlyogiki Vishwavidyalaya, Bhopal
Mr. Vishal Goyal, Department of Computer Science, Punjabi University, India
Dr. R. Baskaran, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Anna University, Chennai

Assist. Prof, Kanwalvir Singh Dhindsa, B.B.S.B.Engg.College, Fatehgarh Sahib (Punjab), India
Dr. Jamal Ahmad Dargham, School of Engineering and Information Technology, Universiti Malaysia Sabah
Mr. Nitin Bhatia, DAV College, India
Dr. Dhavachelvan Ponnurangam, Pondicherry Central University, India
Dr. Mohd Faizal Abdollah, University of Technical Malaysia, Malaysia
Assist. Prof. Sonal Chawla, Panjab University, India
Dr. Abdul Wahid, AKG Engg. College, Ghaziabad, India
Mr. Arash Habibi Lashkari, University of Malaya (UM), Malaysia
Mr. Md. Rajibul Islam, Ibnu Sina Institute, University Technology Malaysia
Professor Dr. Sabu M. Thampi, .B.S Institute of Technology for Women, Kerala University, India
Mr. Noor Muhammed Nayeem, Université Lumière Lyon 2, 69007 Lyon, France
Dr. Himanshu Aggarwal, Department of Computer Engineering, Punjabi University, India
Prof R. Naidoo, Dept of Mathematics/Center for Advanced Computer Modelling, Durban University of Technology,
Durban, South Africa
Prof. Mydhili K Nair, Visweswaraiyah Technological University, Bangalore, India
M. Prabu, Adhiyamaan College of Engineering/Anna University, India
Mr. Swakkhar Shatabda, United International University, Bangladesh
Dr. Abdur Rashid Khan, ICIT, Gomal University, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan
Mr. H. Abdul Shabeer, I-Nautix Technologies, Chennai, India
Dr. M. Aramudhan, Perunthalaivar Kamarajar Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Dr. M. P. Thapliyal, Department of Computer Science, HNB Garhwal University (Central University), India
Dr. Shahaboddin Shamshirband, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Mr. Zeashan Hameed Khan, Université de Grenoble, France
Prof. Anil K Ahlawat, Ajay Kumar Garg Engineering College, Ghaziabad, UP Technical University, Lucknow
Mr. Longe Olumide Babatope, University Of Ibadan, Nigeria
Associate Prof. Raman Maini, University College of Engineering, Punjabi University, India
Dr. Maslin Masrom, University Technology Malaysia, Malaysia
Sudipta Chattopadhyay, Jadavpur University, Kolkata, India
Dr. Dang Tuan NGUYEN, University of Information Technology, Vietnam National University - Ho Chi Minh City
Dr. Mary Lourde R., BITS-PILANI Dubai , UAE
Dr. Abdul Aziz, University of Central Punjab, Pakistan
Mr. Karan Singh, Gautam Budtha University, India
Mr. Avinash Pokhriyal, Uttar Pradesh Technical University, Lucknow, India
Associate Prof Dr Zuraini Ismail, University Technology Malaysia, Malaysia
Assistant Prof. Yasser M. Alginahi, Taibah University, Madinah Munawwarah, KSA
Mr. Dakshina Ranjan Kisku, West Bengal University of Technology, India
Mr. Raman Kumar, Dr B R Ambedkar National Institute of Technology, Jalandhar, Punjab, India
Associate Prof. Samir B. Patel, Institute of Technology, Nirma University, India
Dr. M.Munir Ahamed Rabbani, B. S. Abdur Rahman University, India
Asst. Prof. Koushik Majumder, West Bengal University of Technology, India
Dr. Alex Pappachen James, Queensland Micro-nanotechnology center, Griffith University, Australia
Assistant Prof. S. Hariharan, B.S. Abdur Rahman University, India
Asst Prof. Jasmine. K. S, R.V.College of Engineering, India
Mr Naushad Ali Mamode Khan, Ministry of Education and Human Resources, Mauritius
Prof. Mahesh Goyani, G H Patel Collge of Engg. & Tech, V.V.N, Anand, Gujarat, India
Dr. Mana Mohammed, University of Tlemcen, Algeria
Prof. Jatinder Singh, Universal Institution of Engg. & Tech. CHD, India

Mrs. M. Anandhavalli Gauthaman, Sikkim Manipal Institute of Technology, Majitar, East Sikkim
Dr. Bin Guo, Institute Telecom SudParis, France
Mrs. Maleika Mehr Nigar Mohamed Heenaye-Mamode Khan, University of Mauritius
Prof. Pijush Biswas, RCC Institute of Information Technology, India
Mr. V. Bala Dhandayuthapani, Mekelle University, Ethiopia
Dr. Irfan Syamsuddin, State Polytechnic of Ujung Pandang, Indonesia
Mr. Kavi Kumar Khedo, University of Mauritius, Mauritius
Mr. Ravi Chandiran, Zagro Singapore Pte Ltd. Singapore
Mr. Milindkumar V. Sarode, Jawaharlal Darda Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Dr. Shamimul Qamar, KSJ Institute of Engineering & Technology, India
Dr. C. Arun, Anna University, India
Assist. Prof. M.N.Birje, Basaveshwar Engineering College, India
Prof. Hamid Reza Naji, Department of Computer Enigneering, Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran, Iran
Assist. Prof. Debasis Giri, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Haldia Institute of Technology
Subhabrata Barman, Haldia Institute of Technology, West Bengal
Mr. M. I. Lali, COMSATS Institute of Information Technology, Islamabad, Pakistan
Dr. Feroz Khan, Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants, Lucknow, India
Mr. R. Nagendran, Institute of Technology, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India
Mr. Amnach Khawne, King Mongkut's Institute of Technology Ladkrabang, Ladkrabang, Bangkok, Thailand
Dr. P. Chakrabarti, Sir Padampat Singhanian University, Udaipur, India
Mr. Nafiz Imtiaz Bin Hamid, Islamic University of Technology (IUT), Bangladesh.
Shahab-A. Shamshirband, Islamic Azad University, Chalous, Iran
Prof. B. Priestly Shan, Anna Univeristy, Tamilnadu, India
Venkatramreddy Velma, Dept. of Bioinformatics, University of Mississippi Medical Center, Jackson MS USA
Akshi Kumar, Dept. of Computer Engineering, Delhi Technological University, India
Dr. Umesh Kumar Singh, Vikram University, Ujjain, India
Mr. Serguei A. Mokhov, Concordia University, Canada
Mr. Lai Khin Wee, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Malaysia
Dr. Awadhesh Kumar Sharma, Madan Mohan Malviya Engineering College, India
Mr. Syed R. Rizvi, Analytical Services & Materials, Inc., USA
Dr. S. Karthik, SNS College of Technology, India
Mr. Syed Qasim Bukhari, CIMET (Universidad de Granada), Spain
Mr. A.D.Potgantwar, Pune University, India
Dr. Himanshu Aggarwal, Punjabi University, India
Mr. Rajesh Ramachandran, Naipunya Institute of Management and Information Technology, India
Dr. K.L. Shunmuganathan, R.M.K Engg College , Kavaraipettai ,Chennai
Dr. Prasant Kumar Pattnaik, KIST, India.
Dr. Ch. Aswani Kumar, VIT University, India
Mr. Ijaz Ali Shoukat, King Saud University, Riyadh KSA
Mr. Arun Kumar, Sir Padam Pat Singhanian University, Udaipur, Rajasthan
Mr. Muhammad Imran Khan, Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS, Malaysia
Dr. Natarajan Meghanathan, Jackson State University, Jackson, MS, USA
Mr. Mohd Zaki Bin Mas'ud, Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM), Malaysia
Prof. Dr. R. Geetharamani, Dept. of Computer Science and Eng., Rajalakshmi Engineering College, India
Dr. Smita Rajpal, Institute of Technology and Management, Gurgaon, India
Dr. S. Abdul Khader Jilani, University of Tabuk, Tabuk, Saudi Arabia
Mr. Syed Jamal Haider Zaidi, Bahria University, Pakistan

Dr. N. Devarajan, Government College of Technology, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, INDIA
Mr. R. Jagadeesh Kannan, RMK Engineering College, India
Mr. Deo Prakash, Shri Mata Vaishno Devi University, India
Mr. Mohammad Abu Naser, Dept. of EEE, IUT, Gazipur, Bangladesh
Assist. Prof. Prasun Ghosal, Bengal Engineering and Science University, India
Mr. Md. Golam Kaosar, School of Engineering and Science, Victoria University, Melbourne City, Australia
Mr. R. Mahammad Shafi, Madanapalle Institute of Technology & Science, India
Dr. F. Sagayaraj Francis, Pondicherry Engineering College, India
Dr. Ajay Goel, HIET, Kaithal, India
Mr. Nayak Sunil Kashibarao, Bahirji Smarak Mahavidyalaya, India
Mr. Suhas J Manangi, Microsoft India
Dr. Kalyankar N. V., Yeshwant Mahavidyalaya, Nanded, India
Dr. K.D. Verma, S.V. College of Post graduate studies & Research, India
Dr. Amjad Rehman, University Technology Malaysia, Malaysia
Mr. Rachit Garg, L K College, Jalandhar, Punjab
Mr. J. William, M.A.M college of Engineering, Trichy, Tamilnadu, India
Prof. Jue-Sam Chou, Nanhua University, College of Science and Technology, Taiwan
Dr. Thorat S.B., Institute of Technology and Management, India
Mr. Ajay Prasad, Sir Padampat Singhanian University, Udaipur, India
Dr. Kamaljit I. Lakhtaria, Atmiya Institute of Technology & Science, India
Mr. Syed Rafiul Hussain, Ahsanullah University of Science and Technology, Bangladesh
Mrs Fazeela Tunnisa, Najran University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Mrs Kavita Taneja, Maharishi Markandeshwar University, Haryana, India
Mr. Maniyar Shiraz Ahmed, Najran University, Najran, KSA
Mr. Anand Kumar, AMC Engineering College, Bangalore
Dr. Rakesh Chandra Gangwar, Beant College of Engg. & Tech., Gurdaspur (Punjab) India
Dr. V V Rama Prasad, Sree Vidyanikethan Engineering College, India
Assist. Prof. Neetesh Kumar Gupta, Technocrats Institute of Technology, Bhopal (M.P.), India
Mr. Ashish Seth, Uttar Pradesh Technical University, Lucknow, UP India
Dr. V V S S S Balam, Sreenidhi Institute of Science and Technology, India
Mr Rahul Bhatia, Lingaya's Institute of Management and Technology, India
Prof. Niranjana Reddy, P, KITS, Warangal, India
Prof. Rakesh. Lingappa, Vijetha Institute of Technology, Bangalore, India
Dr. Mohammed Ali Hussain, Nimra College of Engineering & Technology, Vijayawada, A.P., India
Dr. A. Srinivasan, MNM Jain Engineering College, Rajiv Gandhi Salai, Thorapakkam, Chennai
Mr. Rakesh Kumar, M.M. University, Mullana, Ambala, India
Dr. Lena Khaled, Zarqa Private University, Aman, Jordan
Ms. Supriya Kapoor, Patni/Lingaya's Institute of Management and Tech., India
Dr. Tossapon Boongoen, Aberystwyth University, UK
Dr. Bilal Alatas, Firat University, Turkey
Assist. Prof. Jyoti Praaksh Singh, Academy of Technology, India
Dr. Ritu Soni, GNG College, India
Dr. Mahendra Kumar, Sagar Institute of Research & Technology, Bhopal, India.
Dr. Binod Kumar, Lakshmi Narayan College of Tech. (LNCT) Bhopal India
Dr. Muzhir Shaban Al-Ani, Amman Arab University Amman – Jordan
Dr. T.C. Manjunath, ATRIA Institute of Tech, India
Mr. Muhammad Zakarya, COMSATS Institute of Information Technology (CIIT), Pakistan

Assist. Prof. Harmunish Taneja, M. M. University, India
Dr. Chitra Dhawale , SICSR, Model Colony, Pune, India
Mrs Sankari Muthukaruppan, Nehru Institute of Engineering and Technology, Anna University, India
Mr. Aaqif Afzaal Abbasi, National University Of Sciences And Technology, Islamabad
Prof. Ashutosh Kumar Dubey, Trinity Institute of Technology and Research Bhopal, India
Mr. G. Appasami, Dr. Pauls Engineering College, India
Mr. M Yasin, National University of Science and Tech, karachi (NUST), Pakistan
Mr. Yaser Miaji, University Utara Malaysia, Malaysia
Mr. Shah Ahsanul Haque, International Islamic University Chittagong (IIUC), Bangladesh
Prof. (Dr) Syed Abdul Sattar, Royal Institute of Technology & Science, India
Dr. S. Sasikumar, Roever Engineering College
Assist. Prof. Monit Kapoor, Maharishi Markandeshwar University, India
Mr. Nwaocha Vivian O, National Open University of Nigeria
Dr. M. S. Vijaya, GR Govindarajulu School of Applied Computer Technology, India
Assist. Prof. Chakresh Kumar, Manav Rachna International University, India
Mr. Kunal Chadha , R&D Software Engineer, Gemalto, Singapore
Mr. Mueen Uddin, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, UTM , Malaysia
Dr. Dhuha Basheer abdullah, Mosul university, Iraq
Mr. S. Audithan, Annamalai University, India
Prof. Vijay K Chaudhari, Technocrats Institute of Technology , India
Associate Prof. Mohd Ilyas Khan, Technocrats Institute of Technology , India
Dr. Vu Thanh Nguyen, University of Information Technology, HoChiMinh City, VietNam
Assist. Prof. Anand Sharma, MITS, Lakshmanagarh, Sikar, Rajasthan, India
Prof. T V Narayana Rao, HITAM Engineering college, Hyderabad
Mr. Deepak Gour, Sir Padampat Singhania University, India
Assist. Prof. Amutharaj Joyson, Kalasalingam University, India
Mr. Ali Balador, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Mr. Mohit Jain, Maharaja Surajmal Institute of Technology, India
Mr. Dilip Kumar Sharma, GLA Institute of Technology & Management, India
Dr. Debojyoti Mitra, Sir padampat Singhania University, India
Dr. Ali Dehghantanha, Asia-Pacific University College of Technology and Innovation, Malaysia
Mr. Zhao Zhang, City University of Hong Kong, China
Prof. S.P. Setty, A.U. College of Engineering, India
Prof. Patel Rakeshkumar Kantilal, Sankalchand Patel College of Engineering, India
Mr. Biswajit Bhowmik, Bengal College of Engineering & Technology, India
Mr. Manoj Gupta, Apex Institute of Engineering & Technology, India
Assist. Prof. Ajay Sharma, Raj Kumar Goel Institute Of Technology, India
Assist. Prof. Ramveer Singh, Raj Kumar Goel Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Hanan Elazhary, Electronics Research Institute, Egypt
Dr. Hosam I. Faiq, USM, Malaysia
Prof. Dipti D. Patil, MAEER's MIT College of Engg. & Tech, Pune, India
Assist. Prof. Devendra Chack, BCT Kumaon engineering College Dwarahat Almora, India
Prof. Manpreet Singh, M. M. Engg. College, M. M. University, India
Assist. Prof. M. Sadiq ali Khan, University of Karachi, Pakistan
Mr. Prasad S. Halgaonkar, MIT - College of Engineering, Pune, India
Dr. Imran Ghani, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Malaysia
Prof. Varun Kumar Kakar, Kumaon Engineering College, Dwarahat, India

Assist. Prof. Nisheeth Joshi, Apaji Institute, Banasthali University, Rajasthan, India
Associate Prof. Kunwar S. Vaisla, VCT Kumaon Engineering College, India
Prof Anupam Choudhary, Bhilai School Of Engg.,Bhilai (C.G.),India
Mr. Divya Prakash Shrivastava, Al Jabal Al garbi University, Zawya, Libya
Associate Prof. Dr. V. Radha, Avinashilingam Deemed university for women, Coimbatore.
Dr. Kasarapu Ramani, JNT University, Anantapur, India
Dr. Anuraag Awasthi, Jayoti Vidyapeeth Womens University, India
Dr. C G Ravichandran, R V S College of Engineering and Technology, India
Dr. Mohamed A. Deriche, King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals, Saudi Arabia
Mr. Abbas Karimi, Universiti Putra Malaysia, Malaysia
Mr. Amit Kumar, Jaypee University of Engg. and Tech., India
Dr. Nikolai Stoianov, Defense Institute, Bulgaria
Assist. Prof. S. Ranichandra, KSR College of Arts and Science, Tiruchencode
Mr. T.K.P. Rajagopal, Diamond Horse International Pvt Ltd, India
Dr. Md. Ekramul Hamid, Rajshahi University, Bangladesh
Mr. Hemanta Kumar Kalita , TATA Consultancy Services (TCS), India
Dr. Messaouda Azzouzi, Ziane Achour University of Djelfa, Algeria
Prof. (Dr.) Juan Jose Martinez Castillo, "Gran Mariscal de Ayacucho" University and Acantelys research Group, Venezuela
Dr. Jatinderkumar R. Saini, Narmada College of Computer Application, India
Dr. Babak Bashari Rad, University Technology of Malaysia, Malaysia
Dr. Nighat Mir, Effat University, Saudi Arabia
Prof. (Dr.) G.M.Nasira, Sasurie College of Engineering, India
Mr. Varun Mittal, Gemalto Pte Ltd, Singapore
Assist. Prof. Mrs P. Banumathi, Kathir College Of Engineering, Coimbatore
Assist. Prof. Quan Yuan, University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point, US
Dr. Pranam Paul, Narula Institute of Technology, Agarpara, West Bengal, India
Assist. Prof. J. Ramkumar, V.L.B Janakiammal college of Arts & Science, India
Mr. P. Sivakumar, Anna university, Chennai, India
Mr. Md. Humayun Kabir Biswas, King Khalid University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Mr. Mayank Singh, J.P. Institute of Engg & Technology, Meerut, India
HJ. Kamaruzaman Jusoff, Universiti Putra Malaysia
Mr. Nikhil Patrick Lobo, CADES, India
Dr. Amit Wason, Rayat-Bahra Institute of Engineering & Boi-Technology, India
Dr. Rajesh Shrivastava, Govt. Benazir Science & Commerce College, Bhopal, India
Assist. Prof. Vishal Bharti, DCE, Gurgaon
Mrs. Sunita Bansal, Birla Institute of Technology & Science, India
Dr. R. Sudhakar, Dr.Mahalingam college of Engineering and Technology, India
Dr. Amit Kumar Garg, Shri Mata Vaishno Devi University, Katra(J&K), India
Assist. Prof. Raj Gaurang Tiwari, AZAD Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Mr. Hamed Taherdoost, Tehran, Iran
Mr. Amin Daneshmand Malayeri, YRC, IAU, Malayer Branch, Iran
Mr. Shantanu Pal, University of Calcutta, India
Dr. Terry H. Walcott, E-Promag Consultancy Group, United Kingdom
Dr. Ezekiel U OKIKE, University of Ibadan, Nigeria
Mr. P. Mahalingam, Caledonian College of Engineering, Oman
Dr. Mahmoud M. A. Abd Ellatif, Mansoura University, Egypt

Prof. Kunwar S. Vaisla, BCT Kumaon Engineering College, India
Prof. Mahesh H. Panchal, Kalol Institute of Technology & Research Centre, India
Mr. Muhammad Asad, Technical University of Munich, Germany
Mr. AliReza Shams Shafigh, Azad Islamic university, Iran
Prof. S. V. Nagaraj, RMK Engineering College, India
Mr. Ashikali M Hasan, Senior Researcher, CelNet security, India
Dr. Adnan Shahid Khan, University Technology Malaysia, Malaysia
Mr. Prakash Gajanan Burade, Nagpur University/ITM college of engg, Nagpur, India
Dr. Jagdish B.Helonde, Nagpur University/ITM college of engg, Nagpur, India
Professor, Doctor BOUHORMA Mohammed, Univertsity Abdelmalek Essaadi, Morocco
Mr. K. Thirumalaivasan, Pondicherry Engg. College, India
Mr. Umbarkar Anantkumar Janardan, Walchand College of Engineering, India
Mr. Ashish Chaurasia, Gyan Ganga Institute of Technology & Sciences, India
Mr. Sunil Taneja, Kurukshetra University, India
Mr. Fauzi Adi Rafrastara, Dian Nuswantoro University, Indonesia
Dr. Yaduvir Singh, Thapar University, India
Dr. Ioannis V. Koskosas, University of Western Macedonia, Greece
Dr. Vasantha Kalyani David, Avinashilingam University for women, Coimbatore
Dr. Ahmed Mansour Manasrah, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia
Miss. Nazanin Sadat Kazazi, University Technology Malaysia, Malaysia
Mr. Saeed Rasouli Heikalabad, Islamic Azad University - Tabriz Branch, Iran
Assoc. Prof. Dharendra Mishra, SVKM's NMIMS University, India
Prof. Shapoor Zarei, UAE Inventors Association, UAE
Prof. B.Raja Sarath Kumar, Lenora College of Engineering, India
Dr. Bashir Alam, Jamia millia Islamia, Delhi, India
Prof. Anant J Umbarkar, Walchand College of Engg., India
Assist. Prof. B. Bharathi, Sathyabama University, India
Dr. Fokrul Alom Mazarbhuiya, King Khalid University, Saudi Arabia
Prof. T.S.Jeyali Laseeth, Anna University of Technology, Tirunelveli, India
Dr. M. Balraju, Jawahar Lal Nehru Technological University Hyderabad, India
Dr. Vijayalakshmi M. N., R.V.College of Engineering, Bangalore
Prof. Walid Moudani, Lebanese University, Lebanon
Dr. Saurabh Pal, VBS Purvanchal University, Jaunpur, India
Associate Prof. Suneet Chaudhary, Dehradun Institute of Technology, India
Associate Prof. Dr. Manuj Darbari, BBD University, India
Ms. Prema Selvaraj, K.S.R College of Arts and Science, India
Assist. Prof. Ms.S.Sasikala, KSR College of Arts & Science, India
Mr. Sukhvinder Singh Deora, NC Institute of Computer Sciences, India
Dr. Abhay Bansal, Amity School of Engineering & Technology, India
Ms. Sumita Mishra, Amity School of Engineering and Technology, India
Professor S. Viswanadha Raju, JNT University Hyderabad, India
Mr. Asghar Shahrzad Khashandarag, Islamic Azad University Tabriz Branch, India
Mr. Manoj Sharma, Panipat Institute of Engg. & Technology, India
Mr. Shakeel Ahmed, King Faisal University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Mohamed Ali Mahjoub, Institute of Engineer of Monastir, Tunisia
Mr. Adri Jovin J.J., SriGuru Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Sukumar Senthilkumar, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia

Mr. Rakesh Bharati, Dehradun Institute of Technology Dehradun, India
Mr. Shervan Fekri Ershad, Shiraz International University, Iran
Mr. Md. Safiqul Islam, Daffodil International University, Bangladesh
Mr. Mahmudul Hasan, Daffodil International University, Bangladesh
Prof. Mandakini Tayade, UIT, RGTU, Bhopal, India
Ms. Sarla More, UIT, RGTU, Bhopal, India
Mr. Tushar Hrishikesh Jaware, R.C. Patel Institute of Technology, Shirpur, India
Ms. C. Divya, Dr G R Damodaran College of Science, Coimbatore, India
Mr. Fahimuddin Shaik, Annamacharya Institute of Technology & Sciences, India
Dr. M. N. Giri Prasad, JNTUCE, Pulivendula, A.P., India
Assist. Prof. Chintan M Bhatt, Charotar University of Science And Technology, India
Prof. Sahista Machchhar, Marwadi Education Foundation's Group of institutions, India
Assist. Prof. Navnish Goel, S. D. College Of Engineering & Technology, India
Mr. Khaja Kamaluddin, Sirt University, Sirt, Libya
Mr. Mohammad Zaidul Karim, Daffodil International, Bangladesh
Mr. M. Vijayakumar, KSR College of Engineering, Tiruchengode, India
Mr. S. A. Ahsan Rajon, Khulna University, Bangladesh
Dr. Muhammad Mohsin Nazir, LCW University Lahore, Pakistan
Mr. Mohammad Asadul Hoque, University of Alabama, USA
Mr. P.V.Sarathchand, Indur Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Mr. Durgesh Samadhiya, Chung Hua University, Taiwan
Dr Venu Kuthadi, University of Johannesburg, Johannesburg, RSA
Dr. (Er) Jasvir Singh, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, Punjab, India
Mr. Jasmin Cosic, Min. of the Interior of Una-sana canton, B&H, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr S. Rajalakshmi, Botho College, South Africa
Dr. Mohamed Sarrab, De Montfort University, UK
Mr. Basappa B. Kodada, Canara Engineering College, India
Assist. Prof. K. Ramana, Annamacharya Institute of Technology and Sciences, India
Dr. Ashu Gupta, Apeejay Institute of Management, Jalandhar, India
Assist. Prof. Shaik Rasool, Shadan College of Engineering & Technology, India
Assist. Prof. K. Suresh, Annamacharya Institute of Tech & Sci. Rajampet, AP, India
Dr . G. Singaravel, K.S.R. College of Engineering, India
Dr B. G. Geetha, K.S.R. College of Engineering, India
Assist. Prof. Kavita Choudhary, ITM University, Gurgaon
Dr. Mehrdad Jalali, Azad University, Mashhad, Iran
Megha Goel, Shamli Institute of Engineering and Technology, Shamli, India
Mr. Chi-Hua Chen, Institute of Information Management, National Chiao-Tung University, Taiwan (R.O.C.)
Assoc. Prof. A. Rajendran, RVS College of Engineering and Technology, India
Assist. Prof. S. Jaganathan, RVS College of Engineering and Technology, India
Assoc. Prof. (Dr.) A S N Chakravarthy, JNTUK University College of Engineering Vizianagaram (State University)
Assist. Prof. Deepshikha Patel, Technocrat Institute of Technology, India
Assist. Prof. Maram Balajee, GMRIT, India
Assist. Prof. Monika Bhatnagar, TIT, India
Prof. Gaurang Panchal, Charotar University of Science & Technology, India
Prof. Anand K. Tripathi, Computer Society of India
Prof. Jyoti Chaudhary, High Performance Computing Research Lab, India
Assist. Prof. Supriya Raheja, ITM University, India

Dr. Pankaj Gupta, Microsoft Corporation, U.S.A.
Assist. Prof. Panchamukesh Chandaka, Hyderabad Institute of Tech. & Management, India
Prof. Mohan H.S, SJB Institute Of Technology, India
Mr. Hossein Malekinezhad, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Mr. Zatin Gupta, Universti Malaysia, Malaysia
Assist. Prof. Amit Chauhan, Phonics Group of Institutions, India
Assist. Prof. Ajal A. J., METS School Of Engineering, India
Mrs. Omowunmi Omobola Adeyemo, University of Ibadan, Nigeria
Dr. Bharat Bhushan Agarwal, I.F.T.M. University, India
Md. Nazrul Islam, University of Western Ontario, Canada
Tushar Kanti, L.N.C.T, Bhopal, India
Er. Aumreesh Kumar Saxena, SIRTs College Bhopal, India
Mr. Mohammad Monirul Islam, Daffodil International University, Bangladesh
Dr. Kashif Nisar, University Utara Malaysia, Malaysia
Dr. Wei Zheng, Rutgers Univ/ A10 Networks, USA
Associate Prof. Rituraj Jain, Vyas Institute of Engg & Tech, Jodhpur – Rajasthan
Assist. Prof. Apoorvi Sood, I.T.M. University, India
Dr. Kayhan Zrar Ghafoor, University Technology Malaysia, Malaysia
Mr. Swapnil Sonar, Truba Institute College of Engineering & Technology, Indore, India
Ms. Yogita Gigras, I.T.M. University, India
Associate Prof. Neelima Sadineni, Pydha Engineering College, India Pydha Engineering College
Assist. Prof. K. Deepika Rani, HITAM, Hyderabad
Ms. Shikha Maheshwari, Jaipur Engineering College & Research Centre, India
Prof. Dr V S Giridhar Akula, Avanthi's Scientific Tech. & Research Academy, Hyderabad
Prof. Dr.S.Saravanan, Muthayammal Engineering College, India
Mr. Mehdi Golsorkhatabar Amiri, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Prof. Amit Sadanand Savyanavar, MITCOE, Pune, India
Assist. Prof. P.Oliver Jayaprakash, Anna University, Chennai
Assist. Prof. Ms. Sujata, ITM University, Gurgaon, India
Dr. Asoke Nath, St. Xavier's College, India
Mr. Masoud Rafiqhi, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Assist. Prof. RamBabu Pemula, NIMRA College of Engineering & Technology, India
Assist. Prof. Ms Rita Chhikara, ITM University, Gurgaon, India
Mr. Sandeep Maan, Government Post Graduate College, India
Prof. Dr. S. Muralidharan, Mepco Schlenk Engineering College, India
Associate Prof. T.V.Sai Krishna, QIS College of Engineering and Technology, India
Mr. R. Balu, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, India
Assist. Prof. Shekhar. R, Dr.SM College of Engineering, India
Prof. P. Senthilkumar, Vivekanandha Institue of Engineering and Technology for Woman, India
Mr. M. Kamarajan, PSNA College of Engineering & Technology, India
Dr. Angajala Srinivasa Rao, Jawaharlal Nehru Technical University, India
Assist. Prof. C. Venkatesh, A.I.T.S, Rajampet, India
Mr. Afshin Rezakhani Roozbahani, Ayatollah Boroujerdi University, Iran
Mr. Laxmi chand, SCTL, Noida, India
Dr. Dr. Abdul Hannan, Vivekanand College, Aurangabad
Prof. Mahesh Panchal, KITRC, Gujarat
Dr. A. Subramani, K.S.R. College of Engineering, Tiruchengode

Assist. Prof. Prakash M, Rajalakshmi Engineering College, Chennai, India
Assist. Prof. Akhilesh K Sharma, Sir Padampat Singhanian University, India
Ms. Varsha Sahni, Guru Nanak Dev Engineering College, Ludhiana, India
Associate Prof. Trilochan Rout, NM Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Mr. Srikanta Kumar Mohapatra, NMIET, Orissa, India
Mr. Waqas Haider Bangyal, Iqra University Islamabad, Pakistan
Dr. S. Vijayaragavan, Christ College of Engineering and Technology, Pondicherry, India
Prof. Elboukhari Mohamed, University Mohammed First, Oujda, Morocco
Dr. Muhammad Asif Khan, King Faisal University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Nagy Ramadan Darwish Omran, Cairo University, Egypt.
Assistant Prof. Anand Nayyar, KCL Institute of Management and Technology, India
Mr. G. Premsankar, Ericsson, India
Assist. Prof. T. Hemalatha, VELS University, India
Prof. Tejaswini Apte, University of Pune, India
Dr. Edmund Ng Giap Weng, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak, Malaysia
Mr. Mahdi Nouri, Iran University of Science and Technology, Iran
Associate Prof. S. Asif Hussain, Annamacharya Institute of technology & Sciences, India
Mrs. Kavita Pabreja, Maharaja Surajmal Institute (an affiliate of GGSIP University), India
Mr. Vorugunti Chandra Sekhar, DA-IICT, India
Mr. Muhammad Najmi Ahmad Zabidi, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Malaysia
Dr. Aderemi A. Atayero, Covenant University, Nigeria
Assist. Prof. Osama Sohaib, Balochistan University of Information Technology, Pakistan
Assist. Prof. K. Suresh, Annamacharya Institute of Technology and Sciences, India
Mr. Hassen Mohammed Abdullaah Alsafi, International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM) Malaysia
Mr. Robail Yasrab, Virtual University of Pakistan, Pakistan
Mr. R. Balu, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, India
Prof. Anand Nayyar, KCL Institute of Management and Technology, Jalandhar
Assoc. Prof. Vivek S Deshpande, MIT College of Engineering, India
Prof. K. Saravanan, Anna university Coimbatore, India
Dr. Ravendra Singh, MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, India
Mr. V. Mathivanan, IBRA College of Technology, Sultanate of OMAN
Assoc. Prof. S. Asif Hussain, AITS, India
Assist. Prof. C. Venkatesh, AITS, India
Mr. Sami Ulhaq, SZABIST Islamabad, Pakistan
Dr. B. Justus Rabi, Institute of Science & Technology, India
Mr. Anuj Kumar Yadav, Dehradun Institute of technology, India
Mr. Alejandro Mosquera, University of Alicante, Spain
Assist. Prof. Arjun Singh, Sir Padampat Singhanian University (SPSU), Udaipur, India
Dr. Smriti Agrawal, JB Institute of Engineering and Technology, Hyderabad
Assist. Prof. Swathi Sambangi, Visakha Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Ms. Prabhjot Kaur, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, India
Mrs. Samaher AL-Hothali, Yanbu University College, Saudi Arabia
Prof. Rajneeshkaur Bedi, MIT College of Engineering, Pune, India
Mr. Hassen Mohammed Abdullaah Alsafi, International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM)
Dr. Wei Zhang, Amazon.com, Seattle, WA, USA
Mr. B. Santhosh Kumar, C S I College of Engineering, Tamil Nadu
Dr. K. Reji Kumar, N S S College, Pandalam, India

Assoc. Prof. K. Seshadri Sastry, EILM University, India
Mr. Kai Pan, UNC Charlotte, USA
Mr. Ruikar Sachin, SGGSIET, India
Prof. (Dr.) Vinodani Katiyar, Sri Ramswaroop Memorial University, India
Assoc. Prof., M. Giri, Sreenivasa Institute of Technology and Management Studies, India
Assoc. Prof. Labib Francis Gergis, Misr Academy for Engineering and Technology (MET), Egypt
Assist. Prof. Amanpreet Kaur, ITM University, India
Assist. Prof. Anand Singh Rajawat, Shri Vaishnav Institute of Technology & Science, Indore
Mrs. Hadeel Saleh Haj Aliwi, Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM), Malaysia
Dr. Abhay Bansal, Amity University, India
Dr. Mohammad A. Mezher, Fahad Bin Sultan University, KSA
Assist. Prof. Nidhi Arora, M.C.A. Institute, India
Prof. Dr. P. Suresh, Karpagam College of Engineering, Coimbatore, India
Dr. Kannan Balasubramanian, Mepco Schlenk Engineering College, India
Dr. S. Sankara Gomathi, Panimalar Engineering college, India
Prof. Anil kumar Suthar, Gujarat Technological University, L.C. Institute of Technology, India
Assist. Prof. R. Hubert Rajan, NOORUL ISLAM UNIVERSITY, India
Assist. Prof. Dr. Jyoti Mahajan, College of Engineering & Technology
Assist. Prof. Homam Reda El-Taj, College of Network Engineering, Saudi Arabia & Malaysia
Mr. Bijan Paul, Shahjalal University of Science & Technology, Bangladesh
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Ch V Phani Krishna, KL University, India
Dr. Vishal Bhatnagar, Ambedkar Institute of Advanced Communication Technologies & Research, India
Dr. Lamir LAOUAMER, Al Qassim University, Dept. Info. Systems & European University of Brittany, Dept. Computer Science, UBO, Brest, France
Prof. Ashish Babanrao Sasankar, G.H.Raisoni Institute Of Information Technology, India
Prof. Pawan Kumar Goel, Shamli Institute of Engineering and Technology, India
Mr. Ram Kumar Singh, S.V Subharti University, India
Assistant Prof. Sunish Kumar O S, Amalijothei College of Engineering, India
Dr Sanjay Bhargava, Banasthali University, India
Mr. Pankaj S. Kulkarni, AVEW's Shatabdi Institute of Technology, India
Mr. Roohollah Etemadi, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Mr. Oloruntoyin Sefiu Taiwo, Emmanuel Alayande College Of Education, Nigeria
Mr. Sumit Goyal, National Dairy Research Institute, India
Mr Jaswinder Singh Dilawari, Geeta Engineering College, India
Prof. Raghuraj Singh, Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpur
Dr. S.K. Mahendran, Anna University, Chennai, India
Dr. Amit Wason, Hindustan Institute of Technology & Management, Punjab
Dr. Ashu Gupta, Apeejay Institute of Management, India
Assist. Prof. D. Asir Antony Gnana Singh, M.I.E.T Engineering College, India
Mrs Mina Farmanbar, Eastern Mediterranean University, Famagusta, North Cyprus
Mr. Maram Balajee, GMR Institute of Technology, India
Mr. Moiz S. Ansari, Isra University, Hyderabad, Pakistan
Mr. Adebayo, Olawale Surajudeen, Federal University of Technology Minna, Nigeria
Mr. Jasvir Singh, University College Of Engg., India
Mr. Vivek Tiwari, MANIT, Bhopal, India
Assoc. Prof. R. Navaneethakrishnan, Bharathiyar College of Engineering and Technology, India
Mr. Somdip Dey, St. Xavier's College, Kolkata, India

Mr. Souleymane Balla-Arabé, Xi'an University of Electronic Science and Technology, China
Mr. Mahabub Alam, Rajshahi University of Engineering and Technology, Bangladesh
Mr. Sathyapraksh P., S.K.P Engineering College, India
Dr. N. Karthikeyan, SNS College of Engineering, Anna University, India
Dr. Binod Kumar, JSPM's, Jayawant Technical Campus, Pune, India
Assoc. Prof. Dinesh Goyal, Suresh Gyan Vihar University, India
Mr. Md. Abdul Ahad, K L University, India
Mr. Vikas Bajpai, The LNM IIT, India
Dr. Manish Kumar Anand, Salesforce (R & D Analytics), San Francisco, USA
Assist. Prof. Dheeraj Murari, Kumaon Engineering College, India
Assoc. Prof. Dr. A. Muthukumaravel, VELS University, Chennai
Mr. A. Siles Balasingh, St. Joseph University in Tanzania, Tanzania
Mr. Ravindra Daga Badgujar, R C Patel Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Preeti Khanna, SVKM's NMIMS, School of Business Management, India
Mr. Kumar Dayanand, Cambridge Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Syed Asif Ali, SMI University Karachi, Pakistan
Prof. Pallvi Pandit, Himachal Pradesh University, India
Mr. Ricardo Verschueren, University of Gloucestershire, UK
Assist. Prof. Mamta Juneja, University Institute of Engineering and Technology, Panjab University, India
Assoc. Prof. P. Surendra Varma, NRI Institute of Technology, JNTU Kakinada, India
Assist. Prof. Gaurav Shrivastava, RGPV / SVITS Indore, India
Dr. S. Sumathi, Anna University, India
Assist. Prof. Ankita M. Kapadia, Charotar University of Science and Technology, India
Mr. Deepak Kumar, Indian Institute of Technology (BHU), India
Dr. Dr. Rajan Gupta, GGSIP University, New Delhi, India
Assist. Prof. M. Anand Kumar, Karpagam University, Coimbatore, India
Mr. Mr Arshad Mansoor, Pakistan Aeronautical Complex
Mr. Kapil Kumar Gupta, Ansal Institute of Technology and Management, India
Dr. Neeraj Tomer, SINE International Institute of Technology, Jaipur, India
Assist. Prof. Trunal J. Patel, C.G.Patel Institute of Technology, Uka Tarsadia University, Bardoli, Surat
Mr. Sivakumar, Codework solutions, India
Mr. Mohammad Sadegh Mirzaei, PGNR Company, Iran
Dr. Gerard G. Dumancas, Oklahoma Medical Research Foundation, USA
Mr. Varadala Sridhar, Varadhman College Engineering College, Affiliated To JNTU, Hyderabad
Assist. Prof. Manoj Dhawan, SVITS, Indore
Assoc. Prof. Chitreshh Banerjee, Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur, India
Dr. S. Santhi, SCSVMV University, India
Mr. Davood Mohammadi Souran, Ministry of Energy of Iran, Iran
Mr. Shamim Ahmed, Bangladesh University of Business and Technology, Bangladesh
Mr. Sandeep Reddivari, Mississippi State University, USA
Assoc. Prof. Ousmane Thiare, Gaston Berger University, Senegal
Dr. Hazra Imran, Athabasca University, Canada
Dr. Setu Kumar Chaturvedi, Technocrats Institute of Technology, Bhopal, India
Mr. Mohd Dilshad Ansari, Jaypee University of Information Technology, India
Ms. Jaspreet Kaur, Distance Education LPU, India
Dr. D. Nagarajan, Salalah College of Technology, Sultanate of Oman
Dr. K.V.N.R.Sai Krishna, S.V.R.M. College, India

Mr. Himanshu Pareek, Center for Development of Advanced Computing (CDAC), India
Mr. Khaldi Amine, Badji Mokhtar University, Algeria
Mr. Mohammad Sadegh Mirzaei, Scientific Applied University, Iran
Assist. Prof. Khyati Chaudhary, Ram-eesh Institute of Engg. & Technology, India
Mr. Sanjay Agal, Pacific College of Engineering Udaipur, India
Mr. Abdul Mateen Ansari, King Khalid University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. H.S. Behera, Veer Surendra Sai University of Technology (VSSUT), India
Dr. Shrikant Tiwari, Shri Shankaracharya Group of Institutions (SSGI), India
Prof. Ganesh B. Regulwar, Shri Shankarprasad Agnihotri College of Engg, India
Prof. Pinnamaneni Bhanu Prasad, Matrix vision GmbH, Germany
Dr. Shrikant Tiwari, Shri Shankaracharya Technical Campus (SSTC), India
Dr. Siddesh G.K., : Dayananada Sagar College of Engineering, Bangalore, India
Dr. Nadir Bouchama, CERIST Research Center, Algeria
Dr. R. Sathishkumar, Sri Venkateswara College of Engineering, India
Assistant Prof (Dr.) Mohamed Moussaoui, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Morocco
Dr. S. Malathi, Panimalar Engineering College, Chennai, India
Dr. V. Subedha, Panimalar Institute of Technology, Chennai, India
Dr. Prashant Panse, Swami Vivekanand College of Engineering, Indore, India
Dr. Hamza Aldabbas, Al-Balqa'a Applied University, Jordan
Dr. G. Rasitha Banu, Vel's University, Chennai
Dr. V. D. Ambeth Kumar, Panimalar Engineering College, Chennai
Prof. Anuranjan Misra, Bhagwant Institute of Technology, Ghaziabad, India
Ms. U. Sinthuja, PSG college of arts &science, India
Dr. Ehsan Saradar Torshizi, Urmia University, Iran
Dr. Shamneesh Sharma, APG Shimla University, Shimla (H.P.), India
Assistant Prof. A. S. Syed Navaz, Muthayammal College of Arts & Science, India
Assistant Prof. Ranjit Panigrahi, Sikkim Manipal Institute of Technology, Majitar, Sikkim
Dr. Khaled Eskaf, Arab Academy for Science ,Technology & Maritime Transportation, Egypt
Dr. Nishant Gupta, University of Jammu, India
Assistant Prof. Nagarajan Sankaran, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu, India
Assistant Prof. Tribikram Pradhan, Manipal Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Nasser Lotfi, Eastern Mediterranean University, Northern Cyprus
Dr. R. Manavalan, K S Rangasamy college of Arts and Science, Tamilnadu, India
Assistant Prof. P. Krishna Sankar, K S Rangasamy college of Arts and Science, Tamilnadu, India
Dr. Rahul Malik, Cisco Systems, USA
Dr. S. C. Lingareddy, ALPHA College of Engineering, India
Assistant Prof. Mohammed Shuaib, Interat University, Lucknow, India
Dr. Sachin Yele, Sanghvi Institute of Management & Science, India
Dr. T. Thambidurai, Sun Univercell, Singapore
Prof. Anandkumar Telang, BKIT, India
Assistant Prof. R. Poorvadevi, SCSVMV University, India
Dr Uttam Mande, Gitam University, India
Dr. Poornima Girish Naik, Shahu Institute of Business Education and Research (SIBER), India
Prof. Md. Abu Kausar, Jaipur National University, Jaipur, India
Dr. Mohammed Zuber, AISECT University, India
Prof. Kalum Priyanath Udagepola, King Abdulaziz University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. K. R. Ananth, Velalar College of Engineering and Technology, India

Assistant Prof. Sanjay Sharma, Roorkee Engineering & Management Institute Shamli (U.P), India
Assistant Prof. Panem Charan Arur, Priyadarshini Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Ashwak Mahmood muhsen alabaichi, Karbala University / College of Science, Iraq
Dr. Urmila Shrawankar, G H Raison College of Engineering, Nagpur (MS), India
Dr. Krishan Kumar Paliwal, Panipat Institute of Engineering & Technology, India
Dr. Mukesh Negi, Tech Mahindra, India
Dr. Anuj Kumar Singh, Amity University Gurgaon, India
Dr. Babar Shah, Gyeongsang National University, South Korea
Assistant Prof. Jayprakash Upadhyay, SRI-TECH Jabalpur, India
Assistant Prof. Varadala Sridhar, Vidya Jyothi Institute of Technology, India
Assistant Prof. Parameshachari B D, KSIT, Bangalore, India
Assistant Prof. Ankit Garg, Amity University, Haryana, India
Assistant Prof. Rajashe Karappa, SDMCET, Karnataka, India
Assistant Prof. Varun Jasuja, GNIT, India
Assistant Prof. Sonal Honale, Abha Gaikwad Patil College of Engineering Nagpur, India
Dr. Pooja Choudhary, CT Group of Institutions, NIT Jalandhar, India
Dr. Faouzi Hidoussi, UHL Batna, Algeria
Dr. Naseer Ali Hussein, Wasit University, Iraq
Assistant Prof. Vinod Kumar Shukla, Amity University, Dubai
Dr. Ahmed Farouk Metwaly, K L University
Mr. Mohammed Noaman Murad, Cihan University, Iraq
Dr. Suxing Liu, Arkansas State University, USA
Dr. M. Gomathi, Velalar College of Engineering and Technology, India
Assistant Prof. Sumardiono, College PGRI Blitar, Indonesia
Dr. Latika Kharb, Jagan Institute of Management Studies (JIMS), Delhi, India
Associate Prof. S. Raja, Pauls College of Engineering and Technology, Tamilnadu, India
Assistant Prof. Seyed Reza Pakize, Shahid Sani High School, Iran
Dr. Thiyagu Nagaraj, University-INO, India
Assistant Prof. Noreen Sarai, Harare Institute of Technology, Zimbabwe
Assistant Prof. Gajanand Sharma, Suresh Gyan Vihar University Jaipur, Rajasthan, India
Assistant Prof. Mapari Vikas Prakash, Siddhant COE, Sudumbare, Pune, India
Dr. Devesh Katiyar, Shri Ramswaroop Memorial University, India
Dr. Shenshen Liang, University of California, Santa Cruz, US
Assistant Prof. Mohammad Abu Omar, Limkokwing University of Creative Technology- Malaysia
Mr. Snehasis Banerjee, Tata Consultancy Services, India
Assistant Prof. Kibona Lusekelo, Ruaha Catholic University (RUCU), Tanzania
Assistant Prof. Adib Kabir Chowdhury, University College Technology Sarawak, Malaysia
Dr. Ying Yang, Computer Science Department, Yale University, USA
Dr. Vinay Shukla, Institute Of Technology & Management, India
Dr. Liviu Octavian Maftciu-Scai, West University of Timisoara, Romania
Assistant Prof. Rana Khudhair Abbas Ahmed, Al-Rafidain University College, Iraq
Assistant Prof. Nitin A. Naik, S.R.T.M. University, India
Dr. Timothy Powers, University of Hertfordshire, UK
Dr. S. Prasath, Bharathiar University, Erode, India
Dr. Ritu Shrivastava, SIRTIS Bhopal, India
Prof. Rohit Shrivastava, Mittal Institute of Technology, Bhopal, India
Dr. Gianina Mihai, Dunarea de Jos" University of Galati, Romania

Assistant Prof. Ms. T. Kalai Selvi, Erode Sengunthar Engineering College, India
Assistant Prof. Ms. C. Kavitha, Erode Sengunthar Engineering College, India
Assistant Prof. K. Sinivasamoorthi, Erode Sengunthar Engineering College, India
Assistant Prof. Mallikarjun C Sarsamba Bheemna Khandre Institute Technology, Bhalki, India
Assistant Prof. Vishwanath Chikaraddi, Veermata Jijabai technological Institute (Central Technological Institute), India
Assistant Prof. Dr. Ikvinderpal Singh, Trai Shatabdi GGS Khalsa College, India
Assistant Prof. Mohammed Noaman Murad, Cihan University, Iraq
Professor Yousef Farhaoui, Moulay Ismail University, Errachidia, Morocco
Dr. Parul Verma, Amity University, India
Professor Yousef Farhaoui, Moulay Ismail University, Errachidia, Morocco
Assistant Prof. Madhavi Dhingra, Amity University, Madhya Pradesh, India
Assistant Prof. G. Selvavinayagam, SNS College of Technology, Coimbatore, India
Assistant Prof. Madhavi Dhingra, Amity University, MP, India
Professor Kartheesan Log, Anna University, Chennai
Professor Vasudeva Acharya, Shri Madhwa vadiraja Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Asif Iqbal Hajamydeen, Management & Science University, Malaysia
Assistant Prof., Mahendra Singh Meena, Amity University Haryana
Assistant Professor Manjeet Kaur, Amity University Haryana
Dr. Mohamed Abd El-Basset Matwalli, Zagazig University, Egypt
Dr. Ramani Kannan, Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS, Malaysia
Assistant Prof. S. Jagadeesan Subramaniam, Anna University, India
Assistant Prof. Dharmendra Choudhary, Tripura University, India
Assistant Prof. Deepika Vodnala, SR Engineering College, India
Dr. Kai Cong, Intel Corporation & Computer Science Department, Portland State University, USA
Dr. Kailas R Patil, Vishwakarma Institute of Information Technology (VIIT), India
Dr. Omar A. Alzubi, Faculty of IT / Al-Balqa Applied University, Jordan
Assistant Prof. Kareemullah Shaik, Nimra Institute of Science and Technology, India
Assistant Prof. Chirag Modi, NIT Goa
Dr. R. Ramkumar, Nandha Arts And Science College, India
Dr. Priyadarshini Vydhialingam, Harathiar University, India
Dr. P. S. Jagadeesh Kumar, DBIT, Bangalore, Karnataka
Dr. Vikas Thada, AMITY University, Pachgaon
Dr. T. A. Ashok Kumar, Institute of Management, Christ University, Bangalore
Dr. Shaheera Rashwan, Informatics Research Institute
Dr. S. Preetha Gunasekar, Bharathiyar University, India
Asst Professor Sameer Dev Sharma, Uttaranchal University, Dehradun
Dr. Zhihan Iv, Chinese Academy of Science, China
Dr. Ikvinderpal Singh, Trai Shatabdi GGS Khalsa College, Amritsar
Dr. Umar Ruhi, University of Ottawa, Canada
Dr. Jasmin Cosic, University of Bihac, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr. Homam Reda El-Taj, University of Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Dr. Mostafa Ghobaei Arani, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Dr. Ayyasamy Ayyanar, Annamalai University, India
Dr. Selvakumar Manickam, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia
Dr. Murali Krishna Namana, GITAM University, India
Dr. Smriti Agrawal, Chaitanya Bharathi Institute of Technology, Hyderabad, India
Professor Vimalathithan Rathinasabapathy, Karpagam College Of Engineering, India

Dr. Sushil Chandra Dimri, Graphic Era University, India
Dr. Dinh-Sinh Mai, Le Quy Don Technical University, Vietnam
Dr. S. Rama Sree, Aditya Engg. College, India
Dr. Ehab T. Alnfrawy, Sadat Academy, Egypt
Dr. Patrick D. Cerna, Haramaya University, Ethiopia
Dr. Vishal Jain, Bharati Vidyapeeth's Institute of Computer Applications and Management (BVICAM), India
Associate Prof. Dr. Jiliang Zhang, North Eastern University, China
Dr. Sharefa Murad, Middle East University, Jordan
Dr. Ajeet Singh Poonia, Govt. College of Engineering & technology, Rajasthan, India
Dr. Vahid Esmaeaelzadeh, University of Science and Technology, Iran
Dr. Jacek M. Czerniak, Casimir the Great University in Bydgoszcz, Institute of Technology, Poland
Associate Prof. Anisur Rehman Nasir, Jamia Millia Islamia University
Assistant Prof. Imran Ahmad, COMSATS Institute of Information Technology, Pakistan
Professor Ghulam Qasim, Preston University, Islamabad, Pakistan
Dr. Parameshachari B D, GSSS Institute of Engineering and Technology for Women
Dr. Wencan Luo, University of Pittsburgh, US
Dr. Musa PEKER, Faculty of Technology, Mugla Sitki Kocman University, Turkey
Dr. Gunasekaran Shanmugam, Anna University, India
Dr. Binh P. Nguyen, National University of Singapore, Singapore
Dr. Rajkumar Jain, Indian Institute of Technology Indore, India
Dr. Imtiaz Ali Halepoto, QUEST Nawabshah, Pakistan
Dr. Shaligram Prajapat, Devi Ahilya University Indore India
Dr. Sunita Singhal, Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani, India
Dr. Ijaz Ali Shoukat, King Saud University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Anuj Gupta, IKG Punjab Technical University, India
Dr. Sonali Saini, IES-IPS Academy, India
Dr. Krishan Kumar, MotiLal Nehru National Institute of Technology, Allahabad, India
Dr. Z. Faizal Khan, College of Engineering, Shaqra University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Prof. M. Padmavathamma, S.V. University Tirupati, India
Prof. A. Velayudham, Cape Institute of Technology, India
Prof. Seifeidne Kadry, American University of the Middle East
Dr. J. Durga Prasad Rao, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur
Assistant Prof. Najam Hasan, Dhofar University
Dr. G. Suseendran, Vels University, Pallavaram, Chennai
Prof. Ankit Faldu, Gujarat Technological University- Atmiya Institute of Technology and Science
Dr. Ali Habiboghli, Islamic Azad University
Dr. Deepak Dembla, JECRC University, Jaipur, India
Dr. Pankaj Rajan, Walmart Labs, USA
Assistant Prof. Radoslava Kraveva, South-West University "Neofit Rilski", Bulgaria
Assistant Prof. Medhavi Shriwas, Shri vaishnav institute of Technology, India
Associate Prof. Sedat Akleylek, Ondokuz Mayıs University, Turkey
Dr. U.V. Arivazhagu, Kingston Engineering College Affiliated To Anna University, India
Dr. Touseef Ali, University of Engineering and Technology, Taxila, Pakistan
Assistant Prof. Naren Jeeva, SASTRA University, India
Dr. Riccardo Colella, University of Salento, Italy
Dr. Enache Maria Cristina, University of Galati, Romania
Dr. Senthil P, Kurinji College of Arts & Science, India

Dr. Hasan Ashrafi-rizi, Isfahan University of Medical Sciences, Isfahan, Iran
Dr. Mazhar Malik, Institute of Southern Punjab, Pakistan
Dr. Yajie Miao, Carnegie Mellon University, USA
Dr. Kamran Shaukat, University of the Punjab, Pakistan
Dr. Sasikaladevi N., SASTRA University, India
Dr. Ali Asghar Rahmani Hosseinabadi, Islamic Azad University Ayatollah Amoli Branch, Amol, Iran
Dr. Velin Kralev, South-West University "Neofit Rilski", Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria
Dr. Marius Iulian Mihailescu, LUMINA - The University of South-East Europe
Dr. Sriramula Nagaprasad, S.R.R.Govt.Arts & Science College, Karimnagar, India
Prof (Dr.) Namrata Dhanda, Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam Technical University, Lucknow, India
Dr. Javed Ahmed Mahar, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur Mir's, Pakistan
Dr. B. Narendra Kumar Rao, Sree Vidyanikethan Engineering College, India
Dr. Shahzad Anwar, University of Engineering & Technology Peshawar, Pakistan
Dr. Basit Shahzad, King Saud University, Riyadh - Saudi Arabia
Dr. Nilamadhab Mishra, Chang Gung University
Dr. Sachin Kumar, Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee
Dr. Santosh Nanda, Biju-Pattnaik University of Technology
Dr. Sherzod Turaev, International Islamic University Malaysia
Dr. Yilun Shang, Tongji University, Department of Mathematics, Shanghai, China
Dr. Nuzhat Shaikh, Modern Education society's College of Engineering, Pune, India
Dr. Parul Verma, Amity University, Lucknow campus, India
Dr. Rachid Alaoui, Agadir Ibn Zohr University, Agadir, Morocco
Dr. Dharmendra Patel, Charotar University of Science and Technology, India
Dr. Dong Zhang, University of Central Florida, USA
Dr. Kennedy Chinedu Okafor, Federal University of Technology Owerri, Nigeria
Prof. C Ram Kumar, Dr NGP Institute of Technology, India
Dr. Sandeep Gupta, GGS IP University, New Delhi, India
Dr. Shahanawaj Ahamad, University of Ha'il, Ha'il City, Ministry of Higher Education, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Dr. Najeed Ahmed Khan, NED University of Engineering & Technology, India
Dr. Sajid Ullah Khan, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak, Malaysia
Dr. Muhammad Asif, National Textile University Faisalabad, Pakistan
Dr. Yu BI, University of Central Florida, Orlando, FL, USA
Dr. Brijendra Kumar Joshi, Research Center, Military College of Telecommunication Engineering, India
Prof. Dr. Nak Eun Cho, Pukyong National University, Korea
Prof. Wasim Ul-Haq, Faculty of Science, Majmaah University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Mohsan Raza, G.C University Faisalabad, Pakistan
Dr. Syed Zakar Hussain Bukhari, National Science and Technology Azad Jamu Kashmir, Pakistan
Dr. Ruksar Fatima, KBN College of Engineering, Gulbarga, Karnataka, India
Associate Professor S. Karpagavalli, Department of Computer Science, PSGR Krishnammal College for Women
Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India
Dr. Bushra Mohamed Elamin Elhaim, Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Shamik Tiwari, Department of CSE, CET, Mody University, Lakshmangarh
Dr. Rohit Raja, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Shri Shankaracharya Group of Institutions, India
Prof. Dr. Aqeel-ur-Rehman, Department of Computing, HIET, FEST, Hamdard University, Pakistan
Dr. Nageswara Rao Moparthi, Velagapudi Ramakrishna Siddhartha Engineering College, India
Dr. Mohd Muqem, Department of Computer Application, Integral University, Lucknow, India
Dr. Zeeshan Bhatti, Institute of Information and Communication Technology, University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan

Dr. Emrah Irmak, Biomedical Engineering Department, Karabuk University, Turkey
Dr. Fouad Abdulameer salman, School of Informatics and Applied Mathematics, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu
Dr. N. Prasath, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, KPR Institute of Engineering and Technology, Arasur, Coimbatore
Dr. Hasan Ashrafi-rizi, Health Information Technology Research Center, Isfahan University of Medical Sciences, Hezar Jerib Avenue, Isfahan, Iran
Dr. N. Sasikaladevi, School of Computing, SASTRA University, Thirumalisamudram, Tamilnadu, India.
Dr. Anchit Bijalwan, Arba Minch University, Ethiopia
Dr. K. Sathishkumar, BlueCrest University College, Accra North, Ghana, West Africa
Dr. Dr. Parameshachari B D, GSSS Institute of Engineering and Technology for Women, Affiliated to Visvesvaraya Technological University, Belagavi
Dr. C. Shoba Bindu, Dept. of CSE, JNTUA College of Engineering, India
Dr. M. Inbavalli, ER. Perumal Manimekalai College of Engineering, Hosur, Tamilnadu, India
Dr. Vidya Sagar Ponnamp, Dept. of IT, Velagapudi Ramakrishna Siddhartha Engineering College, India
Dr. Kelvin LO M. F., The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong
Prof. Karimella Vikram, G.H. Rasoni College of Engineering & Management, Pune, India
Dr. Shajilin Loret J.B., VV College of Engineering, India
Dr. P. Sujatha, Department of Computer Science at Vels University, Chennai
Dr. Vaibhav Sundriyal, Old Dominion University Research Foundation, USA
Dr. Md Masud Rana, Khulna University of Engineering and Technology, Bangladesh
Dr. Gurcharan Singh, Khalsa College Amritsar, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, India
Dr. Richard Otieno Omollo, Department of Computer Science and Software Engineering, Jaramogi Oginga Odinga University of Science and Technology, Kenya
Prof. (Dr) Amit Verma, Computer Science & Engineering, Chandigarh Engineering College, Landran, Mohali, India
Dr. Vidya Sagar Ponnamp, Velagapudi Ramakrishna Siddhartha Engineering College, India
Dr. Bohui Wang, School of Aerospace Science and Technology, Xidian University, P.R. China
Dr. M. Anjan Kumar, Department of Computer Science, Satavahana University, Karimnagar
Dr. Hanumanthappa J., DoS in CS, Uni of Mysuru, Karnataka, India
Dr. Pouya Derakhshan-Barjoei, Dept. of Telecommunication and Engineering, Islamic Azad University, Iran
Dr. Tanweer Alam, Islamic University of Madinah, Dept. of Computer Science, College of Computer and Information System, Al Madinah, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Kumar Keshamoni, Dept. of ECE, Vaagdevi Engineering College, Warangal, Telangana, India
Dr. G. Rajkumar, N.M.S.S.Vellaichamy Nadar College, Madurai, Tamilnadu, India
Dr. P. Mayil Vel Kumar, Karpagam Institute of Technology, Coimbatore, India
Dr. M. Yaswanth Bhanu Murthy, Vasireddy Venkatadri Institute of Technology, Guntur, A.P., India
Asst. Prof. Dr. Mehmet Barış TABAKCIOĞLU, Bursa Technical University, Turkey
Dr. Mohd. Muntjir, College of Computers and Information Technology, Taif University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Dr. Sanjay Agal, Aravali Institute of Technical Studies, Udaipur, India
Dr. Shanshan Tuo, xAd Inc., US
Dr. Subhadra Shaw, AKS University, Satna, India
Dr. Piyush Anand, Noida International University, Greater Noida, India
Dr. Brijendra Kumar Joshi, Research Center Military College of Telecommunication Engineering, India
Dr. V. Sreerama Murthy, GMRIT, Rajam, AP, India
Dr. S. Nagarajan, Annamalai University, India
Prof. Pramod Bhausaheb Deshmukh, D. Y. Patil College of Engineering, Akurdi, Pune, India

CALL FOR PAPERS

International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security

IJCSIS 2022-2023

ISSN: 1947-5500

<http://sites.google.com/site/ijcsis/>

International Journal Computer Science and Information Security, IJCSIS, is the premier scholarly venue in the areas of computer science and security issues. IJCSIS 2011 will provide a high profile, leading edge platform for researchers and engineers alike to publish state-of-the-art research in the respective fields of information technology and communication security. The journal will feature a diverse mixture of publication articles including core and applied computer science related topics.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the special issue by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to. Submissions may span a broad range of topics, e.g.:

Track A: Security

Access control, Anonymity, Audit and audit reduction & Authentication and authorization, Applied cryptography, Cryptanalysis, Digital Signatures, Biometric security, Boundary control devices, Certification and accreditation, Cross-layer design for security, Security & Network Management, Data and system integrity, Database security, Defensive information warfare, Denial of service protection, Intrusion Detection, Anti-malware, Distributed systems security, Electronic commerce, E-mail security, Spam, Phishing, E-mail fraud, Virus, worms, Trojan Protection, Grid security, Information hiding and watermarking & Information survivability, Insider threat protection, Integrity
Intellectual property protection, Internet/Intranet Security, Key management and key recovery, Language-based security, Mobile and wireless security, Mobile, Ad Hoc and Sensor Network Security, Monitoring and surveillance, Multimedia security ,Operating system security, Peer-to-peer security, Performance Evaluations of Protocols & Security Application, Privacy and data protection, Product evaluation criteria and compliance, Risk evaluation and security certification, Risk/vulnerability assessment, Security & Network Management, Security Models & protocols, Security threats & countermeasures (DDoS, MiM, Session Hijacking, Replay attack etc.), Trusted computing, Ubiquitous Computing Security, Virtualization security, VoIP security, Web 2.0 security, Submission Procedures, Active Defense Systems, Adaptive Defense Systems, Benchmark, Analysis and Evaluation of Security Systems, Distributed Access Control and Trust Management, Distributed Attack Systems and Mechanisms, Distributed Intrusion Detection/Prevention Systems, Denial-of-Service Attacks and Countermeasures, High Performance Security Systems, Identity Management and Authentication, Implementation, Deployment and Management of Security Systems, Intelligent Defense Systems, Internet and Network Forensics, Large-scale Attacks and Defense, RFID Security and Privacy, Security Architectures in Distributed Network Systems, Security for Critical Infrastructures, Security for P2P systems and Grid Systems, Security in E-Commerce, Security and Privacy in Wireless Networks, Secure Mobile Agents and Mobile Code, Security Protocols, Security Simulation and Tools, Security Theory and Tools, Standards and Assurance Methods, Trusted Computing, Viruses, Worms, and Other Malicious Code, World Wide Web Security, Novel and emerging secure architecture, Study of attack strategies, attack modeling, Case studies and analysis of actual attacks, Continuity of Operations during an attack, Key management, Trust management, Intrusion detection techniques, Intrusion response, alarm management, and correlation analysis, Study of tradeoffs between security and system performance, Intrusion tolerance systems, Secure protocols, Security in wireless networks (e.g. mesh networks, sensor networks, etc.), Cryptography and Secure Communications, Computer Forensics, Recovery and Healing, Security Visualization, Formal Methods in Security, Principles for Designing a Secure Computing System, Autonomic Security, Internet Security, Security in Health Care Systems, Security Solutions Using Reconfigurable Computing, Adaptive and Intelligent Defense Systems, Authentication and Access control, Denial of service attacks and countermeasures, Identity, Route and

Location Anonymity schemes, Intrusion detection and prevention techniques, Cryptography, encryption algorithms and Key management schemes, Secure routing schemes, Secure neighbor discovery and localization, Trust establishment and maintenance, Confidentiality and data integrity, Security architectures, deployments and solutions, Emerging threats to cloud-based services, Security model for new services, Cloud-aware web service security, Information hiding in Cloud Computing, Securing distributed data storage in cloud, Security, privacy and trust in mobile computing systems and applications, **Middleware security & Security features:** middleware software is an asset on its own and has to be protected, interaction between security-specific and other middleware features, e.g., context-awareness, **Middleware-level security monitoring and measurement:** metrics and mechanisms for quantification and evaluation of security enforced by the middleware, **Security co-design:** trade-off and co-design between application-based and middleware-based security, **Policy-based management:** innovative support for policy-based definition and enforcement of security concerns, **Identification and authentication mechanisms:** Means to capture application specific constraints in defining and enforcing access control rules, **Middleware-oriented security patterns:** identification of patterns for sound, reusable security, **Security in aspect-based middleware:** mechanisms for isolating and enforcing security aspects, **Security in agent-based platforms:** protection for mobile code and platforms, Smart Devices: Biometrics, National ID cards, Embedded Systems Security and TPMs, RFID Systems Security, Smart Card Security, Pervasive Systems: Digital Rights Management (DRM) in pervasive environments, Intrusion Detection and Information Filtering, Localization Systems Security (Tracking of People and Goods), Mobile Commerce Security, Privacy Enhancing Technologies, Security Protocols (for Identification and Authentication, Confidentiality and Privacy, and Integrity), Ubiquitous Networks: Ad Hoc Networks Security, Delay-Tolerant Network Security, Domestic Network Security, Peer-to-Peer Networks Security, Security Issues in Mobile and Ubiquitous Networks, Security of GSM/GPRS/UMTS Systems, Sensor Networks Security, Vehicular Network Security, Wireless Communication Security: Bluetooth, NFC, WiFi, WiMAX, WiMedia, others

This Track will emphasize the design, implementation, management and applications of computer communications, networks and services. Topics of mostly theoretical nature are also welcome, provided there is clear practical potential in applying the results of such work.

Track B: Computer Science

Broadband wireless technologies: LTE, WiMAX, WiRAN, HSDPA, HSUPA, Resource allocation and interference management, Quality of service and scheduling methods, Capacity planning and dimensioning, Cross-layer design and Physical layer based issue, Interworking architecture and interoperability, Relay assisted and cooperative communications, Location and provisioning and mobility management, Call admission and flow/congestion control, Performance optimization, Channel capacity modeling and analysis, Middleware Issues: Event-based, publish/subscribe, and message-oriented middleware, Reconfigurable, adaptable, and reflective middleware approaches, Middleware solutions for reliability, fault tolerance, and quality-of-service, Scalability of middleware, Context-aware middleware, Autonomic and self-managing middleware, Evaluation techniques for middleware solutions, Formal methods and tools for designing, verifying, and evaluating, middleware, Software engineering techniques for middleware, Service oriented middleware, Agent-based middleware, Security middleware, Network Applications: Network-based automation, Cloud applications, Ubiquitous and pervasive applications, Collaborative applications, RFID and sensor network applications, Mobile applications, Smart home applications, Infrastructure monitoring and control applications, Remote health monitoring, GPS and location-based applications, Networked vehicles applications, Alert applications, Embedded Computer System, Advanced Control Systems, and Intelligent Control : Advanced control and measurement, computer and microprocessor-based control, signal processing, estimation and identification techniques, application specific IC's, nonlinear and adaptive control, optimal and robot control, intelligent control, evolutionary computing, and intelligent systems, instrumentation subject to critical conditions, automotive, marine and aero-space control and all other control applications, Intelligent Control System, Wiring/Wireless Sensor, Signal Control System. Sensors, Actuators and Systems Integration : Intelligent sensors and actuators, multisensor fusion, sensor array and multi-channel processing, micro/nano technology, microsensors and microactuators, instrumentation electronics, MEMS and system integration, wireless sensor, Network Sensor, Hybrid

Sensor, Distributed Sensor Networks. Signal and Image Processing : Digital signal processing theory, methods, DSP implementation, speech processing, image and multidimensional signal processing, Image analysis and processing, Image and Multimedia applications, Real-time multimedia signal processing, Computer vision, Emerging signal processing areas, Remote Sensing, Signal processing in education. Industrial Informatics: Industrial applications of neural networks, fuzzy algorithms, Neuro-Fuzzy application, bioInformatics, real-time computer control, real-time information systems, human-machine interfaces, CAD/CAM/CAT/CIM, virtual reality, industrial communications, flexible manufacturing systems, industrial automated process, Data Storage Management, Harddisk control, Supply Chain Management, Logistics applications, Power plant automation, Drives automation. Information Technology, Management of Information System : Management information systems, Information Management, Nursing information management, Information System, Information Technology and their application, Data retrieval, Data Base Management, Decision analysis methods, Information processing, Operations research, E-Business, E-Commerce, E-Government, Computer Business, Security and risk management, Medical imaging, Biotechnology, Bio-Medicine, Computer-based information systems in health care, Changing Access to Patient Information, Healthcare Management Information Technology. Communication/Computer Network, Transportation Application : On-board diagnostics, Active safety systems, Communication systems, Wireless technology, Communication application, Navigation and Guidance, Vision-based applications, Speech interface, Sensor fusion, Networking theory and technologies, Transportation information, Autonomous vehicle, Vehicle application of affective computing, Advance Computing technology and their application : Broadband and intelligent networks, Data Mining, Data fusion, Computational intelligence, Information and data security, Information indexing and retrieval, Information processing, Information systems and applications, Internet applications and performances, Knowledge based systems, Knowledge management, Software Engineering, Decision making, Mobile networks and services, Network management and services, Neural Network, Fuzzy logics, Neuro-Fuzzy, Expert approaches, Innovation Technology and Management : Innovation and product development, Emerging advances in business and its applications, Creativity in Internet management and retailing, B2B and B2C management, Electronic transceiver device for Retail Marketing Industries, Facilities planning and management, Innovative pervasive computing applications, Programming paradigms for pervasive systems, Software evolution and maintenance in pervasive systems, Middleware services and agent technologies, Adaptive, autonomic and context-aware computing, Mobile/Wireless computing systems and services in pervasive computing, Energy-efficient and green pervasive computing, Communication architectures for pervasive computing, Ad hoc networks for pervasive communications, Pervasive opportunistic communications and applications, Enabling technologies for pervasive systems (e.g., wireless BAN, PAN), Positioning and tracking technologies, Sensors and RFID in pervasive systems, Multimodal sensing and context for pervasive applications, Pervasive sensing, perception and semantic interpretation, Smart devices and intelligent environments, Trust, security and privacy issues in pervasive systems, User interfaces and interaction models, Virtual immersive communications, Wearable computers, Standards and interfaces for pervasive computing environments, Social and economic models for pervasive systems, Active and Programmable Networks, Ad Hoc & Sensor Network, Congestion and/or Flow Control, Content Distribution, Grid Networking, High-speed Network Architectures, Internet Services and Applications, Optical Networks, Mobile and Wireless Networks, Network Modeling and Simulation, Multicast, Multimedia Communications, Network Control and Management, Network Protocols, Network Performance, Network Measurement, Peer to Peer and Overlay Networks, Quality of Service and Quality of Experience, Ubiquitous Networks, Crosscutting Themes – Internet Technologies, Infrastructure, Services and Applications; Open Source Tools, Open Models and Architectures; Security, Privacy and Trust; Navigation Systems, Location Based Services; Social Networks and Online Communities; ICT Convergence, Digital Economy and Digital Divide, Neural Networks, Pattern Recognition, Computer Vision, Advanced Computing Architectures and New Programming Models, Visualization and Virtual Reality as Applied to Computational Science, Computer Architecture and Embedded Systems, Technology in Education, Theoretical Computer Science, Computing Ethics, Computing Practices & Applications

Authors are invited to submit papers through e-mail ijcsiseditor@gmail.com. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated by IJCSIS. Before submission authors should carefully read over the journal's Author Guidelines, which are located at <http://sites.google.com/site/ijcsis/authors-notes> .

© IJCSIS PUBLICATION 2021

ISSN 1947 5500

<http://sites.google.com/site/ijcsis/>